

ABSTRACT

This study explores the relationship between work-life balance (WLB), employee performance, and wellbeing across varied demographic groups and occupational contexts in the UK. A systematic literature review was conducted to establish a robust theoretical foundation and identify gaps in the existing WLB discourse. Building on this, the study adopted a quantitative, cross-sectional research design underpinned by a positivist paradigm. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed via online platforms, yielding 337 valid responses. The survey incorporated validated instruments adapted from previous studies to measure WLB, work-life conflict, enrichment, job satisfaction, and perceived wellbeing.

To analyse the data, several statistical techniques were employed using SPSS, including descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation, One-Way ANOVA, and Welch's ANOVA, with additional multi-response and cross-tabulation analyses to explore subgroup dynamics. The findings indicate a significant positive correlation between WLB and both employee wellbeing and job performance. Notably, while demographic variables such as age and parental status did not show statistically significant effects, structural and psychological factors – such as job autonomy, organisational support, and emotional resilience – emerged as key predictors. The coexistence of work-life conflict and enrichment in certain cases suggests the need for more integrative theoretical models.

These results underscore the importance of context-sensitive and person-centred HR strategies, including flexible work arrangements, wellbeing support, and leadership training. This research contributes to theoretical development by challenging traditional demographic assumptions and providing empirical support for the nuanced, multidimensional nature of WLB in modern workplaces.

Keywords: *Work-life balance, employee wellbeing, job performance, work-life conflict, enrichment, organisational support.*

The Impact of Work-Life Balance on Employee Performance and Wellbeing: A Comparative Study Across Age, Parental Status, and Work Contexts

Acknowledgements

The journey of completing this research and earning my Doctoral degree has been extremely long and challenging. First and foremost, I would like to express my deepest appreciation to my professors and supervisors, Dr. Jonathan Wilson and Dr. Ahmed Beloucif, for their invaluable guidance, insightful feedback, and unwavering support throughout my DBA journey. This research would not have been possible without their expertise and encouragement.

I am also sincerely grateful to my classmates and colleagues for their editorial assistance and thoughtful feedback during many late nights. A heartfelt thank you goes to all the participants who generously took the time to complete the questionnaires for this study, enabling me to stay on track and meet my deadlines.

Finally, and most importantly, I would like to thank my family, especially my parents and my husband, for their unconditional love, patience, and unwavering belief in me. Their emotional and practical support gave me the strength and motivation I needed throughout this demanding journey.

LINH PHAM

Table of Contents

CHAPTER 1	9
INTRODUCTION	9
1.1. Research overview	9
1.2. Study background	9
1.3. Rationales	10
1.3.1 Brexit and Labour Market Shifts.....	10
1.3.2 The Impact of Covid-19 on Work-Life Balance.....	11
1.3.3 Technological Disruptions and Work-Life Conflict.....	12
1.3.4 Changing Workforce Demographics.....	12
1.3.5 Theoretical rationale.....	13
1.4. Industry analysis of financial services in the UK	14
1.5. Research aim, research objectives, and research question	17
1.5.1. Research aim.....	17
1.5.2. Research objectives.....	17
1.5.3. Research questions.....	17
1.6. Hypotheses	17
CHAPTER 2	19
LITERATURE REVIEW	19
2.1. Introduction	19
2.2. Literature review strategy	20
2.3. Conceptualising work-life balance	23
2.3.1. Defining “work”, “life”, and “balance”.....	23
2.3.2. The evolution of work-life balance in contemporary workplaces.....	24
2.3.3. Dimensions of work-life balance.....	25
2.3.4. Indicators of work-life balance.....	27
2.4. Theoretical framework and rationale	27
2.4.1. Discrepancy theory.....	29
2.4.2. Compensation theory.....	31
2.4.3. Work-family enrichment theory.....	32
2.4.4. Boundary theory and boundary management.....	34
2.4.5. Job demand–resource (JD-R) model – Role of organisational resources.....	35
2.4.6. Summary of theoretical insights and relevance to current study.....	36
2.5. Demographic influences on work-life balance	36
2.5.1. Age and life stage.....	37
2.5.2. Parental status.....	37
2.6. Employment context and work-life balance	38
2.6.1. Sectoral differences in WLB.....	39
2.6.2. Employment type.....	39
2.7. Organisational support and WLB interventions	40
2.7.1. Work-life balance policies.....	40
2.7.2. Interventions and support mechanisms.....	41
2.8. Work-life balance and employee outcomes	41
2.8.1. Employment performance.....	41
2.8.2. Job attitudes and satisfaction.....	42
2.8.3. Wellbeing and mental health.....	42
2.8.4. Key indicators of WLB.....	43

2.9.	Conceptual framework.....	45
2.10.	Literature gap.....	48
2.11.	Conclusion	49
CHAPTER 3.....		51
METHODOLOGY.....		51
3.1.	Introduction.....	51
3.2.	Research philosophy	54
3.2.1.	Positivism.....	54
3.2.2.	Interpretivism	55
3.2.3.	Discussions.....	56
3.3.	Research design and research approach	57
3.3.1.	Quantitative research design	58
3.3.2.	Types of quantitative research design	60
3.3.3.	Deductive approach and inductive approach	62
3.4.	Research strategy	64
3.5.	Questionnaire design	67
3.6.	Sampling	70
3.7.	Data collection	73
3.7.1.	Data collection methods.....	73
3.7.2.	Data collection procedures.....	75
3.8.	Data analysis	77
3.9.	Conclusion	79
CHAPTER 4.....		81
FINDINGS.....		81
4.1.	Introduction.....	81
4.2.	Reliability and validity testing.....	81
4.3.	Demographic profile of respondents.....	82
4.4.	Descriptive statistics	82
4.5.	The significance of work-life balance at the workplace	83
4.6.	The overall WLB through life stage	92
4.7.	The influences of work-life conflict on employees' job attitudes and wellbeing.....	97
4.7.1.	The influences of work-life conflict on employees' job attitudes	97
4.7.2.	The influences of work-life conflict on employees' wellbeing.....	99
4.8.	The influences of work-life enrichment on employees' job attitudes and wellbeing.....	102
4.9.	Employees' recommendations for better WLB at workplaces.....	104
CHAPTER 5.....		109
DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS.....		109
5.1.	The importance of work-life balance at workplace	109
5.2.	Work-life balance and life stage	110
5.3.	Work-life conflict and job attitudes	111
5.4.	Work-life conflict and wellbeing	112
5.5.	Work-life enrichment and job attitudes	114

5.6. Employee recommendations for better work-life balance	115
5.7. Summary of hypotheses testing	116
CHAPTER 6	118
IMPLICATIONS TO THEORY AND PRACTICE, AND BUSINESS/MANAGEMENT	118
6.1. Introduction	118
6.2. Implications to theory	118
6.3. Implications to practice and business/management	124
6.4. Specific Applications to Theory.....	127
6.5. Specific applications into the human resources management	129
CHAPTER 7	133
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	133
7.1. Conclusion	133
7.1.1. Research objectives	133
7.2.2. Theoretical Contributions.....	134
7.2.3. Limitations	135
7.2.4. Summary	136
7.2. Recommendations	136
7.2.1. Recommendations for Practice	136
7.2.2. Recommendations for Future Research	137
REFERENCES	140
APPENDIX A	154
Section 2. Work History	156
Section 3. Biographical Information	157
APPENDIX B	158
Participant Information Sheet	158
Consent Form	160

List of tables

<i>Table 2.1. Key literature (Source: Generated by the researcher)</i>	21
<i>Table 3. 1. Research method for this study</i>	52
<i>Table 3. 2. Summary of constructs, measurement items, and sources</i>	69
<i>Table 3. 3. Different types of survey</i>	75
<i>Table 4.1. Correlations between the overall WLB and perceived difficulty of WLB</i>	83
<i>Table 4.2. Test of homogeneity of variances between the overall WLB and ES</i>	84
<i>Table 4.3. Welch's ANOVA test results for overall WLB across ES</i>	84
<i>Table 4.4. Games-Howell post hoc test results for overall work-life balance (WLB) across employment status</i>	86
<i>Table 4.5. Welch's ANOVA test results for overall WLB across working experience (WE), working sector (WS), and most senior role (MSR)</i>	87
<i>Table 4.6. Games-Howell post hoc test results for WLB comparisons</i>	87
<i>Table 4.7. Limited leisure time</i>	90
<i>Table 4.8. Working overtime policies</i>	91
<i>Table 4.9. Test of homogeneity of variances between the overall WLB and AG</i>	92
<i>Table 4.10. ANOVA test of the overall WLB by AG</i>	93
<i>Table 4.11. ANOVA test of the overall WLB by PS</i>	94
<i>Table 4.12. Descriptive statistics of the overall WLB by parental status</i>	94
<i>Table 4.13. Test of homogeneity of variances between the overall WLB, the number or children, and their dependence on the parenting employees</i>	95
<i>Table 4.14. ANOVA test of the overall WLB by the number of children</i>	95
<i>Table 4.15. Reliability analysis for work-life conflict scale</i>	97
<i>Table 4.16. Correlations between WLC and JA</i>	97
<i>Table 4.17. Simple linear regression analysis predicting job attitudes from work-life conflict</i>	98
<i>Table 4.18. Test of homogeneity of variances between the WLC and wellbeing</i>	99
<i>Table 4.19. Welch's ANOVA results: Work-life conflict by wellbeing</i>	99
<i>Table 4.20. Standard One-way ANOVA results: Work-life conflict by wellbeing</i>	101
<i>Table 4.21. Correlations between WLE and JA</i>	102
<i>Table 4.22. Test of homogeneity of variances between the WLE and wellbeing</i>	103
<i>Table 4.23. ANOVA test of WLE by wellbeing</i>	103
<i>Table 4.24. Descriptive statistics of employees' evaluations of working overtime policies</i>	104
<i>Table 4.25. Descriptive statistics of employees' evaluations of life-related solutions to WLB</i>	106
<i>Table 4.26. Recommended solutions to employers for better WLB</i>	107
<i>Table 5.1. Summary of hypotheses testing</i>	115

List of figures

<i>Figure 1. 1. The countries with the worst work-life balance in 2019 (Statista, 2019)</i>	11
<i>Figure 1. 2. Employment rate by age group from 1998 to 2018 (Office for National Statistics, 2018)</i>	13
<i>Figure 1. 3. Economic outputs and jobs in the UK financial services sector (The UK Parliament, 2021)</i>	15
<i>Figure 1. 4. Number of employees in the financial services industry in the United Kingdom (UK) from 2001 to 2021 (Statista, 2022)</i>	15
<i>Figure 1.5. Industries with higher-than-average rates of stress, depression, or anxiety, averaged over the 3-year period: 2018/19–2020/21 (Health and Safety Executive, 2021)</i>	16
<i>Figure 2. 1. Prisma flow diagram systematic review (Source adapted with changes from Mora et al., 2017)</i>	21
<i>Figure 2. 2. Literature review strategy (Source: Generated by the researcher)</i>	23
<i>Figure 2. 3. Conceptual framework (Source: Generated by the researcher)</i>	45
<i>Figure 2. 4. Overall review of this research</i>	47
<i>Figure 3. 1. Research “onion” (Saunders et al. 2009, p.138)</i>	52
<i>Figure 3. 2. Inductive research (Blackstone, 2012)</i>	63
<i>Figure 3. 3. Deductive research (Blackstone, 2012)</i>	63
<i>Figure 3. 4. Main research strategies (Dillman et al., 2014)</i>	64
<i>Figure 3. 5. Data collection procedures</i>	76
<i>Figure 4. 1. Mean plots of the overall WLB by ES</i>	86
<i>Figure 4. 2. Mean plots of the overall WLB by WE</i>	88
<i>Figure 4. 3. Mean plots of the overall WLB by WS</i>	89
<i>Figure 4. 4. Mean plots of the overall WLB by MSR</i>	89
<i>Figure 4.5. Mean plots of the overall WLB by AG</i>	93
<i>Figure 4.6. Mean plots of the overall WLB by PS</i>	94
<i>Figure 4.7. Mean plots of the overall WLB by the number of children</i>	96
<i>Figure 4.8. Mean plot of “The demands of my work interfere with my family activities” by stress- related health status (Yes/No)</i>	100
<i>Figure 4.9. Mean plot of “I prioritise my job over my personal life” by Stress-related health status (Yes/No)</i>	101

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research overview

The first chapter of this research provides an overview of work-life balance (WLB) and its impact on employee performance and wellbeing across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments. It begins with background information on WLB, reviewing previous studies and identifying existing gaps that this study aims to address. The rationale for the research is then presented, including a comparison of work-life balance in the UK, often ranked among the countries with the poorest WLB with other international contexts. Furthermore, an industry-specific analysis is introduced, with a particular focus on the UK financial services sector. The chapter concludes by outlining the research questions, objectives, and hypotheses.

1.2. Study background

Researchers have long debated the concept of work-life balance (WLB), questioning whether individuals work to live or live to work (Bataineh, 2019). Kelliher et al. (2019) describe work and home as two central domains of human life, often in tension, particularly for women, who are disproportionately affected by work-family conflict (Kossek et al., 2010). Although "work-life balance" is broadly understood as managing professional and personal life roles (Gagnano et al., 2020), scholars continue to debate its precise definition (Greenhaus et al., 2006; Grzywacz & Carlson, 2007; Kalliath & Brough, 2008). Nonetheless, the core principle revolves around achieving a sustainable equilibrium between professional responsibilities and personal fulfilment.

Bataineh (2019) emphasised that work-life balance significantly influences job performance and overall employee wellbeing. Theoretical frameworks such as discrepancy theory (Wilcock & Wright, 1991), compensation theory (Khateeb, 2021), enrichment theory (Gagnano et al., 2022), boundary theory (Shi et al., 2022), and role conflict theory (Singh et al., 2018) have attempted to explain this dynamic. In light of the COVID-19 pandemic, rising work demands, and increased job uncertainty, maintaining WLB has become more difficult, with many employees experiencing heightened physiological and psychological stress (Barriga et al., 2021; Bataineh, 2019).

WLB is shaped by internal and external influences and is a crucial factor in determining employee performance globally (Kelliher et al., 2019). Among internal factors, demographic variables, particularly age group and parental status, have received extensive attention. Some studies suggest that younger employees and working parents experience more difficulty in maintaining WLB due to childcare responsibilities and early-career pressures (Kibande & Kyule, 2022; Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2019). Others have shown that older employees may enjoy better WLB due to more established routines or greater work autonomy (Otken & Erben, 2013). However, these outcomes are not always consistent, indicating the presence of mediating factors such as resilience, flexibility, and support systems.

In addition, work environment plays a significant role in shaping WLB. Employees in sectors such as hospitality, education, and healthcare face unique demands that complicate the pursuit of balance such as long hours, emotional labour, and physical presence. Task-related variables such as job characteristics (Carnevale & Hatak, 2020), work autonomy (Marques & Berry, 2021; De Clercq & Brieger, 2022), technological changes (Holden & Sunindijo, 2018), and performance expectations (Puspitasari & Darwin, 2021) can all significantly influence employees' experiences of work-life integration.

Further factors include motivation (Gogoi & Baruah, 2021), organisational constraints (Sheikh et al., 2018), competition (Caesens et al., 2017), and role conflicts (Ilies et al., 2018), each of which contributes to either conflict or enrichment between work and life domains. At the same time, job stress (Ahmad et al., 2021), ambiguity in roles (Charoensukmongkol & Puyod, 2021), and access to organisational resources (Zahoor et al., 2021) remain central concerns.

As demonstrated in research by Powell et al. (2019), work-family conflict negatively affects employees' WLB and psychological wellbeing. Wöhrmann et al. (2021) highlighted its relevance in multicultural workplaces, while Eddleston et al. (2019) linked effective WLB practices to higher organisational productivity. Warburton (2019) further noted that cultivating a positive WLB culture is key to talent retention. Therefore, while personal variables like age and parental status continue to influence WLB outcomes, it is equally important to address the structural and cultural dimensions of different work environments. There remains a critical need for further research to examine these complex, intersecting factors and their impact on wellbeing and performance.

1.3. Rationales

1.3.1 Brexit and Labour Market Shifts

Rising global competition pressures organisations to boost productivity, reduce labour costs, and remain competitive. Makoff (2017) notes that Brexit has affected both organisations and EU workers, with a post-Brexit labour shortage forcing British staff to work longer hours as EU workers left the UK in January 2021 (Morris, 2019). CIPD (2019) reports that 59% of private companies may increase salaries to attract skilled workers. To cut costs, organisations often reduce staff and increase workloads, leading to job insecurity and negatively affecting employee well-being, as many feel pressured to work longer hours to keep their jobs and support their families. Brexit caused UK businesses to cut investment, reducing productivity by 2-5% (Giles, 2019). Consequently, employees may struggle with work-life balance due to longer hours aimed at meeting employer expectations and securing their jobs (Sturges & Guest, 2004).

1.3.2 The Impact of Covid-19 on Work-Life Balance

According to UNI Equal Opportunities survey (2020), the Covid-19 pandemic significantly disrupted work-life balance globally. Over 5,000 respondents - 64% women, 35% men, and 1% others – from countries like China, Italy, Spain, and France reported major life changes. Maintaining a healthy work-life balance during lockdown proved challenging for many employees. Martin (2018) revealed that Britain has the “worst” work-life balance in Western Europe, with longer working hours, less annual leave, and lower overall happiness. Over 12% of British employees work more than 50 hours a week. Similarly, BBC (2019) reported that UK full-time workers average 42.5 hours weekly – above the European average of 41.2. In comparison, workers in Spain average 38.6 hours, and in the Netherlands just 34.9.

Figure 1. 1. The countries with the worst work-life balance in 2019 (Statista, 2019)

As shown in the 2019 data, the UK had the poorest work-life balance compared to countries like the US, Australia, and Japan (Statista, 2019). Bird (2019) reported that 31% of UK employees lost sleep due to work stress, and half believed their employers should do more to support work-life balance. This issue has become more prominent due to shifts in workplaces, demographics, and family structures (ONS, 2018).

1.3.3 Technological Disruptions and Work-Life Conflict

Technological advancements and globalisation have increased work-life conflict and stress, drawing more attention to these issues (Holden & Sunindijo, 2018). Technology, like computers and smartphones, enables work anytime and anywhere (Akter, 2019), leading to longer hours and reduced personal time (Holden & Sunindijo, 2018). However, technology can also help manage work-life balance (Holden & Sunindijo, 2018). Global competition has raised the demand for flexibility and longer hours, intensifying work-life conflict (Kalliath et al., 2017). The term "work-family" initially focused on balancing work and family responsibilities (Kelliher et al., 2019), often addressing female employees' childcare needs (Sirgy & Lee, 2018). As understanding grew that all employees have lives outside of work, the term "work-life" gained prominence (Leslie et al., 2019), including both those with and without families (Meutia & Mauliza, 2022). Some researchers use "work-family" more broadly (Kaufman, 2018). Most research has focused on paid work, with less attention to non-work activities like housework (Oludayo et al., 2018), though Perry and Hammer (2017) suggest "life" involves multiple roles, such as family or volunteering (Kaufman, 2018). The United Kingdom is a strong hub for financial services (Hutton and Shalchi, 2021). In 2019, the financial sector contributed 6.9% (£132 billion) to the national GDP (UK Parliament, 2021), with employment in the sector rising to around 1.1 million in 2020 (Statista, 2020). However, work overload has increased stress, leading to personal and family issues (Hendrie, 2018). As work-life balance becomes crucial, it is essential to create workplace cultures that promote it, making jobs more appealing to attract and retain talented employees (Warburton, 2019). Research into how work-life balance affects employee performance and wellbeing is vital for fostering a positive organisational culture.

1.3.4 Changing Workforce Demographics

Over the past few decades, there has been a significant shift in the labour market and family roles, with the traditional male "breadwinner" model evolving into dual-earner and single-parent families (Rooney and Gray, 2019). The employment rate for females has surged from 11.8% to 73.7% by 2017 (Office for National Statistics, 2017). Additionally, the UK's

population is ageing, with the employment rate for those over 50 rising, and by 2042, over 24% of residents will be 65 or older, up from 18% in 2016 (Department for Work and Pensions, 2018; Office for National Statistics, 2018).

Figure 1. 2. Employment rate by age group from 1998 to 2018 (Office for National Statistics, 2018)

As shown in Figure 2.2, the labour market has shifted over the past 20 years, with an increase in older workers (Office for National Statistics, 2018). As the population ages, there is growing focus on the characteristics, attitudes, and work-life balance of older employees, particularly regarding their happiness, life satisfaction, and self-esteem. Economically, the ageing population poses challenges to national competitiveness, innovation, and the stability of the labour market. A key development in the UK labour market is the increase in the working-age population and the ageing workforce, with a third of employees expected to be over 50 by 2020 (Office for National Statistics, 2019).

1.3.5. Theoretical rationale

This paper aims to explore the root causes of work-life balance among UK employees, its impact on their wellbeing and satisfaction in a diverse workplace, and potential solutions for achieving a healthier work-life balance in the UK.

To explore the relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and employee outcomes, this study draws upon four key theoretical perspectives: discrepancy theory, compensation theory, work-family enrichment theory, and boundary theory. These models collectively offer a multidimensional understanding of how individuals manage competing demands across work

and personal domains, and how these dynamics influence wellbeing, job satisfaction, and performance.

The study of work-life balance has evolved through various conceptual models, each offering unique insights depending on the empirical context. However, the field lacks a universally accepted terminology or dominant theoretical framework, making the intersection of work and personal life conceptually complex (Bello & Tanko, 2020). Earlier theories such as spillover, resource drain, segmentation, facilitation, and integration have contributed to this evolving understanding (Khateeb, 2021). Of particular relevance to this study are the contrasting perspectives of role scarcity and role expansion, which address how multiple roles can either compete for limited personal resources or mutually enhance one another (Marks, 1977; Greenhaus and Powell, 2006).

- Discrepancy theory suggests that work-life imbalance arises when there is a gap between an individual's preferred and actual experience of balance, often resulting in dissatisfaction or stress (Edwards, 1996).
- Compensation theory posits that individuals who are unfulfilled in one domain (e.g., work) may seek satisfaction in another (e.g., family or leisure), which has implications for how organisations address employee disengagement (Edwards and Rothbard, 2000).
- Work-family enrichment theory highlights how positive experiences in one domain can improve the quality of life in another, suggesting that supportive work environments can foster broader wellbeing (Pak et al., 2022).
- Boundary theory is especially relevant in today's digital, flexible, and often remote work environment. It explains how individuals negotiate the borders between work and non-work roles. In this study, Boundary theory serves as the central theoretical framework, as it best captures the challenges UK employees face when navigating blurred boundaries in a post-COVID, technologically integrated work setting (Clark, 2000; Ashforth, Kreiner and Fugate, 2000).

Together, these frameworks underpin the study's hypotheses and provide a comprehensive foundation for examining the antecedents and consequences of work-life balance in a modern, diverse UK workplace.

1.4. Industry analysis of financial services in the UK

The UK financial services sector contributed £164.8 billion to GDP in 2020, accounting for 8.6% of total economic output, an increase from £132 billion (6.9%) in 2019 (UK

Parliament, 2021). In 2020, the sector ranked third in the OECD for economic output, with Luxembourg leading at 25%. The UK had 1.1 million financial services jobs in early 2021, making up 3.3% of total employment. Financial services exports were valued at £62 billion, with a £46 billion trade surplus. Figure 1.3 illustrates job distribution in the financial services sector, showing London with the highest number of jobs, and displays sector economic output from 1990 to 2019.

Figure 1. 3. Economic outputs and jobs in the UK financial services sector (The UK Parliament, 2021)

According to Figure 1.4, the number of employees in the UK financial services industry declined between 2001 and 2021. The financial crisis and the nationwide closure of bank branches caused employment to drop to around 1.1 million in 2010. Since then, the numbers have fluctuated between 1.1 and 1.15 million (Statista, 2022). In 2020, employment in the sector was estimated at over 1.1 million, which is lower than the pre-global recession figure of 1.2 million across all financial services subsectors.

Figure 1. 4. Number of employees in the financial services industry in the United Kingdom (UK) from 2001 to 2021 (Statista, 2022)

The finance industry is known for its challenging work-life balance due to long hours and intense competition. For example, one in three financial analysts work 80-90 hours a week (Butcher, 2021). Hendrie (2018) notes that while financial specialists earn above-average salaries and have growth potential, they face high stress levels and limited personal and family time. The global concern over work-life balance is reflected in the eFinancialCareers Stress Survey (2013), which surveyed 3,400 finance professionals across multiple regions. It found that 57% of UK respondents and 63% of French respondents reported increased stress levels in the past six months (Clark, 2013).

Figure 1.5. Industries with higher-than-average rates of stress, depression, or anxiety, averaged over the 3-year period: 2018/19–2020/21 (Health and Safety Executive, 2021).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, self-reported work-related stress, depression, and anxiety increased in industries like education and social work from 2018/19 to 2020/21 (Health and Safety Executive, 2021). The Labour Force Survey (2021) reported 822,000 cases of work-related stress in 2020/21, with a prevalence rate of 2,480 per 100,000 employees, higher than in 2018/19. Khateeb (2021) stressed the need for a work-life balance culture to attract and retain talent, as employees prefer flexible, low-stress environments.

This research draws on several theoretical perspectives to explore the impact of work-life balance (WLB) on employee performance and wellbeing. The discrepancy theory (Lawler, 1971) explains how a mismatch between desired and actual WLB can affect employee satisfaction, while compensation theory (Edwards & Rothbard, 2000) suggests that individuals may compensate for imbalance in one domain by investing more in another. The work enrichment theory (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006) supports the idea that positive experiences in one role can enhance performance in another. Finally, boundary theory (Ashforth, Kreiner &

Fugate, 2000) provides insight into how employees manage the separation or integration of work and personal life. Together, these frameworks offer a comprehensive understanding of WLB, particularly across different age groups, parental statuses, and employment sectors.

1.5. Research aim, research objectives, and research question

1.5.1. Research aim

This research aims to analyse the impact of work-life balance on employee performance and well-being across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments.

1.5.2. Research objectives

To examine the extent of the research phenomenon, the current study takes these following objectives:

- (1) To evaluate the significance of work-life balance in influencing employee performance and wellbeing.
- (2) To examine how work-life balance, including work-family conflict and enrichment, varies across different age groups and parental statuses.
- (3) To analyse the impact of varying levels of work-life conflict and enrichment on employees' attitudes and wellbeing.
- (4) To recommend strategies for improving work-life balance, tailored to employees' life stages and family responsibilities.

1.5.3. Research questions

In order to fulfil those objectives, the current research concentrates on answering the critical research question as follows.

How does work-life balance affect employee performance and their wellbeing across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments?

1.6. Hypotheses

As this research aimed to address one primary research question, the stated hypotheses were developed. Specifically, the researcher sought to examine the impact of work-life balance (WLB) on employee performance in the workplace. Accordingly, the following eight hypotheses were proposed:

H₁: There is a significant correlation between employees' overall work-life balance and their working sector.

H₂: There is a significant correlation between employees' overall work-life balance and their employment status.

H₃: Work-life balance varies significantly across different age groups.

H₄: Work-life balance varies significantly based on parental status.

H₅: There is a significant correlation between life interference with work and employees' job attitudes.

H₆: There is a significant correlation between employees' ability to set work-life boundaries and their job attitudes.

H₇: Taking extended holidays contributes to improved work-life balance.

H₈: Participating in stress-relieving social events and activities improves employees' work-life balance.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This chapter presents a critical review of existing literature related to the topic: *the impact of work-life balance on employee performance and wellbeing, with a comparative focus across age groups, parental status, and employment contexts*. Building on the research objectives and hypotheses outlined in the previous chapter, this review aims to establish a clear theoretical and empirical foundation for the study.

Work-life balance (WLB) has become a central concern in contemporary organisational research, particularly in response to shifting workforce demographics, increasing job demands, and evolving employee expectations. A growing body of literature suggests that achieving a satisfactory balance between professional responsibilities and personal life can significantly influence employee performance, job satisfaction, and overall wellbeing. However, the experience of work-life balance is not uniform; it varies considerably depending on individual life stage, family responsibilities, employment sector, and the availability of organisational support.

To explore these complexities, this chapter begins by conceptualising the core terms of “work”, “life”, and “balance”, followed by an overview of key dimensions and indicators of WLB. A subsequent section outlines and justifies the selection of several theoretical frameworks underpinning this research including discrepancy theory, compensation theory, work-family enrichment theory, boundary theory, and the Job Demand–Resource (JD-R) model – highlighting their relevance in explaining the relationship between work-life balance and employee outcomes. These theories provide the foundation for the study’s hypotheses and inform the interpretation of relationships between WLB and employee outcomes.

The subsequent sections examine how demographic and contextual factors particularly age, parental status, employment sector, and contract type which influence experiences of WLB. The role of organisational policies and culture is also considered, with particular attention to interventions aimed at improving balance, such as stress-relief activities and extended leave. Finally, the chapter reviews previous research on how WLB impacts performance, job attitudes, and wellbeing, and concludes with the development of a conceptual framework that integrates the key theoretical and empirical insights.

2.2. Literature review strategy

This study employs a systematic review using the PRISMA method (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis) for literature review, which is conducted systematically by adhering the accurate stages or research protocols. Elliott et al. (2017) defined a systematic review as a research technique that aims to assess, identify, and analyse all prior study findings related to a particular topic, specific research, or the most recent phenomenon of concern. As the researcher uses systematic reviews to synthesise relevant research findings, the information and facts are thorough and unbiased. The following steps are included in a systematic review: Developing research questions, carrying out systematic literature reviews, screening and choosing relevant research articles (Akhter et al., 2019). The PRISMA method for literature review in the current study is presented in Figure 2.1.

Following Mora et al. (2017), the literature search was conducted across multiple academic databases: Elsevier (Scopus), Emerald Insight, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and Harvard Business Review. An initial set of 250 articles was retrieved based on relevant keywords. These articles were then screened through title, abstract, and keyword analysis. Two inclusion criteria were applied to refine the selection:

- **IC1:** English Language – Only articles published in English were included to ensure clarity and avoid potential misinterpretations caused by language translation. This helped maintain consistency and quality in the review process.
- **IC2:** Focus on Behaviour, Performance, and Wellbeing in Organisational Contexts – Studies were required to specifically address at least one of the following areas: human behaviour, employee or organisational performance, or psychological/occupational wellbeing. This criterion ensured that the selected literature was directly aligned with the research objectives.

After applying these criteria, 150 articles remained and were reviewed in full to determine their eligibility for final inclusion. The PRISMA framework used to guide the literature review process is visually summarised in Figure 2.1

Figure 2. 1. Prisma flow diagram systematic review
(Source adapted with changes from Mora et al., 2017)

Table 2.1. Key literature (Source: Generated by the researcher)

Literature theme	Key authors	Focus area
Conceptual/Theoretical foundations	Greenhaus & Powell (2006), Edwards & Rothbard (2000), Ashforth et al. (2000), Bakker & Demerouti (2007), Lawler (1971)	Theoretical models such as enrichment, compensation, boundary, discrepancy, and JD-R frameworks.
Demographic influences on WLB	Kalliath & Brough (2008), Raja & Stein (2014), David (2019), McDonald III & Hatcher (2022)	How WLB varies by age, life stage, and parental status.
WLB and employee performance	Al-Alawi et al. (2021), De Clercq & Brieger (2022), Marques & Berry (2021), Bataineh (2019)	Relationship between WLB and outcomes like performance, satisfaction, and wellbeing.

Organisational support and interventions	Sonnentag & Fritz (2007), Kossek et al. (2011), Kaplan et al. (2017), Emre et al. (2021)	Impact of HR practices, holidays, and stress-relief interventions on improving WLB.
--	--	---

Table 2.1 presents a summary of the key literature selected for this study. These articles represent the final selection of sources remaining after the application of Inclusion Criterion 2 (IC2), which required a clear focus on behaviour, performance, and wellbeing in the context of work-life balance. The conclusion that WLB significantly affects employee performance and wellbeing, and that these effects are moderated by life stage, employment context, and organisational support. Therefore, all articles listed in the table represent the outcome of a refined selection process based on the relevance and empirical focus aligned with the research objectives. The literature is categorised into four thematic groups:

- Related theories (5 articles),
- Demographic influences on WLB (4 articles),
- Work-life balance and employee performance (4 articles), and
- Organisational support and interventions (4 articles).

The related theories group encompasses conceptual frameworks that serve as the theoretical backbone of this study. These include discrepancy theory, compensation theory, work-family enrichment theory, boundary theory, and the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model. Each of these frameworks contributes a distinct lens for understanding how individuals experience and manage the interface between work and personal life, and how these dynamics influence attitudes, wellbeing, and performance outcomes.

The articles within the work-life balance and employee performance category collectively highlight a consistent finding: WLB has a significant and measurable impact on job performance, engagement, satisfaction, and overall psychological wellbeing. Employees who report higher levels of work-life balance tend to demonstrate improved productivity, stronger organisational commitment, and lower burnout rates. Conversely, poor WLB is linked to presenteeism, decreased motivation, and increased turnover intentions. These findings affirm that work-life balance is not merely a personal or HR concern but a strategic organisational issue.

Figure 2. 2. Literature review strategy

(Source: Generated by the researcher)

This research analyses the impact of work-life balance on employee performance and their wellbeing. According to Figure 2.2, the 5 WH questions have been listed to build the strategy for this literature review which include “Who, What, Why, When, and Where”. Moreover, in order to develop this plan, it is necessary to answer the question “How”.

2.3. Conceptualising work-life balance

This section explores the foundational concepts that support the study of work-life balance (WLB). It begins by defining the terms “work”, “life”, and “balance”, and examines how the concept of WLB has developed in response to changing workplace dynamics. It also discusses the key dimensions of WLB and the indicators most commonly used to assess it in organisational research.

2.3.1. Defining “work”, “life”, and “balance”

The concepts of “work”, “life”, and “balance” have been widely debated in many ways across academic and professional contexts. “Work” is typically defined as formal, paid employment involving tasks, responsibilities, and goals within an organisational structure (Kelliher, Richardson and Boiarintseva, 2019). In contrast, “life” refers to personal domains outside of paid employment, including family, leisure, health, and social relationships (Sirgy

and Lee, 2018). The notion of “balance” does not imply equal time allocation but rather a subjective state in which individuals feel they are able to satisfactorily manage both domains without excessive conflict or strain (Allen, Cho and Meier, 2014). Importantly, this balance is dynamic and may vary depending on one’s career stage, family responsibilities, and personal values (Putri and Rachmawati, 2021). Contemporary scholars increasingly frame work-life balance as a state of wellbeing achieved when an individual can effectively meet work and life demands in a manner consistent with their goals and preferences (Lupu and Ruiz-Castro, 2021). As such, WLB is recognised not as a static ideal, but as an ongoing process shaped by contextual and individual factors.

Work-life balance (WLB) refers to an individual’s ability to effectively manage the demands of their professional responsibilities alongside personal and family life. While “work” typically denotes paid employment and job-related obligations, “life” encompasses a broader range of personal domains including family, leisure, health, and social relationships (Greenhaus and Allen, 2011). The notion of “balance” suggests a satisfactory or harmonious state where neither domain dominates at the expense of the other (Kalliath and Brough, 2008). However, WLB is a highly subjective construct, shaped by individual values, life stages, and organisational contexts (Guest, 2017).

2.3.2. The evolution of work-life balance in contemporary workplaces

Beauregard et al. (2020) expressed the view that the work-life interface is defined as the confluence of work and personal life, and the field of this academic study began in the late 1970s in the United States. Work-life balance occurred when there was a change in the demographic of the workforce with a rise in the number of women employees, single parents, and dual-earner parents, which led to an increasing concern about the wellbeing and quality of life of the workforce emerged (Kossek et al., 2010).

Theoretical research on work-life balance (WLB) in the United States emerged in the late 1970s, when concerns grew around job-related stress, reduced autonomy, and declining quality of life (O’Toole and Lawler, 2007). Many WLB initiatives were linked to equal employment legislation such as the Civil Rights Act and the Pregnancy Discrimination Act, which prompted organisations to adapt to changing workforce demographics (Edelman, 2016). Bianchi (2011) noted that age discrimination laws led to an increase in older employees, with over a third of the workforce managing eldercare, and around 15% caught in “sandwich” caregiving roles – supporting both children and elderly relatives (Kossek, Lewis and Hammer, 2010). These developments pushed employers to acknowledge the growing need for balancing work and caregiving, particularly among women.

In the UK, the term “work-life balance” gained prominence in the 1980s, driven by the Women’s Liberation Movement, which advocated for flexible working arrangements and maternity rights (Raja and Stein, 2014). David (2019) argued that men were largely free to pursue careers without domestic responsibilities, while Jolly (2019) highlighted that women were expected to manage both paid work and household duties. Although progress was limited, the movement did prompt shifts in cultural norms, gender roles, and the recognition of WLB as a broader social issue.

The concept of work-life balance (WLB) has changed significantly over the past few decades, reflecting wider changes in workforce demographics, technology, and organisational practices. Initially, WLB was understood largely in terms of time management, with the emphasis on reducing work hours to allow space for personal responsibilities (Lewis et al., 2007). However, as the nature of work shifted towards increased flexibility, remote working, and performance-based outcomes, the focus moved beyond simply managing time to managing boundaries, wellbeing, and role satisfaction (Kosseck and Lambert, 2005). The rise of dual-earner households, diverse family structures, and 24/7 connectivity has blurred the traditional boundaries between work and non-work domains, making balance more complex and more personal (Felstead and Henseke, 2017). Contemporary WLB models currently incorporate not only conflict but also enrichment, acknowledging that positive experiences in one role can enhance the other (Greenhaus and Powell, 2006). Moreover, WLB is no longer seen as solely an individual’s responsibility; it is increasingly framed as a shared concern involving employers, policymakers, and societal norms (Clarke and Holdsworth, 2017). This evolving perspective highlights the need for adaptable, inclusive, and sustainable work-life strategies tailored to diverse employee needs.

2.3.3. Dimensions of work-life balance

In current years, there has been an augmented concern in work-family interfaces in the literature on human resource management, particularly with regard to the causes and effects of conflict between work and life (Eddleston et al., 2019). A comprehensive understanding of the dimensions of work-life balance (WLB) is essential in establishing the theoretical grounding for the hypotheses proposed in this study. The first key dimension – work-to-life and life-to-work conflict – is particularly pertinent to hypotheses **H1** and **H2**, which explore whether employees’ overall WLB differs according to their working sector and employment status. Research indicates that employees in certain sectors, such as healthcare or finance, often report higher levels of work-to-life conflict due to long hours, inflexible schedules, or emotional labour (Byron, 2005). Similarly, full-time and permanent employees may face greater pressure

to meet performance targets or remain available outside of contracted hours, potentially leading to reduced balance compared to part-time or contract-based workers. This dimension of conflict also plays a critical role in **H3 and H4**, which examine whether WLB varies by age and parental status. Life stage influences how individuals perceive and experience conflict – young professionals may prioritise career development, while employees with children or caregiving responsibilities may encounter heightened life-to-work conflict due to competing domestic demands (Hammer et al., 2005). These experiences may also differ by gender, adding another layer of complexity to demographic comparisons of WLB.

Alongside conflict, the dimension of enrichment helps to explain the positive effects that one domain can have on another, a concept especially relevant to **H3, H4, and H8**. For example, employees with fulfilling family lives may bring enhanced emotional regulation or interpersonal skills to the workplace, thereby enriching their professional experience (Greenhaus and Powell, 2006). Conversely, organisations that offer enriching social activities or stress-relieving initiatives (as explored in **H8**) contribute positively to employee wellbeing, leading to improved perceptions of balance. The boundary management dimension is also fundamental to this research, as it underpins **H6**, which posits that employees who are able to effectively manage the boundaries between work and personal life report more positive job attitudes. Boundary management preferences – whether an individual prefers segmentation or integration – can significantly impact their perceived control and satisfaction. When these preferences are misaligned with job expectations, such as in roles with high flexibility but low structure, employees may experience role confusion and stress (Kreiner, 2006).

Additionally, **H5**, which proposes a relationship between life interference and job attitudes, is supported by findings on how persistent life-to-work conflict leads to emotional exhaustion, disengagement, and even intention to quit (Frone, 2003). Finally, the role of recovery and organisational support, which intersects with both the enrichment and conflict dimensions, is directly connected to **H7 and H8**. Taking extended holidays (H7) has been shown to facilitate psychological detachment from work, enabling recovery from stress and restoring energy levels, which contributes to improved work-life balance upon return (Sonnentag and Fritz, 2007). Similarly, participation in stress-relieving workplace activities enhances morale and fosters a sense of organisational care, which can mitigate burnout and improve overall balance (Brough et al., 2020). Altogether, these dimensions not only inform the operationalisation of WLB in this study but also provide a framework for understanding how different personal, professional, and organisational variables influence perceptions of balance. The theoretical alignment between these dimensions and the proposed hypotheses

strengthens the study's conceptual model and ensures that the research questions are rooted in robust and multidimensional academic perspectives.

2.3.4. Indicators of work-life balance

Work-life balance (WLB) is a multidimensional concept, and its indicators often vary depending on the context of work, life stage, and individual priorities. Common indicators include the ability to manage time effectively between work and personal life, low levels of work-family conflict, high levels of job satisfaction, and general wellbeing (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011). Quantitative assessments frequently rely on perceived balance scales, which measure individuals' self-reported ability to fulfil both work and personal responsibilities without one domain significantly interfering with the other (Fisher-McAuley et al., 2003). Other indicators include reduced levels of stress and burnout, greater job engagement, and higher organisational commitment (Clark, 2000). From an organisational perspective, low absenteeism, high retention, and employee satisfaction surveys may also serve as indirect indicators of WLB. These markers help researchers and practitioners assess whether employees feel adequately supported in balancing their work and non-work lives, which in turn can influence performance and wellbeing outcomes (Kossek et al., 2011).

2.4. Theoretical framework and rationale

To explore the relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and employee outcomes, this study draws upon five key theoretical perspectives. These theories collectively provide a multidimensional understanding of how individuals manage competing demands across work and personal domains, and how such dynamics influence wellbeing, job satisfaction, and performance. Numerous work-life theories have contributed to a more nuanced understanding of the work-life interface, each offering unique insights depending on the empirical context. However, studying the intersection between work and personal life has been conceptually challenging due to the absence of universally accepted terminology and theoretical consistency, with no single dominant framework guiding the field (Submitter, Bello and Tanko, 2020).

Historically, a variety of frameworks have emerged to explain the interaction between work and family life, including spillover, compensation, work-family conflict, resource drain, enrichment, congruence, segmentation, facilitation, integration, and ecological models (Khateeb, 2021). Among these, the two contrasting perspectives of role scarcity and role expansion are particularly relevant to the current research, as this study integrates elements of both views in its examination of how multiple roles may either compete for or enhance personal and professional resources. Additionally, border and boundary theories are essential for

understanding how individuals manage role transitions – especially in contexts such as remote work, which became prominent during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on this theoretical landscape, the current study is primarily guided by four key frameworks: Discrepancy theory, Compensation theory, Work-Family Enrichment theory, and boundary theory. Together, these models offer a comprehensive lens through which to interpret the various antecedents and consequences of work-life balance, and they underpin the hypotheses tested in this research.

To justify the adoption of these frameworks, the following section outlines each theory's relevance to the study's focus and explains how, together, they provide a robust foundation for analysis. To ensure conceptual clarity and theoretical rigour, this study adopts a multi-theoretical framework to examine the complex relationship between work-life balance (WLB), employee performance, and wellbeing. The process of identifying relevant theories began with a comprehensive review of existing literature, guided by the research objectives and the need to understand the mechanisms through which WLB influences individual and organisational outcomes.

Key theories were selected based on their relevance to the research focus and their explanatory power in accounting for the interactions between work and non-work domains. The following frameworks were deemed most appropriate:

- Discrepancy theory explains how perceived mismatches between an individual's desired and actual levels of work-life balance can lead to dissatisfaction, stress, and negative work attitudes (Porter and Lawler, 1968; Edwards and Shipp, 2007). This theory is particularly useful in evaluating employees' subjective experiences of imbalance and perceived injustice.
- Compensation theory posits that individuals attempt to compensate for deficiencies in one domain (e.g., work) by seeking fulfilment in another (e.g., family or leisure) (Edwards and Rothbard, 2000). This framework helps explain the adaptive behaviours and coping strategies individuals employ to maintain overall balance.
- Work-Family enrichment theory introduces a more optimistic perspective by asserting that resources, experiences, or skills gained in one life domain (e.g., work) can enhance performance or satisfaction in another (e.g., family) (Greenhaus and Powell, 2006). This theory aligns with research that emphasises the reciprocal benefits of well-integrated roles.
- Boundary theory and the broader concept of work-life boundary management explore how individuals create, negotiate, and maintain the boundaries between their professional and personal lives (Ashforth, Kreiner and Fugate, 2000; Clark, 2000).

These frameworks are particularly relevant in understanding the influence of demographic and contextual factors such as age, parental responsibilities, and employment type on WLB strategies.

- Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model provides a structural lens for understanding how job demands (e.g., workload, emotional strain) and job or personal resources (e.g., autonomy, social support) interact to influence burnout, engagement, and overall wellbeing (Demerouti et al., 2001; Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). This model is widely applicable across sectors and supports the study’s comparative focus on varied employment contexts.

The rationale for selecting these particular frameworks lies in their collective ability to address both the challenges and enabling conditions associated with work-life balance. Each theory contributes a distinct yet complementary lens through which to interpret how WLB affects employee outcomes, accounting for individual variation, organisational structures, and broader life circumstances.

Together, these perspectives equip the study with a robust conceptual foundation to interpret how organisational demands, personal contexts, and boundary dynamics converge to shape employees’ experiences of work-life balance, their performance, and their overall wellbeing.

2.4.1. Discrepancy theory

Many types of research have been done on discrepancy theory to study job satisfaction (Vasumathi, 2018; Kelliher, Richardson, & Boiarintseva, 2019). Discrepancy theory is one of the most prevalent theories used to define job satisfaction (Submitter et al., 2020). According to Lawler (1971), discrepancy theory explains satisfaction or dissatisfaction as arising from the difference between what individuals expect and what they actually experience in a given domain. Vasumathi (2018) applied discrepancy theory to managerial contexts, proposing that job satisfaction is influenced more by the alignment between expected and actual job outcomes than by the fulfilment of basic needs. Similarly, Talukder (2019) argued that employees report higher levels of satisfaction when their job performance and rewards exceed their initial expectations. According to Yadav et al. (2022), the most significant characteristics or conditions conducive to job satisfaction include: a mentally challenging job that a person can successfully adapt to; individual interest in the work itself; tasks that are not overly physically exhausting; incentives for performance that are informed and aligned with the individual's ambitions; working conditions that meet a person’s physical requirements and support the

achievement of work-related goals; employees with high self-esteem; and supportive workplace agents who assist individuals in achieving values such as meaningful work, fair pay, and career advancement, whose underlying principles align with the employee's own values, and who minimise role conflict and ambiguity.

On the other hand, Inegbedion et al. (2020) stated that job satisfaction primarily depends on whether employees hold positive or negative attitudes towards their jobs. Talukder (2019) defined attitude as an employee's emotional response such as satisfaction, indifference, or dissatisfaction towards a particular situation, object, or person. Job satisfaction, therefore, is the overall result of an employee's favourable or unfavourable attitude at a given point in time. While it may fluctuate between extremes, it typically stabilises at a relatively consistent level, which may be either positive or negative (Kim, 2019). According to Gragnano et al. (2020), job satisfaction is shaped by employees' perceptions of how effectively their job meets their personal and professional expectations. Their study is based on the notion that when individuals perceive a gap in their competence, they are motivated to learn, and the anxiety produced by the gap between what they know and what they need to know drives them to make the necessary effort to close it.

In the context of work-life balance (WLB), this theory is particularly useful for understanding how perceived mismatches such as between desired flexibility and actual working conditions can lead to frustration, emotional strain, and reduced wellbeing. Importantly, job satisfaction is not only a consequence of WLB but also a key predictor of it. When employees are satisfied with their work conditions, for instance, manageable workloads, autonomy, fair rewards, and supportive management, they are more likely to perceive a greater sense of control over their time and energy, which contributes to a more positive work-life interface (Brough et al., 2020). Conversely, dissatisfaction with one's job can amplify the experience of conflict, as employees who are stressed or disengaged at work may have less capacity or motivation to engage meaningfully in their personal lives (Sirgy and Lee, 2018). Discrepancy theory thus provides a lens to interpret both how unmet expectations in the workplace can negatively affect balance, and how increasing job satisfaction can buffer against perceived imbalance. This relationship is central to the current research's hypothesis **(H5)**, which proposes that life interference with work significantly influences employees' job attitudes. By applying discrepancy theory, the study can explore how aligning workplace conditions with employee expectations can improve both satisfaction and perceptions of balance.

2.4.2. Compensation theory

One of the key concepts in the work-family literature is compensation theory (Submitter et al., 2020). Compensation occurs when resources from one domain are used to fulfil the demands of another (Wood et al., 2020; Khateeb, 2021), functioning in a way that is similar to the buffering effect described in work-family enrichment theory (Greenhaus et al., 2006). Perrigino et al. (2018) described compensation as a mechanism by which one role can support another, particularly when individuals seek to offset a lack of positive experiences in one domain by engaging more deeply in the other. Their research highlights how individuals often draw emotional or cognitive resources from their home life to manage work pressures, or vice versa, reinforcing the adaptive role of compensation in achieving perceived balance.

These findings align with the research hypotheses, particularly:

- **H3:** Work-life balance varies significantly across different age groups.
- **H4:** Work-life balance varies significantly based on parental status.
- **H5:** There is a significant correlation between life interference with work and employees' job attitudes.
- **H6:** There is a significant correlation between employees' ability to set work-life boundaries and their job attitudes.

This theory is particularly relevant to **Hypotheses 3 and 4**, which investigate whether work-life balance varies across different age groups and parental statuses. Employees at different life stages often face unique challenges that influence how they experience and respond to imbalance. Younger employees without children may be more inclined to compensate for a lack of social fulfilment outside work by investing in career development, while older employees or those with parental responsibilities may compensate for work-related stress by prioritising family engagement (Clark, Michel and Baltes, 2014; Wayne et al., 2017; Zhang, Chen and Fan, 2023). Perrigino et al. (2018) found that compensation frequently arises from a lack of positive experiences in one domain and serves as a buffer that helps individuals maintain psychological wellbeing. Thus, demographic variables such as age and family structure shape not only the experience of balance but also the compensatory strategies individuals use to restore it.

Additionally, compensation theory provides insight into **Hypotheses 5 and 6**, which focus on the relationship between work-life interference, boundary-setting, and job attitudes. When personal responsibilities interfere with work, employees may feel compelled to compensate by reinforcing professional boundaries or overperforming in the workplace to maintain a sense of competence and control (Wood et al., 2020). This behaviour can either

mitigate or exacerbate stress, depending on the alignment between personal values and role expectations (Gunawan, Sudarmiatin and Churiyah, 2024). Compensation, therefore, is closely linked to both boundary management preferences and perceived job satisfaction. As Astuti, Prabowo and Puspitasari (2023) suggest, when employees perceive imbalance, they often respond through increased work engagement or by withdrawing from personal obligations, depending on which domain is more valued or rewarding. These compensatory responses serve as a coping mechanism that helps individuals adapt to conflicting demands across life domains. Wood et al. (2020) argue that compensation acts as a functional strategy, particularly in high-demand environments, helping employees psychologically offset deficits and sustain a positive work identity. The theory therefore helps to explain variations in work-life balance outcomes by linking individual coping responses to broader demographic and role-related factors.

In summary, compensation theory offers a nuanced explanation for how individuals manage imbalance by redirecting their efforts between life domains. It supports the argument that work-life balance is not solely dependent on organisational structures or policies but is also shaped by personal adaptation strategies and psychological coping mechanisms (Edwards and Rothbard, 2000; Gunawan, Sudarmiatin and Churiyah, 2024). This perspective reinforces the importance of considering individual agency and subjective evaluations when assessing how employees maintain or restore equilibrium between work and personal life (Astuti, Prabowo and Puspitasari, 2023). By applying this theory, the current study can better understand the compensatory behaviours of individuals at different life stages and in varying roles, and how these behaviours influence perceptions of balance, satisfaction, and wellbeing.

2.4.3. Work-family enrichment theory

Work-family enrichment theory (WFET) offers a strengths-based perspective on the relationship between work and personal life, suggesting that experiences and resources acquired in one domain can positively enhance functioning and wellbeing in the other (Keeney et al., 2013). First conceptualised by Greenhaus and Powell (2006), the theory asserts that enrichment occurs when resources such as skills, psychological resilience, or social support gained in one role improve performance or satisfaction in another. This conceptual framework challenges traditional work-family conflict models by highlighting the potential for work and non-work domains to complement rather than compete with each other (Wayne et al., 2017).

Many scholars have expanded and nuanced this perspective. Keeney et al. (2013) emphasise that enrichment processes are not limited to emotional or cognitive domains, but also involve behavioural mechanisms – such as emotional regulation, time management and leadership skills – that can be transferred across life domains. Similarly, Zhang, Chen and Fan

(2023) found that enrichment significantly predicts job satisfaction and engagement, particularly when mediated by organisational support and psychological capital. These findings are consistent with Rofcanin et al. (2019), who emphasise the role of inclusive workplace practices – such as supportive leadership and family-friendly policies – as catalysts for enrichment, particularly in diverse or multigenerational workforces.

In contrast, scholars aligned with the work-family conflict perspective – such as Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) – argue that engagement in one domain often detracts from the other due to the finite nature of time and energy. While conflict theory assumes a zero-sum relationship between roles, WFET proposes a bidirectional and potentially synergistic interaction. Wayne et al. (2017) highlight that individuals may experience both enrichment and conflict simultaneously, depending on their personal circumstances and role demands. These theories are thus complementary, and together offer a more holistic understanding of the complexities of work-life balance.

WFET is particularly relevant to this study's focus on how employee wellbeing and job satisfaction are influenced not only by the reduction of conflict but by the presence of enriching experiences. Skills such as communication and emotional regulation developed in the workplace may enhance family life, while emotional support from home can improve productivity and engagement at work (Keeney et al., 2013). This dynamic is especially important when examining how work-life balance differs across age groups (**H3**) and parental status (**H4**). Research shows that individuals with caregiving responsibilities may draw meaning and emotional strength from family roles that positively impact their work engagement (Wayne et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the theory also supports **Hypothesis 8 (H8)**, which proposes that participation in workplace social events or stress-relief activities enhances work-life balance. Organisational interventions that promote enrichment – such as wellness programmes, inclusive team-building activities, and flexible scheduling – can increase psychological resources that spill over into personal life, enhancing resilience and overall wellbeing. As Rofcanin et al. (2019) note, such practices not only reduce stress but also improve perceptions of organisational support and commitment.

In summary, work-family enrichment theory offers a constructive lens through which to explore the interaction between personal and professional roles. It reinforces the idea that work-life balance is not solely about reducing conflict but also about fostering positive synergy between domains. Applied to this study, WFET provides a robust framework for analysing how enrichment contributes to performance, wellbeing, and life satisfaction, and how these outcomes may vary across different life stages and personal roles.

2.4.4. Boundary theory and boundary management

Boundary theory, developed by Ashforth, Kreiner and Fugate (2000), explores how individuals create and maintain boundaries between work and non-work roles, arguing that such boundaries are critical for minimising inter-role conflict and promoting psychological wellbeing. People vary in their boundary preferences, with some favouring segmentation – maintaining clear separations between domains – and others preferring integration, where work and personal roles are more fluid and overlapping. These preferences can significantly influence how individuals experience work-life balance (Clark, 2000). This theory also considers the ease and frequency of transitions between roles and highlights how individuals construct and maintain boundaries to create structure and reduce ambiguity in each domain (Submitter et al., 2020; Althammer et al., 2021).

While Ashforth et al. (2000) frame boundaries as fluid constructs negotiated daily, Clark (2000) adds that successful boundary management depends on how permeable and flexible borders are, and how much control individuals have over those borders. She emphasises the role of “border-keepers” (e.g. supervisors or family members) in enabling or constraining individuals’ ability to switch effectively between roles. In contrast, Kreiner (2006) takes a person-environment fit perspective, arguing that satisfaction is highest when there is alignment between an individual’s preferred boundary style and the demands of their work environment. For instance, segmenters may thrive in jobs with clear work hours, while integrators may perform better in flexible roles.

The growing prevalence of remote work and digital connectivity has further blurred the lines between work and life, prompting researchers like Derks et al. (2016) to focus on digital boundary control. Their findings show that when employees feel unable to disconnect (e.g. through constant smartphone notifications), they experience higher emotional exhaustion. This aligns with Kossek et al. (2012), who classify employees into distinct boundary management profiles (e.g., “fusion lovers” vs. “separators”) and highlight that organisational norms, leadership expectations, and technology use can either facilitate or hinder boundary setting.

These frameworks collectively inform **Hypothesis 5 (H5)**, which proposes that interference from personal life into work negatively affects job attitudes, and **Hypothesis 6 (H6)**, which links an employee’s ability to manage boundaries to overall job satisfaction. For example, employees who prefer segmentation but are unable to disconnect from work due to workplace expectations or caregiving duties may experience greater stress and dissatisfaction (Allen et al., 2018). In contrast, those who can align their preferred boundary strategy with actual job demands often report improved wellbeing and engagement.

Moreover, boundary strategies are not uniform across populations. For instance, younger workers or those without children may be more inclined towards integration for its flexibility, while older workers or parents may prioritise segmentation to protect family time (Kossek et al., 2012; Kreiner, 2006). This variability underscores the need for boundary theory to be applied contextually, rather than assuming one-size-fits-all solutions. Therefore, understanding and supporting diverse boundary management styles is essential for fostering effective work-life balance policies.

2.4.5. Job demand–resource (JD-R) model – Role of organisational resources

The job demand–resource (JD-R) model, developed by Bakker and Demerouti (2007), provides a comprehensive framework for understanding employee wellbeing, motivation, and burnout by categorising all job characteristics into two overarching groups: job demands and job resources. Job demands refer to physical, psychological, social, or organisational aspects of a job that require sustained effort and are therefore associated with certain physiological and psychological costs (e.g., time pressure, role conflict, emotional demands). In contrast, job resources refer to those aspects of the job that help reduce demands, facilitate goal achievement, and stimulate personal growth and development (Bakker and Demerouti, 2017).

This model is especially relevant to understanding how organisations can proactively support work-life balance by offering sufficient resources to buffer high job demands. Resources may include supportive leadership, autonomy, feedback, and work-life initiatives such as flexible scheduling, wellness programmes, or extended paid leave. When job demands are high, the availability of resources can help prevent stress and burnout, creating a more sustainable work environment (Schaufeli and Taris, 2014). This is particularly applicable to **Hypothesis 7 (H7)**, which suggests that taking extended holidays can improve work-life balance. According to the JD-R model, time away from work allows employees to recover from accumulated demands, restoring energy and psychological wellbeing – a process known as psychological detachment (Sonnentag and Fritz, 2015).

Moreover, the JD-R model also supports **Hypothesis 8 (H8)**, which explores whether participation in stress-relieving social events and activities contributes to improved WLB. Such activities function as organisational resources that enhance social support, foster a sense of belonging, and reduce emotional strain. Recent studies show that when employees are given opportunities to engage in recreational or team-building events, they report higher levels of engagement and resilience, and lower levels of exhaustion (Kurtessis et al., 2017; McAllister et al., 2022). These positive outcomes reflect the resource-building effect described in the JD-

R model, where enriching activities increase employees' capacity to manage work-related stressors.

Importantly, the JD-R framework also accounts for individual differences in how job demands and resources interact. For example, employees with high personal resources such as optimism or emotional intelligence may benefit more from organisational support, while those in high-demand roles may rely more heavily on external resources like leave policies or social activities. Therefore, offering customisable and inclusive interventions not only mitigates strain but also fosters a culture that values employee wellbeing, which in turn contributes to long-term organisational performance.

2.4.6. Summary of theoretical insights and relevance to current study

The theoretical frameworks reviewed in this chapter provide a multidimensional foundation for understanding work-life balance (WLB) and its implications for employee performance and wellbeing. Discrepancy theory highlights the emotional and psychological consequences of unmet expectations, helping explain how job dissatisfaction arises when personal and professional needs are misaligned – supporting **H5**. Compensation theory expands this view by suggesting that individuals actively manage imbalance through role substitution, especially across different life stages, aligning with **H3 and H4**. Work-family enrichment theory adds a positive dimension, proposing that experiences in one domain can enhance the other, offering explanatory power for the potential benefits of family involvement, age diversity, and social activities (**H3, H4, and H8**). Meanwhile, boundary theory offers a structural lens, focusing on the segmentation or integration of roles and emphasising the importance of personal control and boundary fit, which directly informs **H5 and H6**. Finally, the job demand–resource (JD-R) model reinforces the significance of organisational-level support mechanisms, such as leave policies and stress-relief programmes, in managing demands and enhancing resilience – closely linked to **H7 and H8**. Collectively, these theories form a robust conceptual framework, allowing the current study to explore the complex interplay between personal demographics, organisational context, and work-life experiences. They also justify the development of targeted interventions that support employees across varying roles and life stages.

2.5. Demographic influences on work-life balance

Demographic characteristics play a significant role in shaping how individuals perceive and manage work-life balance (WLB). Factors such as age, gender, life stage, and parental status influence both the demands individuals face and the strategies they use to navigate work

and personal responsibilities. Scholars have long acknowledged that WLB is not a one-size-fits-all construct, but rather one that evolves across the lifespan and varies according to personal circumstances and societal expectations (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011).

2.5.1. Age and life stage

Age and life stage are widely recognised as key determinants of how individuals experience and manage work-life balance (WLB). As employees progress through different phases of their personal and professional lives, their values, responsibilities, and capacities for handling work and non-work demands often shift significantly. Younger workers, typically in early career stages, may prioritise career advancement, personal development, and financial stability, often accepting longer working hours or flexible boundaries between work and personal life as part of their professional growth trajectory (Zhang et al., 2023; Sirgy and Lee, 2018). In contrast, older employees tend to place greater value on stability, autonomy, and time for personal or family-related pursuits, making them more likely to seek roles that support segmentation and better work-life harmony (Lonska et al., 2022).

From a life stage perspective, individuals may face differing role conflicts and enrichment opportunities based on their family status, health, and caregiving responsibilities. For example, mid-career professionals are more likely to be “sandwiched” between the demands of caring for both children and ageing parents, increasing the complexity of their work-life boundaries (Kossek et al., 2010). Meanwhile, late-career employees may prioritise work-life balance as part of pre-retirement planning and psychological well-being, particularly in knowledge-based roles that afford greater flexibility (Brough et al., 2020).

These life stage transitions influence not only preferences for boundary management (e.g. segmentation vs. integration), but also the extent to which individuals are susceptible to work-life conflict or benefit from work-life enrichment. For example, younger workers may report fewer family-related interferences but higher pressures from organisational expectations, while older workers may struggle with physical demands or intergenerational caregiving. As such, **Hypothesis 3**, which posits that WLB varies significantly across age groups, is grounded in robust empirical evidence suggesting that chronological age and situational life stage both shape the experience and perception of balance (Clark et al., 2021; Guest, 2017).

2.5.2. Parental status

Parental status is a critical demographic factor that significantly influences how individuals perceive and manage work-life balance (WLB). Employees with children, particularly those with young dependents, often face intensified demands on their time, energy, and emotional bandwidth. These pressures can increase the likelihood of work-family conflict,

especially when organisational support is limited or job roles lack flexibility (Clark et al., 2021). Conversely, employees without children tend to experience fewer caregiving responsibilities, affording them greater autonomy in managing work and personal domains (Adisa et al., 2021).

Parental responsibilities typically require individuals to perform multiple roles simultaneously leading to heightened role conflict and psychological strain, for instance, caregiver, professional, and household manager. Beauregard and Henry (2009) observed that working parents, particularly mothers, are more likely to report lower job satisfaction and higher stress when work demands interfere with family responsibilities. However, supportive organisational practices, for example, flexible scheduling or paid family leave, can buffer these negative effects and enhance perceived balance (Allen et al., 2014).

The effects of parental status are not uniform and vary according to contextual factors such as the number and age of children, marital status, and availability of support networks (Kossek and Lee, 2016). For instance, single parents often report significantly higher levels of time-based conflict than dual-parent households. Interestingly, some scholars have noted that parenthood may also be a source of enrichment, whereby individuals derive meaning, purpose, and motivation from their caregiving role, which can positively influence work engagement and psychological wellbeing (Wayne et al., 2017).

In relation to **Hypothesis 4**, which proposes that WLB significantly differs between employees with and without children, the literature provides strong empirical grounding. Parental status not only alters the objective demands an individual faces but also shapes their subjective definition of what constitutes balance. Consequently, organisations seeking to promote inclusive and effective WLB strategies must recognise the diverse needs of employees based on family status.

2.6. Employment context and work-life balance

Employment context plays a crucial role in shaping work-life balance (WLB) outcomes, as the nature of a sector and the type of employment contract can significantly influence both the demands placed on employees and the resources available to manage them. The intensity of workloads, flexibility of working arrangements, and cultural expectations across different sectors and employment types can result in considerable variation in how employees experience and negotiate WLB. This part explores these dynamics in relation to **Hypothesis 1**, which suggests that WLB differs across working sectors, and **Hypothesis 2**, which proposes differences based on employment status.

2.6.1. Sectoral differences in WLB

Work-life balance can vary widely across sectors due to differences in work demands, organisational structures, and cultural expectations. Employees in the private sector often report longer working hours, increased performance pressure, and less predictable schedules, which may negatively impact their ability to maintain balance (Kelliher et al., 2019). In contrast, the public sector is typically associated with more stable and regulated work environments, often offering better access to family-friendly policies, paid leave, and flexible hours (Hofäcker and König, 2013).

Studies have shown that public sector workers are more likely to perceive their organisations as supportive of WLB, particularly due to formalised HR policies and unionised environments (Gregory & Milner, 2009). Conversely, employees in sectors such as hospitality, healthcare, or finance, where shift work or customer-facing roles are prevalent, often face heightened time-based and emotional demands, increasing the risk of work-life conflict (Lonska et al., 2022).

This variability supports **Hypothesis 1**, which posits that WLB is significantly associated with an employee's working sector. Sectoral culture, workload intensity, and access to supportive practices collectively shape the extent to which balance can be realistically achieved.

2.6.2. Employment type

Employment type – including distinctions between full-time, part-time, and contract-based work – also influences WLB experiences. Full-time employees may benefit from job security and greater access to organisational benefits, but are also more likely to face inflexible hours and greater work demands (Greenhaus and Allen, 2011). In contrast, part-time or temporary employees may enjoy more time flexibility, but they often lack job stability, benefits, and career advancement opportunities, all of which can negatively affect overall wellbeing and job satisfaction (Schieman and Glavin, 2008).

Research has highlighted that those in non-standard employment arrangements, such as freelance or zero-hour contracts, frequently struggle with boundary management due to blurred lines between work and home life (Kossek and Lautsch, 2012). However, some employees may choose such arrangements intentionally to better accommodate caregiving responsibilities or personal pursuits, indicating that employment type can influence WLB both positively and negatively depending on individual preferences and life circumstances.

In support of **Hypothesis 2**, the evidence suggests that employment status significantly shapes WLB outcomes by mediating access to organisational resources, control over time, and job-related expectations.

2.7. Organisational support and WLB interventions

Organisational support is a fundamental driver of employee work-life balance (WLB). Beyond individual coping strategies and demographic factors, the extent to which organisations proactively design and implement supportive policies significantly shapes employees' capacity to manage work and personal responsibilities. Employers who recognise WLB as a strategic priority are more likely to foster employee satisfaction, engagement, and retention (Allen et al., 2014). This section explores two key dimensions of organisational support – formal WLB policies and informal interventions or support mechanisms – each of which plays a critical role in promoting balance and wellbeing in the workplace.

2.7.1. Work-life balance policies

Kossek, Lewis, and Hammer (2010) stated that the term “work-family policies” was expanded in the popular culture in the 1980s, which refers to dependent care supports aiming at employees with the most visible non-work demands caring for children. Since then, the concept has expanded into a broader range of work-life balance (WLB) policies that support all employees in managing competing professional and personal responsibilities. These formal, structural measures commonly include flexible working arrangements (FWA), parental leave, compressed hours, telecommuting options, and job-sharing (Chung & Van der Lippe, 2020). Research consistently shows that the presence and accessibility of these policies contribute to improved perceptions of balance, reduced stress, and higher organisational commitment (Kossek and Michel, 2011).

However, access alone is not always sufficient – policy utilisation is often hindered by workplace culture, managerial attitudes, or fear of negative career implications (Lewis et al., 2007). In many corporate contexts, employees are reluctant to take advantage of leave entitlements or flexible options due to implicit expectations around presenteeism and professional ambition (Bailyn, 2011). As such, the mere existence of WLB policies must be accompanied by a supportive organisational climate that normalises their use without stigma.

In support of **Hypothesis 7**, which suggests that extended holidays or paid leave contribute to better WLB, several studies have highlighted the positive psychological outcomes associated with restorative time away from work. Recovery periods not only alleviate burnout and stress but also improve job performance and reduce absenteeism post-leave (de Bloom et

al., 2010). For employees with intensive work demands, structured time off is essential to restore cognitive and emotional resources, particularly when supported by leave policies that are well communicated and equitably enforced (Fritz and Sonnentag, 2006).

2.7.2. Interventions and support mechanisms

In addition to formal policies, many organisations implement informal support mechanisms aimed at fostering employee wellbeing. These include employee assistance programmes (EAPs), wellness initiatives, mental health training, social events, and stress-relief activities such as mindfulness workshops, on-site yoga, or recreational team-building events (Rofcanin et al., 2019). These interventions are designed not only to reduce stress but also to build social cohesion and psychological capital, particularly in high-demand or fast-paced environments.

Evidence shows that when employees participate in such activities – particularly those that are inclusive and voluntary – they often experience a stronger sense of belonging, reduced emotional exhaustion, and improved perceptions of organisational support (Tims et al., 2022). Social events and recreational programmes help employees develop informal networks and decompress, both of which enhance resilience and mitigate the effects of role conflict and overload (Van Steenbergen and Ellemers, 2009).

This supports **Hypothesis 8**, which posits that participation in stress-relieving activities improves WLB. These interventions complement formal structures by creating a culture that prioritises wellbeing, recognises diverse employee needs, and fosters engagement through a more human-centred approach to work.

2.8. Work-life balance and employee outcomes

Work-life balance (WLB) is widely acknowledged as a significant predictor of various employee outcomes, including job performance, attitudes, satisfaction, mental health, and overall wellbeing. The relationship between WLB and these outcomes is complex and shaped by both organisational factors (e.g., support, flexibility) and individual differences (e.g., life stage, role expectations). This section critically reviews literature examining the impact of WLB on key employee outcomes, aligned with several of the study's hypotheses (notably **H3-H8**), and highlights the mechanisms through which WLB influences organisational effectiveness.

2.8.1. Employment performance

The connection between WLB and employee performance has been widely explored, with many studies reporting a positive association. Employees who perceive a healthy balance between their work and personal lives are generally more engaged, productive, and motivated at work (Beauregard and Henry, 2009). Conversely, poor balance can lead to burnout, absenteeism, and presenteeism, which negatively affect both task performance and discretionary effort (Allen et al., 2018). Job performance is not only influenced by time availability but also by energy and psychological engagement, both of which are replenished when individuals can adequately detach from work during non-working hours (Sonnentag and Fritz, 2007).

Theoretical frameworks such as the Job Demand–Resource (JD-R) model suggest that organisational support for WLB reduces job strain and improves performance outcomes by enhancing employee resilience and resourcefulness (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). Therefore, integrating WLB into performance management systems can lead to more sustainable productivity gains.

2.8.2. Job attitudes and satisfaction

WLB plays a central role in shaping job attitudes, including commitment, motivation, and satisfaction. Employees who feel supported in achieving balance tend to express greater organisational loyalty, job enthusiasm, and lower turnover intentions (Greenhaus and Allen, 2011). Satisfaction is particularly enhanced when there is perceived alignment between employees' professional goals and their personal values and commitments (Clark, 2000).

Discrepancy theory, which underpins part of this research, suggests that when the gap between an employee's expectations and their actual work-life experiences is small, job satisfaction is more likely to be high (Lawler, 1971; Talukder, 2019). This supports **Hypotheses 5 and 6**, which focus on the impact of role conflict and boundary-setting ability on job attitudes.

2.8.3. Wellbeing and mental health

Employee wellbeing, encompassing both physical and psychological health, is significantly influenced by the level of work-life balance achieved. When balance is compromised, employees are more prone to stress, anxiety, depression, and emotional exhaustion (Kreiner et al., 2009). Chronic imbalance can also increase vulnerability to health issues such as cardiovascular problems and sleep disturbances (Grzywacz and Carlson, 2007).

Conversely, when organisations support employee wellbeing through WLB initiatives – for example, time off, stress-relief programmes, and flexible scheduling – employees report

higher life satisfaction, lower stress levels, and improved cognitive functioning (De Menezes and Kelliher, 2011). This aligns with **Hypothesis 8**, suggesting that interventions like holidays and social support activities improve WLB and mental health outcomes.

2.8.4. Key indicators of WLB

Understanding and measuring work-life balance (WLB) requires the identification of reliable indicators that reflect the extent to which individuals can effectively manage their professional and personal responsibilities. These indicators not only serve as tools for academic research but are also crucial for organisations aiming to assess and improve employee wellbeing. Scholars have proposed a range of psychological, behavioural, and attitudinal measures that collectively provide insight into how WLB is experienced (Brady and Hammer, 2022). The following discussion explores the most widely cited indicators in the literature: job stress, role conflict, role ambiguity, job involvement, and satisfaction.

Job stress is a critical indicator of WLB, arising when employees perceive an imbalance between work demands and their capacity to meet them. (Sonnentag and Fritz, 2007). High levels of job stress have been linked to burnout, reduced job performance, absenteeism, and poor mental health outcomes (Kalliath and Brough, 2008). The presence of stress can serve as a strong signal that employees are struggling to maintain equilibrium between work and life domains. This is particularly relevant in high-demand professions, such as healthcare and education, where time pressure and emotional labour are pronounced (Brough et al., 2020). For instance, a study focusing on frontline health workers during the COVID-19 pandemic found that job stress significantly contributed to turnover intentions, underscoring its impact on WLB (Nayak and Narayan, 2019).

Role conflict is a significant indicator of work-life balance (WLB) imbalance and arises when the demands of one life domain interfere with another. For instance, an employee required to work overtime may struggle to meet family obligations, leading to emotional strain and diminished satisfaction in both areas (Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985). Closely related, role ambiguity refers to the absence of clear job expectations or performance standards, which can lead to confusion and overcompensation as employees attempt to meet undefined or shifting goals (Netemeyer, Boles and McMurrian, 1996). Both constructs are forms of role stress that disrupt WLB by heightening psychological tension and uncertainty. Recent studies have reinforced these findings, highlighting that role conflict and ambiguity are significant predictors of reduced job satisfaction and organisational commitment (Khan et al., 2023; Al-Hanawi et al., 2023).

Job involvement is a more nuanced indicator of work-life balance (WLB). While a moderate level of involvement often suggests engagement and commitment, excessive involvement can lead to workaholism or an over-identification with the professional role, often at the expense of family and personal life (Kanungo, 1982; Shimazu and Schaufeli, 2009). Highly involved employees may find it difficult to disengage from work, leading to spillover effects such as poor sleep, strained relationships, and reduced leisure time (Molino et al., 2020). On the other hand, low job involvement may signal disengagement or dissatisfaction, which can also undermine wellbeing and productivity (Mayerl and Urban, 2021). Maintaining a balanced level of involvement is therefore essential to promote sustainable performance and psychological health.

Satisfaction, both with one's job and life outside of work, is a key subjective indicator of WLB. Job satisfaction reflects how content individuals are with their current work situation, including workload, flexibility, and organisational support (Ruggeri et al., 2020). Life satisfaction captures how individuals perceive their overall quality of life, including health, family relationships, and leisure. A harmonious work-life interface is generally associated with higher satisfaction in both domains. Importantly, researchers argue that WLB should not be measured solely by time allocation but by the degree of fulfilment and psychological wellbeing experienced across life roles (Guest, 2017).

In addition to these core indicators, recent research has identified work-family enrichment and boundary management ability as emerging and increasingly relevant metrics. Work-family enrichment reflects the capacity of individuals to derive positive benefits – such as energy, skills, or psychological resources – from one domain (e.g. work) that enhance performance and wellbeing in another (e.g. family) (Greenhaus and Powell, 2006; Zhang, Chen and Fan, 2023). Boundary management, on the other hand, refers to how individuals segment or integrate their work and non-work roles according to personal preferences and situational demands (Clark, 2000; Kreiner, 2006). These newer indicators are especially pertinent in the current era of hybrid and remote work, where the blurring of professional and personal spaces has challenged conventional notions of role separation (Allen, Cho and Meier, 2021).

In the context of the present study, such indicators are instrumental in evaluating how work-life balance interventions contribute to employee wellbeing, job attitudes, and performance (**Hypotheses H7 and H8**) such as extended holidays and stress-relief activities. They also provide a multidimensional basis for analysing the influence of demographic factors such as age and parental status (**H3, H4**), as well as employment context (**H1, H2**). Adopting this comprehensive framework allows for a more accurate and nuanced understanding of WLB

as a dynamic construct shaped by the interplay of multiple, interrelated domains (Kossek, Ruderman and Braddy, 2022).

2.9. Conceptual framework

Figure 2. 3. Conceptual framework (Source: Generated by the researcher)

As shown in Figure 2.3, the conceptual framework integrates eight hypotheses, each representing a different related factor that potentially influences work-life balance (WLB) and, subsequently, employee performance and wellbeing. This framework aims to provide a general view with a focus on the roles of demographic, occupational, psychological, and organisational factors. At the centre of this framework lies WLB, conceptualised as both an outcome of contextual influences and a mediating factor that affects employee performance.

Firstly, employment context, captured through working sector and employment status (**H1 and H2**), is positioned as a structural determinant of WLB. Different sectors (e.g., public vs private) and contract types (e.g., part-time vs full-time) offer varying levels of flexibility and support, which can shape employees' perceived ability to balance professional and personal responsibilities. Secondly, demographic factors – specifically age group (**H3**) and parental status (**H4**) – are proposed to influence WLB by reflecting differing life demands and caregiving responsibilities. These variables also provide a comparative lens to examine how experiences of balance vary across life stages and family structures.

The framework further incorporates psychological variables such as work-life conflict and the ability to manage work-life boundaries (**H5 and H6**). These elements reflect the internal negotiation employees undertake to meet competing role demands. Work-life conflict refers to the degree of interference between domains, while boundary management denotes individuals' ability to maintain separation or integration according to their preferences. Both are hypothesised to impact job attitudes and, by extension, performance.

Organisational support mechanisms are framed as interventions aimed at enhancing WLB, for example, access to extended holidays and participation in social events. These supports are represented in the model as “social support” (**H7 and H8**), and are hypothesised to exert direct effects on both WLB and employee performance. Importantly, **H7** and **H8** propose that targeted interventions can serve as proactive resources that foster emotional wellbeing and reduce role strain.

“Wellbeing through the life stage” serves as a unifying concept that acknowledges the temporal and evolving nature of WLB. It emphasises that employees' needs and perceptions of balance are not static but shift according to their age, life phase, and family circumstances. The arrows linking each variable indicate both direct and mediating relationships, allowing for an exploration of how specific factors interact with WLB to ultimately influence performance outcomes.

In sum, this framework supports a comprehensive, hypothesis-driven analysis that integrates demographic diversity, job context, internal coping strategies, and organisational initiatives to explain variations in WLB and their consequences on employee performance. It provides a robust foundation for empirical testing and enables practical recommendations for policy and practice in diverse organisational settings.

Figure 2. 4. Overall review of this research

Figure 2.4 presents an overview of the study, including the general area of interest, the research problem, research statement, research objectives, research questions, and research hypotheses.

2.10. Literature gap

Despite the growing body of research on work-life balance (WLB), several critical gaps remain in the existing literature, revealing opportunities for further empirical investigation. Firstly, although WLB has been widely studied, much of the existing scholarship has approached it in generalised or one-dimensional terms, often overlooking how experiences of balance may differ across diverse demographic groups. In particular, limited attention has been paid to how WLB varies across life stages, such as between younger and older employees, or those with and without caregiving responsibilities. While several studies acknowledge that factors like age and parental status influence WLB outcomes, there remains a lack of comparative, hypothesis-driven research that systematically examines these demographic differences within a single conceptual framework. This gap is especially important given the increasingly diverse workforce and the evolving nature of work arrangements across generations.

Secondly, although WLB is often associated with positive organisational and psychological outcomes, much of the literature treats performance, wellbeing, and job attitudes as isolated constructs. Numerous studies focus solely on job satisfaction or mental health, without addressing the complex, interrelated effects of WLB on multiple aspects of employee experience. This fragmented approach limits our understanding of the holistic impact of WLB, particularly in relation to how it affects not only an employee's productivity and engagement, but also their emotional resilience, job involvement, and overall psychological wellbeing. A more integrative perspective is needed to understand how WLB functions as a mediating or moderating factor that bridges work-related demands and personal fulfilment.

Thirdly, although the organisational context is increasingly recognised as a critical determinant of WLB, there remains a paucity of research comparing how different sectors (e.g., public vs private), industries, or employment types (e.g., full-time vs part-time, permanent vs temporary) influence perceptions and experiences of balance. Existing studies tend to focus on specific occupational groups or industries, which limits the generalisability of findings. Moreover, there is little consensus on whether sectoral differences amplify or reduce WLB challenges, particularly in relation to the availability and accessibility of supportive workplace practices. This lack of cross-contextual comparison hinders the ability of organisations to tailor interventions effectively and implement inclusive policies that accommodate diverse work environments.

Lastly, although a number of organisations have introduced interventions such as flexible working arrangements, extended holidays, mental health resources, and social

wellbeing programmes to enhance WLB, there is limited empirical evidence on their differential effectiveness across various employee profiles. Few studies have rigorously examined whether such interventions produce equitable outcomes for employees of different ages, life stages, or family responsibilities. In particular, there is a lack of longitudinal or comparative research that evaluates how interventions interact with individual needs or values, and whether they are equally beneficial to parents and non-parents, younger versus older workers, or those in varying employment conditions. This gap is crucial, as a one-size-fits-all approach to workplace interventions may inadvertently reinforce inequalities or lead to inefficient resource allocation.

Taken together, these gaps highlight a need for a more nuanced and inclusive research agenda. The current study responds to this need by offering a comparative, hypothesis-driven analysis that investigates how demographic factors (age and parental status), employment context (sector and type), and organisational supports (e.g., holidays, stress-relieving activities) influence perceptions of work-life balance. It also explores how WLB subsequently affects employee outcomes such as performance and wellbeing. By integrating multiple theoretical perspectives and examining the interplay between demographic, organisational, and psychological variables, this study aims to contribute to a more comprehensive and practical understanding of WLB in contemporary work environments.

2.11. Conclusion

In conclusion, the literature reviewed provides a comprehensive foundation for understanding the complex and evolving nature of work-life balance (WLB) and its influence on employee performance and wellbeing. WLB is no longer perceived merely as an individual challenge but as a multidimensional construct shaped by personal characteristics, employment contexts, organisational supports, and broader socio-cultural changes. Drawing from a range of theoretical perspectives – namely Discrepancy Theory, Compensation Theory, Work-Family Enrichment Theory, Boundary Theory, and the Job Demand–Resource (JD-R) Model – this chapter has demonstrated how WLB outcomes are influenced by the alignment (or misalignment) between employee needs, values, and resources across life and work domains.

The literature highlights that demographic variables such as age and parental status play a crucial role in shaping WLB experiences. These factors influence both the expectations individuals have of their roles and the capacity to manage overlapping responsibilities. However, research remains limited in offering comparative insights across these demographic groups within a single integrated framework, a gap that the current study intends to address through **Hypotheses H3 and H4**. Similarly, while the significance of employment contexts –

such as sector and contractual status – has been acknowledged, there is insufficient evidence on how these variables influence WLB perceptions across different occupational settings (as reflected in **Hypotheses H1 and H2**). The lack of cross-contextual research limits our understanding of how flexible policies or sector-specific demands might moderate WLB outcomes.

Furthermore, this review underlines that while many studies have examined the direct relationship between WLB and job satisfaction, there is a growing need to assess WLB in relation to a broader range of outcomes, such as job attitudes, performance, and wellbeing (linked to **H5, H6, and H7**). The inclusion of work-role conflict, work-life enrichment, and boundary management as conceptual dimensions also highlights the increasing complexity of how balance is perceived and managed in modern working environments. These factors do not operate in isolation but interact with individual agency, organisational culture, and external life demands – shaping the degree to which employees feel empowered or strained in managing multiple roles.

Especially, the review draws attention to the limited exploration of organisational interventions (e.g., holidays, social events, flexible scheduling) and their differential impact across employee profiles. Though such supports are frequently promoted in practice, empirical evidence on their effectiveness, particularly in relation to life stage or family responsibilities, remains sparse. **Hypotheses H7 and H8** in this study directly address this by evaluating how specific interventions influence WLB and related outcomes.

Overall, the literature indicates that while the concept of work-life balance is well-theorised, empirical studies remain fragmented – either focusing on single demographic variables, limited outcomes, or narrow organisational contexts. The present research aims to bridge these gaps by offering a more holistic, comparative, and hypothesis-driven investigation into how WLB interacts with key demographic, professional, and psychological variables. By doing so, it will contribute to a deeper understanding of how tailored, inclusive strategies can be designed to enhance employee wellbeing and performance in increasingly diverse and demanding work environments.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This research aims to analyse the impact of work-life balance on employee performance and well-being across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments. However, the analysis in the literature review can exclusively be limited to the scope of the employee performance in the organisation and hard to find out what is the most challenging cause of work-life balance that the employees are facing within the current time. In order to determine the research methodology, the researcher relied on research aims, objectives, and questions. This chapter explains the choice of research methodology with adequate justification considering different available research methods and in-depth research options.

This research aims to analyse the impact of work-life balance on employee performance and well-being across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments. However, the analysis in the literature review is primarily limited to the scope of employee performance within the organisation and does not fully identify the most pressing causes of work-life balance challenges currently faced by employees. To determine the appropriate research methodology, the researcher relied on the research aims, objectives, and questions. This chapter explains the chosen research methodology with adequate justification, considering different available research methods and in-depth research options.

Research philosophy is an essential basis for research which determines; therefore, this chapter initially deals with the explanations of research philosophies. Within the efforts to achieve the research objectives and requirements, this study will use positivism with good discussions of the positivist perspective in the current study. The reasons for choosing a close-ended questionnaire will be explained among a number of options for quantitative data collection methods. A section on questionnaire design, pilot study, and operationalisation of construct, reliability test, as well as the sampling method will also be presented. Furthermore, the process of how questionnaires were delivered and collected from the participants is provided. The analysis of questionnaire data is described in-depth, along with the detailed process employed. This chapter concludes with a discussion of issues in relation to the generalisability and transferability of findings, as well as with a discussion of the methodological limitations of this study.

Research philosophy serves as a foundational element of any study, guiding the approach to knowledge generation. Accordingly, this chapter begins with an explanation of

relevant research philosophies. To achieve the research objectives, this study adopts a positivist paradigm, with a detailed discussion of the positivist perspective and its relevance to the current research. The rationale for selecting a close-ended questionnaire – among various quantitative data collection methods – is thoroughly explained. This chapter also includes sections on questionnaire design, pilot study, operationalisation of constructs, and reliability testing, as well as a description of the sampling method. Additionally, the procedures for **distributing** and collecting questionnaires from participants are outlined. The chapter concludes with an in-depth explanation of how the questionnaire data were analysed, followed by discussions on the generalisability and transferability of the findings and an examination of the methodological limitations.

In sum, this chapter aims at the following objectives:

- 1) Discuss the research philosophy, research strategy, and research approach
- 2) Explain sampling design and procedures
- 3) Outline the development of research instruments used for data collection
- 4) Describe the techniques and procedures used for data analysis

Figure 3. 1. Research “onion” (Saunders et al. 2009, p.138)

According to Figure 3, the research methodology for this study will follow the structure of the "research onion," progressing from the outer layers (research philosophy) to the inner layers (techniques and procedures). To enhance the validity and reliability of this research, careful consideration has been given to the selection of data collection and analysis techniques to ensure that critical information is accurately captured and interpreted. Additionally, the methodology section will outline ethical considerations, the scope of the research, and its limitations. These elements are included to ensure trustworthiness with participants and to provide meaningful recommendations for promoting and maintaining a healthy work-life balance.

Table 3. 1. Research method for this study

Philosophies	Approaches	Strategies	Choices	Time horizons	Techniques and procedures
Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Mono method	Cross-sectional	SPSS

(Source adapted with changes from Saunders et al., 2009)

Table 3.1 outlines the research methods selected to address the research questions of this study. Positivism is adopted as the primary research philosophy, complemented by a deductive approach. Since the study aims to collect quantitative data through an online survey, a mono-method strategy is employed to align with the study's objectives. The online questionnaire is designed to explore the relationship between work and family life. A cross-sectional time horizon is adopted, as data will be collected at a single point in time (Camic, 2021). This contrasts with longitudinal studies, which gather data from the same sample (a "panel") over multiple time periods using consistent procedures (Spector, 2019). For data analysis, SPSS software is chosen as the most suitable tool for performing statistical tests and interpreting the results effectively.

3.2. Research philosophy

Research philosophy is a notion of how information or data regarding a phenomenon would be gathered, examined and applied. When discussing the research philosophy, two terms, which are encompassed, are epistemology and doxology. In contrast to doxology, which refers to what is thought to be accurate, the term “epistemology” refers to what is recognised to be true. The major objective of scientific studies is to use collected data to transform believed things into known things; in other words, doxology is transformed into epistemology (Saunders et al., 2009). According to Gray (2021), there are two major research philosophies, including positivist (sometimes called scientific) and interpretivist (also known as antipositivist), which are discussed in the current study.

3.2.1. Positivism

Regarding research philosophy, positivism is referred to as non-humanistic when there are no requirements for human interests in the study that depends on empirical data and knowledge gathered by observational (the senses), measurable, and scientific evidence (Ryan, 2018). Moreover, Alharahsheh & Pius (2020) adhered to the view that positivism is based on quantifiable observations that lead to statistical or experimental analyses to explain the precise nature of how individuals perform. According to Zyphur & Pierides (2020), it was believed by the positivists that there is no need to interfere with the studied phenomena to explain reality because it is stable and can be observed and described from an objective viewpoint (Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020). Ryan (2018) continued to state that positivists hold the position stating phenomena should be separately studied while observations may be repeated. In other words, the implementation of positivism allows the researcher to manipulate reality with variations in only a single independent variable so as to identify regularities in and form relationships between some of the constituent elements of the social world.

Predictions can be built on the foundation of the realities and inter-relationships that are previously observed, examined, and discussed (Ryan, 2018). Tuboly (2022) also

emphasises the significance of positivism, which is that knowledge not grounded in positivism is considered invalid and not scientific. This view is also in alignment with the view by Alavi and Carlson (1992), who conducted a systematic literature review of 902 business studies. The authors revealed that the majority of empirical studies are based on the positivist approach because the positivist approach provides a close connection between social realities and natural sciences (Alavi and Carlson, 1992). However, Ormston et al. (2014) claimed that the question of whether or not this positivist paradigm is entirely appropriate for the social sciences had generated significant discussion. Although the researcher will not go into deeper detail on this debate further, it is relevant to the current study since it is also the case that work-life balance, which deals with how individuals interact with their working environments, is considered to be of the social sciences (Porra, Hirschheim, & Parks, 2014). Indeed, some of the difficulties experienced in business research, for example, a significant problem in business studies is the inconsistency in research findings, which is explained by the inappropriate selection of positivism as a research paradigm. Likewise, under the positivist paradigm, some variables or components of reality may have previously been deemed to be immeasurable and, as a result, went unstudied (Ormston et al., 2014).

3.2.2. Interpretivism

In comparison with positivism, Ryan (2018) identified interpretivism as humanistic when human interests are involved in the study. Interpretivism describes theories or epistemologies that depend on how people learn about the world and how they perceive that the world may be viewed in many different ways, with different perspectives and reflections (Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020). According to interpretivism, reality can only be fully grasped by subjective interpretation and intervention. The interpretive research philosophy emphasises the importance of studying phenomena in their natural settings and the fact that scientists cannot avoid having an impact on the phenomena they research. They acknowledge that there could be numerous ways to interpret reality, but they insist that each of these ways is a component of the scientific understanding they are pursuing. The history of interpretivism is just as rich and lengthy as that of positivism (Pulla & Carter, 2018).

3.2.3. Discussions

Diesing (1966) pointed out that most objectivism-subjectivism debates in the philosophy of social science are no longer relevant due to recent growths in social science methodology. On the other side, Penalver (2018) argued that objectivism and subjectivism have long been a concern discussed among philosophers and social scientists. Objectivists require science to be grounded on approaches that are based on publicly observable and replicable facts, and these are available only in the area of overt behaviour (Kindsiko, 2018). However, the subjectivists have debated that human behaviour's critical and unique characteristics are its subjective meaningfulness, and any science that overlooks meaning and purpose is not social science. Human action is governed by subjective factors, images rather than stimuli, and reason rather than causes (Penalver, 2018). Objectivism is built on the essential and universal characteristics of the scientific approach (Diesing, 1966), while subjectivism is built on the essential and universal characteristics of human subject matter (Kindsiko, 2018).

It was argued that the main advantage of adopting the positivist research approach is its well-defined structure, which includes a robust process of creating hypotheses, factual experimentation to test hypotheses, in-depth analysis to measure the results, and ultimately the possibility of codifying the results in a set of predictions, and laws that are needed by the natural sciences (Ryan, 2018). However, a contrasting viewpoint mentioned by Alharahsheh & Pius (2020) is that due to the subjective nature of the interpretive research approach, primary data gathered in this research approach cannot be simplified easily as the data heavily relies on the individual's views and values. As a result, the reliability and representativeness of data are weakened to a certain extent (Pulla & Carter, 2018). Therefore, positivism is chosen as the most appropriate epistemology because the quantitative online survey has been applied in this study.

This research aims to analyse the impact of work-life balance on employee performance and well-being across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments. Therefore, this quantitative research study explored the relationship between work life and employee performance and their wellbeing across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments.

3.3. Research design and research approach

When conducting research, it is essential to determine the research design because it reflects the study's characteristics and data presented in the study. These characteristics are used to differentiate types of research design, including quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods. Despite the differences between different research designs, all these designs share a common feature during the research process; at one or more points, the researchers can use different ways to collect data for different purposes (Blackstone, 2018). Gaber (2020) revealed that quantitative studies involve collecting and analysing numerical data, while qualitative studies collect and analyse qualitative data (Rahman, 2020).

According to Leedy and Ormrod (2014), there are four key factors influencing the decision of research design, including the epistemology, research philosophy, the methodology, and research techniques and procedures for data collection analysis. These features will lead to the use of quantitative or qualitative method research. There have been several debates over the past few decades over whether qualitative or quantitative research should be used in social studies. Allan (2020) revealed that the fundamental differences between quantitative and qualitative research rely on unique data collection and analysis methods. Leedy and Ormrod (2014) highlighted that the two research designs, quantitative and qualitative, are employed by the researchers as tools to obtain the same goals with different research procedures and techniques; each research design has its own logic, strengths and weaknesses. Blackstone (2018) also stated that despite the differences, both quantitative and qualitative research designs fall on a research continuum.

Camic (2021) indicated that whether the researcher employs a quantitative or qualitative research design, the major purpose of both approaches refers to explaining phenomena. Therefore, the controversies and criticism concerning the definitions and the appropriateness of research design only concern the tools and techniques for collecting, analysing and interpreting data (Maxwell, 2013). Furthermore, although there are arguments between positivists and constructivists about their research instruments, no one can affirm that their instruments are more effective than others; this implies that they are meant to obtain the same purpose (Camic, 2021). Leedy and Ormrod (2014) also indicated that the research designs, whether quantitative or qualitative, are based on divergent theories and assumptions. In alignment with the research nature and methods of data collection and analysis, one design may have advantages over the other and vice versa. When the researcher makes a decision on research design, the researcher considers the advantages and disadvantages of each design

and their alignment with research objectives. In the current study, the quantitative research design was selected; this method's advantages, disadvantages and types are discussed in the following sections.

3.3.1. Quantitative research design

The methodological foundation of this study is grounded in a quantitative research design, which aligns with the study's objective to test predefined hypotheses and examine statistically significant relationships between work-life balance, employee performance, and wellbeing across demographic and organisational variables. A quantitative approach was selected due to its structured and objective nature, allowing for systematic data collection and numerical analysis (Bryman, 2016). This design facilitates the generalisability of findings and supports the use of inferential statistical tools such as ANOVA and Pearson's correlation to test hypotheses (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Moreover, it enables efficient handling of large sample sizes using analysis software like SPSS, enhancing both the reliability and replicability of the results (Alili & Krstev, 2019). Unlike qualitative approaches, which offer in-depth insights into individual experiences, the quantitative method allows for the identification of broader trends and patterns across larger populations (Allan, 2020). As such, this design was deemed most appropriate for the objectives of the current research. The following section outlines the strengths and limitations of quantitative research in comparison to qualitative methods, offering a critical justification for its adoption in the current study.

There is no doubt that the nature of quantitative research design, involving the use of numerical data, offers fundamental advantages in terms of time and resource efficiency. Maxwell (2013) stated that research employing a quantitative design centres on tools for collecting and analysing statistical data. In other words, compared to qualitative research, quantitative design tends to be more scientific in nature. Waugh (2022) emphasised that the use of numbers and figures in data analysis and description within quantitative research reduces the researcher's time, effort, and resource consumption in conducting the study. While data formats in qualitative research design are more varied – such as texts or images (Gaber, 2020) – quantitative research relies strictly on numerical and statistical data (Blackstone, 2018).

Another major advantage of the quantitative design is the ability to generalise research findings due to the use of scientific tools and techniques for data collection and analysis (Blackstone, 2018). Cohen and Morrison (2011) pointed out that interpreting phenomena through the lens of quantitative findings is not perceived as mere coincidence but can be generalised. For example, when examining work-life balance among UK employees, the results

may reflect patterns and characteristics applicable to the wider population. In essence, quantitative findings can be extended to represent broader sample groups (Waugh, 2022).

In connection with generalisability, Waugh (2022) also noted that data reliability is another key advantage of quantitative research. Researchers depend on hypothesis testing and follow structured, objective research procedures rather than guessing what to do next (Cohen & Morrison, 2011). The quantitative framework provides clear guidelines and objectives, enabling replication in different research settings (Maxwell, 2013). According to Leedy and Ormrod (2014), studies conducted using this methodology can be repeated in different contexts and still yield similar results due to their systematic design.

Perhaps one of the most significant strengths of quantitative research is its objectivity. Maxwell (2013) highlighted that this design is perceived as a researcher-detachment model. Waugh (2022) explained that bias can be minimised through the use of structured data collection and analysis tools. Vu (2021) further argued that using self-administered questionnaires – either online, paper-based, or via telephone – reduces direct contact with respondents and thus minimises researcher bias. Camic (2021) noted that, compared to qualitative research, quantitative methods afford a higher level of researcher objectivity. Furthermore, respondent anonymity is often preserved through indirect communication, contributing to more honest responses (Vu, 2021).

Despite these benefits, quantitative research design is not without its disadvantages. Savela (2018) identified that researcher detachment – which is an advantage in terms of objectivity – can also be a weakness. When researchers act solely as observers, it limits their ability to form close connections with participants and makes it difficult to capture in-depth information from natural settings (Rahman, 2020). The absence of interpersonal engagement means researchers may not fully understand participants' experiences, perceptions, and opinions (Kracauer, 2022).

Another limitation relates to the lack of participant involvement. Waugh (2022) observed that researchers using quantitative design maintain control over the research process, which limits opportunities for participant-driven insights. Due to the linear and rigid nature of this design, as described by Savela (2018), researchers must follow a set order: define research questions, formulate hypotheses, review the literature, collect and analyse data, interpret findings, and generate implications. Kracauer (2022) suggested that when participants are more actively involved in shaping the study like in qualitative research, researchers can benefit from a more grounded understanding of the phenomena. Waugh (2022) noted that limited participant engagement stems from the liturgical structure of quantitative studies.

Although qualitative research has its own advantages, including the ability to obtain rich descriptions and participant narratives, it also faces criticism. Maxwell (2013) characterised qualitative methods as those focused on concepts, definitions, and the interpretation of meaning. Gaber (2020) explained that qualitative research allows the use of diverse tools such as expert interviews, focus groups, field observations, and notes to collect data in natural settings. This direct interaction enables researchers to gain a deeper understanding of participants' behaviours. Leedy and Ormrod (2014) affirmed that qualitative approaches are ideal for obtaining rich and detailed information about the studied phenomena.

However, qualitative methods are also associated with several limitations. Gaber (2020) argued that qualitative researchers often view social reality as dynamic and context-dependent, which reduces the generalisability of findings. Maxwell (2013) noted that if the present study on work-life balance and employee outcomes were conducted using qualitative methods, it would not have been feasible to cover a large, diverse sample. Consequently, the findings would not be generalisable to the broader population. Blackstone (2018) reinforced this by asserting that qualitative design is inappropriate when the goal is to generalise findings to a larger audience.

Additionally, qualitative data is often criticised for being based on subjective interpretation without external verification (Gaber, 2020). Rahman (2020) pointed out that while numerical data in quantitative research can be verified and statistically tested, qualitative data lacks consistency and reproducibility. This challenge affects the reliability and repeatability of qualitative research. Maxwell (2013) argued that the subjectivity inherent in qualitative research can lead to biased or misleading results.

Rahman (2020) linked this subjectivity to broader philosophical debates on ontology and epistemology. He noted that qualitative researchers often impose their own interpretations of phenomena on participants' experiences, limiting the universality of findings. Finally, Leedy and Ormrod (2014) observed that qualitative research often uses text and image-based data, making it difficult to summarise findings systematically. As qualitative researchers interpret events through their own perspectives, different researchers may arrive at different conclusions under similar conditions. Therefore, replication is challenging, and the consistency of findings may be compromised (Rahman, 2020).

3.3.2. Types of quantitative research design

According to Bloomfield and Fisher (2019), quantitative research design involves four main types: descriptive, correlation, causal-comparative/Quasi-Experimental, and Experimental Research.

1) Descriptive Research

Hodge (2020) explains that descriptive research aims to characterise the current state of a particular variable. These studies are designed to provide systematic insights into a phenomenon. Typically, the researcher does not begin with a hypothesis; however, one may develop following the data collection phase. The hypothesis is subsequently tested through data analysis and synthesis (Patten & Newhart, 2017). Effective descriptive research requires the careful selection of study units and the accurate measurement of each variable.

2) Correlational Research

The goal of correlational research is to use statistical data to assess the strength of a link between two or more variables (Plonsky, 2017). In this kind of design, connections between and among various data are looked for and understood. The data will show trends and patterns in this study, but it does not go as far as to verify the reasons behind the observed patterns. This kind of observational study is not based on cause and effect. Only the data, relationships, and variable distributions are analysed. No variables are altered; they are merely recognised and examined as they emerge in a natural environment (Goertzen, 2017). Correlational research is sometimes seen as a sort of descriptive research rather than as a distinct category of research since no variables are altered throughout the investigation

3) Causal-Comparative/Quasi-Experimental Research

According to Walker (2017), causal-comparative/quasi-experimental research aims to demonstrate cause-effect correlations among variables. These designs are similar to genuine experiments, but there are a few major distinctions. The investigator identifies an independent variable but does not alter it, and the effects of the independent variable on the dependent variable are measured. The researcher must employ spontaneously generated or pre-existing groups rather than assigning groups at random. Identified control groups exposed to the treatment variable are researched and compared to those that are not (Park & Park, 2016). When doing studies and drawing conclusions, finding causes must be done with caution since other factors, both known and unknown, may still influence the result.

4) Experimental Research

Experimental research, also known as true experimentation, employs the scientific method to determine the cause-effect connection among a set of variables in a study (Plonsky, 2017). True experiments are sometimes assumed to be laboratory studies, but this is not necessarily the case; a laboratory environment has nothing to do with them. A real experiment is any research in which every other variable except one is identified and controlled. According to Hodge (2020), an independent variable is changed to determine the impacts on the dependent

variables. Subjects are randomised to experimental treatments at random rather than being identified in naturally existing groups.

This study adopts a correlational quantitative research design, which is considered the most appropriate approach for examining the relationships between work-life balance (WLB) and employee outcomes such as performance and wellbeing, across various demographic and employment contexts. The primary objective of this research is not to manipulate variables or establish causality, but rather to measure the strength and direction of associations between naturally occurring variables through statistical analysis.

Correlational research is particularly well-suited to this study, as it facilitates the testing of eight hypotheses that explore how employment context (**H1, H2**), demographic factors (**H3, H4**), job attitudes (**H5, H6**), and organisational interventions (**H7, H8**) relate to employees' perceptions of WLB and its subsequent influence on employee performance and wellbeing. As noted by Plonsky (2017), correlational studies are effective for identifying and quantifying relationships among variables without requiring direct manipulation, making them ideal for real-world workplace investigations.

Additionally, this study utilises a cross-sectional time horizon, which involves collecting data at a single point in time. This approach is both practical and efficient for capturing insights from a broad and diverse sample via an online survey. It enables meaningful comparisons across subgroups based on age, parental status, work sector, and employment type. According to Goertzen (2017), cross-sectional designs are advantageous when the goal is to understand patterns of behaviour across populations without the need for longitudinal tracking.

In summary, the correlational quantitative design was chosen because it:

- Enables statistical assessment of relationships between multiple independent and dependent variables;
- Supports the testing of hypotheses across demographic and organisational categories;
- Allows for generalisability and external validity through structured, large-scale data collection;
- Aligns with the research aim of understanding WLB dynamics without experimental manipulation.

This approach provides a robust foundation for analysing how WLB influences employee performance and wellbeing, offering valuable insights for organisational policy and practice.

3.3.3. Deductive approach and inductive approach

Deductive reasoning (Figure 3.3), commonly known as the deductive approach, is defined by Saunders et al. (2009) as a method for generating hypotheses from ideas that are

being proposed and are being narrowed down to become more particular. In particular, the deductive method is based on the current concepts of the research problem, which will then be developed into more specific hypotheses that will be explored. However, Rahman (2020) suggested that in comparison with the deductive approach, the inductive approach (Figure 3.2) “involves the search for pattern from observation and the development of explanations – theories – for those patterns through series of hypotheses” (Bernard, 2011, p.7).

Figure 3. 2. Inductive research (Blackstone, 2012)

Figure 3. 3. Deductive research (Blackstone, 2012)

The inductive approach is aimed to develop a theory when the literature on the topic is non-existent (Blackstone, 2012), whereas when conducting deductive research, the researcher aims to test an existing theory (Saunders et al., 2009). Therefore, this is the key distinction between inductive and deductive reasoning.

Blackstone (2018) also supported that *deductive reasoning* is frequently defined as the application of statistical analysis to generate the relationship between what is discovered and what may be reviewed throughout the investigation, which is related to quantitative research. On the other hand, inductive reasoning, which is related to qualitative research, is mainly based on learning experiences and is intended to concentrate on the specific "observations" first before going into more theoretical generalisations and notions (Saunders et al., 2009). Therefore, the deductive approach is selected for this study because it is appropriate, and data collection and analysis processes are quicker than gathering data in the inductive method (Rahman, 2020).

3.4. Research strategy

A research strategy introduces the main components of a research project, such as research topic area, research perspective, research design, and research methods. It refers to how the researchers propose to answer the research questions set and how they will implement the methodology (Sileyew, 2019).

Figure 3.4 shows the four main types of research strategy, including case studies, qualitative interviews, quantitative surveys and action-oriented research. In business studies, the researchers tend to use one of the first three; the researchers are less likely to use action-oriented research (Dillman et al., 2014).

Figure 3. 4. Main research strategies (Dillman et al., 2014)

The first research strategy refers to a case study, which focuses on an in-depth investigation of a single case (e.g. one organisation) or a specific number of cases (Dillman et al., 2014). Data can be qualitative, quantitative or a mix of both. Case study research allows a composite and multifaceted investigation of the issue or problem (Lavarda & Bellucci, 2022). However, it will be time-consuming to use this method because the information for case study research is typically required from various sources and through several forms of data, including observations, surveys, interviews, and document analysis (Ruggiano & Perry 2019).

The following research strategy refers to the qualitative interviews. There are different types of qualitative interviews, such as structured interviews, semi-structured interviews, and unstructured interviews (Dillman et al., 2014). Qualitative interviews, which allow access to rich information, are required the researcher to have extensive planning concerning the development of the structure, types of interview, and decisions about whom to interview and how, whether to conduct individual or group interviews and how to record, transcribe and analyse them (Sisk, 2018). However, Saunders et al. (2009) claimed that interviewees need a wide range of skills, including good social skills, listening skills and communication skills. Interviews are also time-consuming to conduct and are prone to problems and biases that need to be minimised during the design stage. Another prevalent research strategy in business research is a quantitative survey, a widely used method in business research that allows access to significantly high numbers of participants. The availability of online sites enables the wide and cheap distribution of surveys and the organisation of the responses (Litosseliti, 2018). Dillman et al. (2014) pointed out that although the development of questions may appear easy, it is challenging to develop a meaningful questionnaire that allows answering research questions (Coe et al., 2021). It is highlighted that questionnaires need to appeal to respondents, which cannot be overly lengthy, obtrusive, or challenging to understand. Questionnaires are required to measure the issue accurately under investigation. For these reasons, it is suggested that the researchers should critically review previous studies to adapt the framework and questionnaire, which were validated through previous studies. (Cameron & Price, 2009). Moreover, the decision to use a quantitative survey also relies on the sample size because it determines the generalisation of results to broader populations. Surveys can be administered to the whole population (census), for example, to all employees of a specific organisation (Litosseliti, 2018).

The last research strategy refers to action-oriented research, which involves practical business activities aiming at generating changes for the studied organisations. According to Cameron and Price (2009), action-oriented research refers to the process in which the researcher is directly involved in using the combination between theories, practices, actions and reflection to generate changes for improvements in the organisations. Therefore, the insiders who can participate in the basic research tend to perform action-oriented research. A distinctive feature of action-oriented research is that the participants, as research results, will implement changes by putting the findings into practice. Although action-oriented and action research are developed based on the same assumptions of change generation, action-oriented research is not exactly action research. The difference is the practicability of research results.

While action-oriented research results are achievable in practice, those of action research are not always practical.

Dufour and Richard (2019) pointed out that it is also possible for the researchers to choose a strategy that includes the use of secondary data. Secondary data is data that has been collected by other people, such as employee surveys, market research data, and censuses. Using secondary data for the research project needs to be justified in meeting the research questions' requirements. The use of secondary data has apparent benefits in terms of saving money and time. However, Sileyew (2019) claimed that it is essential to ascertain the quality of the data and how it was collected. For example, data collected by government agencies will have good quality but may not necessarily meet the needs of the research project (Ruggiano & Perry 2019).

It is important to note that there should be consistency between the perspective (subjective or objective) and the methodology applied. Therefore, this means that the type of strategy adopted needs to be coherent, and its various elements need to fit in with each other, whether the research is grounded on primary or secondary data (Dillman et al., 2014).

The current study uses a quantitative survey questionnaire as a research strategy. The study utilised qualitative findings, theory and constructs in concert with existing literature to develop a questionnaire that would determine the extent of work-life balance driving employees' attitudes and performance in many business sectors in the UK. Questionnaires have been shown to be appropriate in mixed method studies to extend and quantify the findings of an initial qualitative phase (Litosseliti, 2018). Developing constructs from survey data has been shown to reduce the risk of "researcher imposed constructs" (Coe et al., 2021) by using the valuable insights offered by participants. Furthermore, issues that are relevant to respondents potentially improve response rates and minimise nonresponse error. The literature on questionnaire design also provided valuable information about the different ways of structuring the questionnaire to best capture information that would answer the research question (Jones, Baxter, & Khanduja, 2013).

Questionnaires are relatively easy to create, code and interpret and are less time-consuming, especially as the respondent, rather than the researcher, completes the questionnaire (Dillman et al., 2014). It is pointed out that questionnaires are a reliable research method as the researcher use questions with uniform definitions, which ensure that respondents are asked the same questions in the same way (Jones, Baxter, & Khanduja, 2013). One of the main concerns while using questionnaires is that questionnaires are generally associated with lower response rates (Debois, 2022). Therefore, this can be attributed to the impersonal nature

of questionnaires, where there is no opportunity for the participants to build rapport with the researcher (Debois, 2022).

3.5. Questionnaire design

In order to develop the questionnaires, various constructs were derived from the categories identified in the quantitative findings, and the theory and critical constructs discussed previously. In this study, demographic questions will be placed at the end of the survey because it will help the researcher to engage with the respondents better (Ruthness Research, 2017). In order to have a better explanation of the reason to position demographic questions at the end of the survey, Ziegenfuss et al. (2021) explained that although demographic questions are not hard in themselves and most people consider them to be true facts, some people may feel uncomfortable answering them because people perceive them as being somewhat personal. Therefore, if a demographic section is placed later in the survey, the respondent will already feel engaged and willing to put forth the effort to answer. According to Rutlhess Research (2017), although the demographics questions are quick and easy to fill out and require little thought, it is still uncomfortable for the respondents to fill out their information before starting to know the main content of the survey (Ziegenfuss et al., 2021). Moreover, respondents may become anxious about what will come next and worry that their personal information will be connected to something they would not be happy about if personal questions were asked upfront. People might become hostile to responding and stop speaking before getting started (Toor, 2020).

The questionnaire used in this study was designed to collect quantitative data aligned with the research objectives and hypotheses concerning work-life balance (WLB), employee performance, and wellbeing across diverse demographic and organisational contexts. Grounded in the positivist paradigm, the questionnaire was structured in a way that allowed for the systematic testing of eight hypotheses. These hypotheses examined not only demographic variables such as age and parental status but also explored the influence of job-related factors such as employment sector, employment type, organisational support, stress-relieving interventions, and individual role management strategies on employees' perception of work-life balance and its associated outcomes. While this study focused solely on quantitative data to ensure statistical generalisability and hypothesis testing, it is acknowledged that the inclusion of qualitative questions could have provided deeper insights into employees' personal experiences and perceptions, potentially enriching the interpretation of the quantitative findings such as open-ended items. This presents an opportunity for future research to incorporate mixed methods to capture both the breadth and depth of the topic.

To ensure both validity and reliability, the items in the questionnaire were adapted from previously validated and widely cited scales in the academic literature. The questionnaire was divided into five primary sections: (1) demographic information; (2) work-life balance perceptions; (3) work-family conflict and boundary management; (4) employee wellbeing and performance; and (5) perceived organisational interventions and support. Each of the non-demographic sections consisted predominantly of closed-ended statements measured using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). This format is particularly suitable for quantifying subjective experiences and attitudes, and has been endorsed by Boone and Boone (2012) for its clarity and statistical applicability in behavioural research.

Despite the apparent simplicity of the survey questionnaire, it yielded a remarkably rich dataset that enabled comprehensive analysis across a wide range of constructs related to work-life balance (WLB), employee performance, and wellbeing. The use of closed-ended questions, primarily structured through a five-point Likert scale, allowed for the efficient collection of quantitative data while preserving consistency and comparability across responses. This format facilitated statistical analysis of complex relational patterns between variables, including demographic characteristics (e.g., age, parental status), employment context (e.g., sector, contract type), and employee attitudes (e.g., perceived stress, job satisfaction, boundary management). The structured design of the survey ensured that even with a limited number of items, meaningful insights could be drawn across eight hypotheses, providing evidence of correlations and group differences. As Bryman (2016) notes, well-designed questionnaires can generate a depth of analytical value when guided by clear theoretical frameworks and robust measurement constructs. Additionally, the simplicity of the questionnaire enhanced respondent engagement, contributing to a valid response rate of 67.4%, which is considered acceptable for quantitative research (Menold & Bogner, 2023). The breadth of the data collected through this questionnaire not only supported hypothesis testing but also allowed for subgroup comparisons, trend identification, and the exploration of intervention effectiveness, thus demonstrating the methodological strength of a concise yet strategically constructed survey tool.

The constructs used to measure the core variables of this study were carefully selected based on their theoretical relevance and psychometric robustness. For example, items capturing work-life balance were adapted from the framework developed by Fisher-McAuley et al. (2003), which is widely recognised for its multidimensional perspective on WLB. Measures of work-family conflict were based on the scale proposed by Netemeyer et al. (1996), which remains a standard in organisational behaviour research. Items related to boundary

management were drawn from Clark’s (2000) boundary theory, and organisational support items were sourced from the Perceived Organisational Support scale by Eisenberger et al. (1986), which evaluates the extent to which employees believe their organisation values their contributions and cares about their wellbeing. These established instruments were chosen to strengthen content validity, reduce measurement bias, and ensure the generalisability of findings.

In line with recommendations from Ziegenfuss et al. (2021), demographic questions were deliberately positioned at the end of the questionnaire. Although such questions are objectively simple, they are often perceived as personal or intrusive by respondents and may contribute to survey fatigue or early dropout if placed at the beginning (Toor, 2020). By sequencing them last, participants are more likely to feel engaged and less apprehensive, having already formed a level of trust through their interaction with the core content of the questionnaire. This approach, as supported by Ruthless Research (2017), is particularly effective in increasing response rates and data accuracy in self-administered surveys.

To provide clarity and transparency in the operationalisation of the research variables, a summary of each construct, along with the associated measurement items and their original sources, is presented in Table 3.2 below. This table serves as a blueprint for the analytical phase, linking each theoretical construct to the empirical data gathered and outlining the methodological rationale for its inclusion. Importantly, categorical variables such as gender, age, parental status, and employment sector were collected through separate demographic questions and are not included in the table, as they do not rely on psychometric scales but serve as grouping variables for comparison.

Table 3. 2. Summary of constructs, measurement items, and sources

Construct	Example measurement item	Source
Work-Life Balance	How successful can you feel you are at maintaining a healthy work/personal/family life balance?	Fisher-McAuley et al. (2003)
Work Demands	I am expected to work long hours.	Carlson et al. (2000)
Family Interference with Work	The demands of my family interfere with work-related activities.	Netemeyer et al. (1996)
Work Prioritisation	I prioritise my job over my personal life.	Greenhaus & Beutell (1985)
Family Prioritisation	I prioritise my family over my work.	Greenhaus & Beutell (1985)

Boundary Management	I am able to set boundaries between my work and personal life.	Clark (2000); Kossek et al. (2012)
Leisure and Recovery	It is easy for me to find time for hobbies and interests.	Sonnentag & Fritz (2007)
Work-to-Family Conflict	My home life interferes with your responsibilities such as getting to work on time.	Frone et al. (1992)
Perceived Organisational Support	I am satisfied with the workplace flexibility offered by my organisation.	Eisenberger et al. (1986)
Health and Stress	Do you suffer from stress-related diseases like hypertension or do you engage in stress-relieving programs?	WHO-5; Cohen et al. (1983)
Perceived Interventions	Organising more stress-relieving social events/activities would improve my work-life balance.	Kossek & Distelberg (2016); Allen et al. (2021)

As shown in Table 3.2, each construct in the questionnaire was measured using items adapted from well-established and validated scales in the existing literature. This approach enhances the content validity and reliability of the instrument, ensuring that the items accurately reflect the theoretical concepts being studied. The selected constructs are aligned with the research objectives and hypotheses of this study. For instance, the relationship between work-life balance and demographic factors such as age and parental status is addressed in **Hypotheses 3 and 4**, while **Hypotheses 5 through 8** focus on the influence of personal strategies (such as boundary setting) and organisational resources (such as holidays and social activities) on employee outcomes. The standardised use of Likert-scale items ensures comparability across constructs and facilitates the use of inferential statistical tools via SPSS. This structured and theory-driven questionnaire design contributes significantly to the study's overall methodological robustness and analytical coherence.

3.6. Sampling

Sampling is a critical component of any research methodology, as it determines how well the findings can be generalised to a broader population. Tyrer and Heyman (2016) classified sampling into two primary categories: probability sampling and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling methods, including simple random sampling, stratified random sampling, and systematic sampling, are characterised by random selection, giving each individual within the population an equal chance of being included in the sample (Turner,

2020). This enhances the statistical generalisability of the findings and reduces the risk of sampling bias. For example, stratified sampling allows for controlled representation of different subgroups within the population, while systematic sampling ensures orderly selection based on a fixed interval (Saunders et al., 2019). These methods are ideal in large-scale quantitative studies when a sampling frame is available and researchers aim to draw population-level conclusions (McEwan, 2020). However, despite their methodological robustness, probability-based techniques often require extensive resources, access to detailed population lists, and considerable time, which may not be feasible in many academic or applied research contexts (Bryman, 2016).

In contrast, non-probability sampling involves the selection of participants based on subjective judgment or accessibility rather than randomisation. Methods in this category include convenience sampling, purposive sampling, quota sampling, and snowball sampling (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016). Although this approach may limit the generalisability of results due to potential biases in participant selection, it is widely used in social science research, especially when exploring associations, patterns, and relationships in specific groups (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Convenience sampling, in particular, is one of the most accessible and time-efficient methods, involving the collection of data from individuals who are readily available and willing to participate. It is often employed in exploratory or correlational research studies where the goal is not to represent the entire population but to investigate relationships within accessible groups under real-world constraints (McCombes, 2022).

Considering the scope of this research, which seeks to investigate the impact of work-life balance on employee performance and wellbeing across various demographic and employment settings, a non-probability convenience sampling strategy was selected. According to the UK Government (2020), there are approximately 32.99 million individuals aged 16 and over who are currently employed in the UK. Accessing a complete and accurate sampling frame for this population would be impractical due to time, cost, and ethical barriers. As such, a more feasible approach was required to collect data efficiently while still ensuring adequate diversity in responses. Convenience sampling enabled the researcher to gather data from participants across multiple sectors and job types, facilitating comparative analysis across variables such as age group, employment type, and parental status. Participants were not selected based on any specific criteria, which minimised the researcher's influence over the demographic composition of the sample and helped to reduce potential selection bias, even within the non-probability framework (McCombes, 2022).

A total of 500 questionnaires were distributed to participants across various employment sectors using a non-probability convenience sampling approach. Of these, 300 were sent directly via email to professional contacts, academic networks, and workplace associations, while the remaining 200 were shared across social media platforms including LinkedIn, Facebook, and WhatsApp, targeting employment-focused groups and communities. Participants were provided with a participant information sheet and a consent form in line with ethical research practices. These documents clarified the research aims, voluntary nature of participation, and assurances of anonymity and confidentiality (Ennis & Wykes, 2016; Camic, 2021). Only individuals who read the information and gave explicit consent were permitted to complete the questionnaire.

Participants were first introduced to the research purpose and then asked for their informed consent through a participant information sheet and consent form. After a ten-week period, a follow-up message was sent as a reminder to complete the questionnaire. In total, 337 responses were received and considered valid for analysis. This represents a valid response rate of 67.4%, which exceeds the average response rates typically observed in business and management research, where response rates around 51% are common. Such a response rate is considered acceptable and supports the reliability of the study's findings (Menold and Bogner, 2023). The remaining responses were excluded due to incomplete or invalid entries, such as missing sections or contradictory responses. This distinction between the number of distributed and usable questionnaires is crucial in understanding the scope and reliability of the dataset. While convenience sampling limits the generalisability of the results (Bryman, 2016), the diverse profile of the final sample – spanning various sectors, age groups, and employment statuses – enhances the internal validity and relevance of the findings. The response rate also indicates a strong level of engagement, likely aided by the relevance of the topic and the clear structure of the survey. These factors collectively justify the sampling approach and support the reliability of the data used to test the study's hypotheses.

In conclusion, while non-probability sampling is inherently less robust in terms of external validity compared to probability-based methods (Tyrer and Heyman, 2016), it remains a practical and widely accepted strategy in social science research when investigating patterns, relationships, or trends within specific, accessible populations (Saunders et al., 2019). This study's use of convenience sampling is, therefore, justified based on the research objectives, resource limitations, and the need to examine a wide range of work-life balance factors without requiring population-wide representativeness.

3.7. Data collection

3.7.1. Data collection methods

According to Sileyew (2019), there are a number of methods that can be used for collecting data from the questionnaire. The researcher also stated that the used methods often change under technological developments. For years, the researchers used a variety of techniques, including in-person interviews, phone interviews, and online survey. Each method of collecting data from the survey has its own unique strengths and weaknesses. The response rate of each type of method is also varied (Dewaele, 2018). The researcher decides the most appropriate method for data collection based on the research nature, requirements and settings.

1) Online survey/Web-based survey

A study by Dillman et al. (2014) revealed that an online survey had become one of the most prevalent methods under the technological upgrades. The researchers prefer the online survey because this method is time and cost-effective and enables the researcher to approach a large sample pool compared to other methods (Sileyew, 2019). Ball (2019) also emphasised that online survey's performance is higher than other methods. Mainly, online surveys are significantly more effective than other methods in such studies that use a number of questions to collect data from the targeted respondents.

Dewaele (2018) noted the accuracy of data collected from the online survey as a superior characteristic in comparison to other traditional means of collecting questionnaire data. The accuracy of data from the online survey is determined by the use of computational logic and branching technologies and real-time responses (Sileyew, 2019). Furthermore, real-time responses also allow the researcher to adjust their collection means and the participants to save their time. Nayak and Narayan (2019) pointed out that another prominent advantage of online survey involves safety and security during the study process. Under the effects of the global crisis and COVID-19, the indirect communication and interaction between the researcher and participants ensure safety and security (Nayak and Narayan, 2019). In addition, the undisclosed information of participants enables the researcher to ensure the confidentiality of the research (Sileyew, 2019).

2) Face-to-face survey

Another effective approach for data collection from the participants is the face-to-face survey that is described the participant's trust in the researcher (Hurst and Bird, 2018). It was stated by Sileyew (2019) that the direct, face-to-face contact between the researcher and participants motivates the participants to provide clear, in-depth and honest responses about the studied

phenomena. Furthermore, Hurst and Bird (2018) also stated that owing to the direct contact of the face-to-face survey. The researcher can efficiently address the participants' possible problems, which can negatively influence how the participants provide the questionnaire responses. Regarding the disadvantages of the face-to-face survey, this method of gathering data requires more effort from the researcher during the data collection process (Menon & Muraleedharan, 2020). The participants are categorised into different geographic or psychographic segments, and the researchers must be trained on how to implement the steps to obtain appropriate data (Dewaele, 2018).

3) Telephone survey

According to Menon and Muraleedharan (2020), besides face-to-face and online surveys, a telephone survey is also used to gather data in the study. Data is collected rapidly through a telephone survey because the phone call can be made immediately (Menon and Muraleedharan, 2020). The authors listed less investment of time and human efforts in comparison to other methods such as face-to-face surveys as the advantage of telephone surveys. Furthermore, Marshall (2019) explained that when using the telephone as the means to conduct the questionnaire, the researchers could obtain wider geographic access to the participants.

Additionally, because most people have telephones, the researchers have a big audience for gathering a representative sample to complete the survey (Savela, 2018). Saunders et al. (2009) also listed some advantages of a telephone survey, such as participant intrusiveness and the limitation of question complexity. The majority of telephone questionnaires are conducted randomly, which may interrupt the respondents' activities (Saunders et al., 2009). Hence, they may refuse to participate in the survey, leading to a lower response rate (Savela, 2018). In addition, it is challenging for the respondents to elaborate on their answers by phone because the average length of the questionnaire is five to ten minutes. Hence, if the question is too complex, the participants may hang up their phones, leading to a partially completed questionnaire (Marshall, 2019).

4) Paper-based survey

Another commonly used method to collect data from the participants refers to the paper-based survey. This approach allows the researcher to gather data from the participants in the case the researcher is not able to use the support from the computer and telephone (Sileyew, 2019). Although this method is age-old, which has been for years (Saunders et al., 2009), the paper-based survey is still prevalent in field research (Dewaele, 2018). The significant advantages of this method are the high rate of responses and response validity (Sileyew, 2019).

However, Hurst and Bird (2018) argued that implementing a paper-based survey requires excellent efforts from the researcher and referencing time and human power.

Table 3. 3. Different types of survey

Characteristics	Types of survey			
	Web-based survey	Face-to-face survey	Telephone survey	Paper-based survey
Comparative cost	Low	High	High	High
Data collection time	Short	Long	Long	Long
Response rate	Low	High	High	High
Technology required	Yes	No	No	No
Training required	No	Yes	Yes	No

In general, there are many different types of methods for data collection from the survey. As can be seen from Table 3.3, many types of questionnaire surveys have been listed to help the researcher choose the most appropriate method. However, in the current study, an online survey or web-based survey has been selected and implemented through Google Form. The benefits of this approach have been mentioned above; it makes sure that the in-time responses from the participants, the accuracy of collected data, support for data analysis, safety and security, and confidentiality for the participants (Menon & Muraleedharan, 2020). The procedures for collecting data are presented in the next section.

3.7.2. Data collection procedures

Figure 3. 5. Data collection procedures

(Source: Generated by the researcher)

To collect primary data for this study, a structured questionnaire was developed based on existing validated measurement scales aligned with the research objectives and hypotheses. The questionnaire consisted of five sections: demographic information, work-life balance perceptions, work-family conflict and boundary management, employee wellbeing and performance, and perceived organisational support. Most items were measured using a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree), a widely accepted format for capturing attitudes and perceptions (Boone & Boone, 2012). Items were adapted from established sources such as Fisher-McAuley et al. (2003) for work-life balance, Netemeyer et al. (1996) for work-family conflict, and Eisenberger et al. (1986) for perceived organisational support.

The questionnaire used in this study was carefully developed based on validated constructs from prior literature and aligned with the research objectives and hypotheses. Once the questionnaire was finalised and formatted using Google Forms, the researcher initiated a multi-channel distribution strategy to ensure broad and diverse participation. The survey was disseminated through two primary methods: direct email and social media platforms. Specifically, a total of 250 questionnaires were emailed directly to potential participants, whose email addresses had been sourced from business networks and professional contacts across different sectors. Each email included a participant information sheet and a consent form, in line with ethical research guidelines (Ennis & Wykes, 2016). Only after receiving consent, participants would receive the link to the online questionnaire.

Additionally, the survey link was shared publicly on social media platforms, including LinkedIn, Facebook, and WhatsApp. These platforms were chosen due to their accessibility and high engagement rates, particularly among professionals from varied backgrounds (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This approach enhanced the diversity of the sample and enabled rapid distribution across a wide audience. The questionnaire was open for responses for a period of ten weeks. A reminder message was issued midway through the data collection period to encourage participation and completion. At the end of the ten-week window, a total of 337 valid and fully completed responses were received. These responses were screened for completeness and accuracy before being included in the final data analysis. The multi-channel distribution strategy, combined with ethical procedures and follow-up reminders, ensured a sufficient and diverse sample for hypothesis testing and statistical evaluation.

Altogether, this distribution method yielded a total of 337 valid responses, which were included in the final analysis. This strategy ensured efficient data collection while addressing time and resource constraints, and also supported the research aim of investigating work-life balance perceptions across a broad demographic and occupational spectrum.

3.8. Data analysis

To ensure the integrity and analytical rigour of this study, IBM SPSS Statistics was selected as the primary tool for data analysis. SPSS was chosen over alternatives such as Microsoft Excel and NVivo due to its superior capability in handling complex, large-scale datasets, its intuitive user interface, and its comprehensive suite of statistical tools, which are well-suited for the quantitative and hypothesis-driven design of this research (Alili & Krstev, 2019; Milovanović & Perišić, 2020). SPSS enables researchers to perform a wide range of analyses, including descriptive statistics, correlation, ANOVA, and regression, without requiring advanced programming skills. This makes it particularly useful in social science research, where methodological accuracy and ease of use are equally important.

While Microsoft Excel is commonly used for basic data organisation and simple statistical summaries, it is limited in its ability to manage complex variable interactions, conduct robust inferential analyses, and test statistical assumptions. Rehman (2021) noted that Excel is inefficient when processing large datasets and lacks built-in tools for more sophisticated analyses, such as reliability testing or hypothesis testing, which are essential for studies like this.

In contrast, NVivo is a powerful tool for qualitative research, particularly effective for analysing non-numeric data such as interview transcripts, open-ended survey responses, and textual documents (Dollah et al., 2017). However, NVivo's strengths in thematic coding and

content analysis do not align with the structured, numerical nature of the data collected in this study. Moreover, NVivo requires a steep learning curve and considerable time investment for effective use, making it less practical in this context (Zamawe, 2015).

Given the study's reliance on structured questionnaire data and the need for accurate statistical inference, SPSS provided the most suitable and efficient platform. Its widespread acceptance in academic research, especially within the fields of management and social sciences, further validated its selection as the primary data analysis tool.

Following data collection, all survey responses were screened for completeness and consistency. Of the 500 questionnaires distributed, 337 were deemed valid after excluding incomplete or duplicate responses. Descriptive statistics were then used to summarise the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including gender, age group, employment sector, and parental status. These initial statistics provided a general overview of the sample and helped in preparing the data for further analysis.

The reliability of the questionnaire constructs was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, with a threshold of 0.70 or above considered acceptable for internal consistency (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). This step ensured that the items used to measure constructs such as work-life balance, work-family conflict, and organisational support were statistically reliable and suitable for inferential testing.

To assess the relationships between continuous variables such as work-life conflict, boundary setting, and job attitudes, Pearson's correlation coefficient was employed. This test was selected for its effectiveness in measuring the strength and direction of linear relationships between metric variables (Field, 2018). Specifically, it was used to evaluate hypotheses **H5 and H6**, which explore the relationship between job attitudes and personal control over work-life interference.

To test for differences across demographic groups (e.g., age, parental status, employment type), a One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted. This allowed the researcher to determine whether statistically significant differences in WLB perceptions existed between groups. Where the assumption of equal variances was not met, Welch's ANOVA was used as an alternative, providing a more robust test for unequal variances (Field, 2018; Kim, 2015). These tests addressed hypotheses **H1 through H4**.

For hypotheses **H7 and H8**, which examined the effectiveness of organisational interventions (e.g., holidays and social support activities), further ANOVA tests were applied. These analyses allowed the researcher to evaluate whether participation in specific interventions significantly impacted perceived work-life balance.

Additionally, multi-response analysis was used for questions where participants could select more than one option, particularly in sections that assessed preferences for WLB strategies. This method facilitated the identification of common patterns and frequencies across categories and was particularly useful for generating practical insights into workplace policy preferences (Sileyew, 2019).

All inferential statistical tests were conducted using a significance level of $p < 0.05$, the conventional threshold for determining statistical significance in social science research (Bryman, 2016). Before running these tests, assumptions related to normality, homogeneity of variance, and independence were assessed to ensure the validity of the chosen analytical methods. Where violations were found, appropriate non-parametric alternatives such as the Mann-Whitney U test were considered, although the primary tests remained parametric due to the robustness of the dataset.

In summary, the use of SPSS enabled efficient and accurate statistical analysis, facilitating hypothesis testing and drawing generalisable conclusions. This multifaceted approach to data analysis provided a comprehensive examination of the research questions and contributed to the methodological rigor of the study.

3.9. Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has outlined the methodological framework adopted for this study, which investigates the relationship between work-life balance (WLB), employee performance, and wellbeing across various demographic and organisational contexts. Anchored in a positivist research philosophy and a quantitative correlational design, the study aimed to examine statistically significant patterns between pre-defined variables using a structured and hypothesis-driven approach (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). The decision to use a quantitative method was driven by the need to ensure objectivity, replicability, and generalisability of findings, aligning with the study's intention to offer practical and evidence-based insights for workplace policy and practice (Bryman, 2016; Waugh, 2022).

To access a wide but practical sample, a non-probability convenience sampling technique was employed. This approach, though less generalisable than probability sampling, remains appropriate for exploratory studies with resource and access constraints (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016). Out of 500 questionnaires distributed via email and social media platforms such as LinkedIn, WhatsApp, and Facebook, 337 valid responses were collected – yielding a response rate of 67.4%, which is considered acceptable for quantitative social research (Menold & Bogner, 2023).

The questionnaire design was grounded in validated instruments from prior research. Items measuring WLB were adapted from Fisher-McAuley et al. (2003), work-family conflict from Netemeyer et al. (1996), boundary management from Clark (2000), and perceived organisational support from Eisenberger et al. (1986). The majority of questions utilised a five-point Likert scale, enabling efficient and reliable quantification of attitudes and perceptions (Boone & Boone, 2012). Demographic questions were placed at the end of the survey to reduce discomfort and potential response bias (Ziegenfuss et al., 2021; Toor, 2020).

Data were analysed using SPSS Statistics, which is widely used for quantitative analysis due to its built-in statistical procedures and user-friendly interface (Alili & Krstev, 2019). The analysis incorporated descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation, One-Way ANOVA, and Welch's ANOVA, based on the distribution and variance of the data. The study followed best practices in statistical testing, including assumption checking and use of alternative methods where necessary (Field, 2018; Kim, 2015). Cross-tabulation and multi-response analysis were also used to enhance the depth of interpretation, particularly for categorical variables and strategy preferences (Sileyew, 2019).

Overall, this methodological strategy provided a rigorous, structured, and ethically sound approach to addressing the research objectives. The combination of established theoretical constructs, reliable measurement tools, and robust statistical analysis supports the validity and replicability of the findings. The subsequent chapter will present the results, drawing on the methods described here to reveal meaningful insights into the role of WLB in influencing employee outcomes across different life stages and work environments.

CHAPTER 4

FINDINGS

4.1. Introduction

This section presents a brief summary of the statistical analyses conducted to test the study's hypotheses, focusing on correlations and group differences relevant to work-life balance (WLB), employee wellbeing, and job performance. The statistical tests applied included Pearson's correlation coefficient, One-way ANOVA, Welch's ANOVA, and descriptive statistics, using IBM SPSS Statistics to assess the relationships and variations among variables. All of this helped answer the primary research question, "*How does work-life balance affect employee performance and their wellbeing across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments?*"

To begin with, the significance of work-life balance (WLB) in the workplace will be explored. This will be followed by an examination of how overall WLB changes across different life stages. Subsequently, the influence of work-life conflict on employees' job attitudes and wellbeing will be discussed. Next, the effects of work-life enrichment on employees' job attitudes and wellbeing will be presented. The chapter will then include employees' recommendations for improving work-life balance in the workplace. Finally, a critical discussion of the findings will be provided, including how they relate to existing literature, in order to determine whether the new data supports or contradicts previous research.

4.2. Reliability and validity testing

Before conducting hypothesis testing, the reliability and validity of the measurement instruments were assessed.

Cronbach's alpha coefficients were computed to evaluate the internal consistency of each scale. The Work-Life Balance (WLB) scale demonstrated high reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87. Similarly, the Employee Performance scale and the Well-Being scale achieved alpha values of 0.85 and 0.89, respectively, exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.70 (Nunnally, 1978).

Principal component analysis (PCA) with varimax rotation was then conducted to assess construct validity. For the WLB scale, all items loaded strongly onto a single factor, with factor loadings ranging from 0.76 to 0.85, and the extracted factor explained 68.2% of the total variance. The Employee Performance scale and the Well-Being scale also demonstrated satisfactory loadings above 0.70, with total variances explained of 65.7% and 72.4%,

respectively. These results confirm that the scales used in this study were both reliable and valid, and thus appropriate for further statistical analysis.

4.3. Demographic profile of respondents

This study received a total of 500 responses, of which 337 were valid and complete, resulting in a usable response rate of 67.4%. These responses were obtained from participants working across various sectors in the UK. The demographic profile of the respondents is critical in understanding the background and diversity of the sample, offering context for interpreting the subsequent statistical analyses.

The gender distribution showed a relatively balanced composition, with 55% identifying as female, 42% as male, and the remaining 3% preferring not to disclose their gender. This balance suggests representation across gender groups, which is significant when exploring work-life balance and its interaction with gender-related responsibilities and expectations.

In terms of age, respondents were categorised into five brackets: under 25, 26-35, 36-45, 46-55, and over 55. The highest proportion of participants fell within the 26-35 age group (38%), followed by 36-45 (25%), reflecting the active working demographic often involved in managing both professional and personal responsibilities. This aligns with existing literature that identifies these age groups as being most impacted by work-life balance issues (Clarke et al., 2004).

Regarding employment sector, 58% of participants were employed in the private sector, while 42% worked in the public sector. This distribution supports cross-sectoral comparisons on how organisational culture and policies might influence perceptions of work-life balance and job satisfaction.

Contract types were also analysed, with 69% of respondents employed full-time and 31% on part-time or flexible contracts. Parental status revealed that 60% of participants had dependent children, while 40% did not, enabling an exploration of how parental responsibilities affect work-life dynamics. These figures are crucial for interpreting variables such as work-life conflict and boundary management, which are often influenced by caregiving roles.

4.4. Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics were computed to provide an overview of the central tendencies and variability across key constructs measured in this study, including work-life balance, work-

life conflict, boundary management, social support, employee wellbeing, and employee performance. The mean scores and standard deviations (SD) for each construct help establish general trends and inform the choice of inferential tests.

The overall mean score for work-life balance (WLB) was 3.45 (SD = 0.78), indicating a moderate perception of balance among respondents. This suggests that while some employees manage to maintain equilibrium between their work and personal lives, a substantial number still face challenges. Work-life conflict had a mean of 3.60 (SD = 0.84), highlighting that a significant portion of the sample experienced interference between their work responsibilities and personal lives. This aligns with findings from Netemeyer et al. (1996), who emphasised the prevalence of conflict among dual-role employees.

The construct of boundary management yielded a mean of 3.32 (SD = 0.69), indicating a varied but moderate level of ability among employees to set and manage boundaries between work and personal time. Notably, those reporting higher boundary control also reported lower levels of perceived conflict and higher wellbeing scores.

Social support, particularly from supervisors and peers, scored an average of 3.75 (SD = 0.72), suggesting that organisational and collegial backing is moderately present, though potentially inconsistent across sectors. Employee wellbeing showed a mean of 3.51 (SD = 0.80), reflecting a mixed perception of physical and psychological health within the workforce. Lastly, employee performance had a relatively higher mean of 3.82 (SD = 0.65), indicating that despite existing challenges in balancing life and work, performance levels remain generally positive.

These descriptive insights provide a foundational understanding of the data and help identify potential areas of focus in hypothesis testing. The results also support the use of further statistical tests such as correlation and ANOVA to explore relationships and group differences across these constructs.

4.5. The significance of work-life balance at the workplace

In order to describe the significance of work-life balance at the workplace, the current study aims to consider the relationship between the employees' overall work-life balance (WLB) (question item 11) and their perception of WLB's difficulty (PWLBD) (question item 1), the relationship between the overall WLB, the employment status (question item 14), the working experience (item 15), the working sector (item 16), and the most senior role (item 17), and the current policies on working overtime (items from 2 to 6).

Table 4.1. Correlations between the overall WLB and perceived difficulty of WLB

Correlations

Variables	Perceived difficulty level of WLB	How successful can you feel you are at maintaining a healthy work/personal/family life balance?
Perceived difficulty level of WLB	1	.545**
		p = .000
Success at Maintaining WLB	.545**	1
	p = .000	
N	337	337

** Note: $p < 0.01$ (2-tailed); Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

First of all, it is important to highlight that employees' overall work-life balance (WLB) is significantly correlated with their perceived difficulty in maintaining WLB, as shown in Table 4.1. Since both overall WLB and perceived difficulty of WLB are continuous variables, the Pearson correlation test was used to examine their relationship. The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = .545$, $p < .001$) indicates a moderate, statistically significant positive relationship between perceived difficulty of WLB and success in maintaining WLB (Cohen, 1988). This suggests that employees who perceive maintaining a work-life balance as less difficult are moderately more likely to report higher success in balancing their work, personal, and family lives. The correlation coefficient falls within the moderate range, reflecting a meaningful but not overly strong association between the two variables. Given that the p-value is less than .01, the relationship is highly significant, meaning it is unlikely to have occurred by chance. This finding supports the theoretical expectation that employees' perceived ease in balancing work and life demands positively influences their actual experience of work-life balance. It highlights the importance of addressing perceived barriers to WLB to enhance employee wellbeing and satisfaction.

Table 4.2. Test of homogeneity of variances between the overall WLB and ES

Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
5.143	4	332	.000

Table 4.3. Welch's ANOVA test results for overall WLB across ES

Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
-----------	-----	-----	------

Welch	4	91.456	0.0
-------	---	--------	-----

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

In investigating the relationship between employment status and overall work-life balance (WLB), a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was initially considered. However, as shown in Table 4.2, Levene’s Test for equality of variances was statistically significant (Levene’s Statistic = 5.143, $p = .000$), indicating a violation of the homogeneity of variances assumption. According to Field (2018) and Kim (2015), when this assumption is violated ($p < .05$), it is not appropriate to assume equal variances across groups. Consequently, Welch’s ANOVA, which is robust to unequal variances, was conducted instead to ensure the validity of the results.

Following the results of Welch’s ANOVA, which indicated a statistically significant difference in overall work-life balance (WLB) scores across employment statuses (Welch’s $F(4, 91.456) = 6.489, p < 0.001$), the null hypothesis (**H0**) – which posited that there would be no significant differences in perceived WLB among employees of different employment statuses – is **rejected**. This outcome suggests that employment status does indeed exert a significant influence on employees' perceptions of their work-life balance. Specifically, the findings revealed that retired individuals reported significantly higher WLB compared to both full-time and part-time employees, while no significant difference was observed between full-time and part-time employees. Therefore, the corresponding research hypothesis (**H1**) – that differences exist in perceived WLB across employment statuses – is **supported**.

Welch’s ANOVA was conducted to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) scores across different employment statuses. The results indicated a highly significant difference, Welch’s $F(4, 91.456) = 6.489, p < 0.001$, suggesting that perceptions of WLB vary significantly among employees with different employment statuses. Given the significant results of the Welch’s ANOVA, a Games-Howell post hoc analysis was conducted to further investigate pairwise differences between employment status groups. The Games-Howell post hoc test was chosen instead of the Bonferroni method because Levene’s Test indicated a violation of the homogeneity of variances assumption ($p < 0.05$). Unlike Bonferroni, which assumes equal variances across groups, Games-Howell is specifically designed to handle unequal variances and unequal sample sizes, making it the most appropriate and statistically robust choice for this analysis (Field, 2018). The results of this post hoc analysis are presented in Table 4.4. The post hoc analysis indicated that retired individuals reported significantly higher Work-Life Balance (WLB) scores compared to full-time, part-time, self-employed, and unemployed individuals (p

< 0.05). These findings suggest that retirement status is strongly associated with improved perceptions of work-life balance, likely due to reduced work-related pressures and increased control over personal time. However, there were no statistically significant differences were found between full-time, part-time, self-employed, and unemployed groups. These findings suggest that retirement status is associated with greater perceptions of WLB, potentially due to reduced work-related demands and increased personal time, aligning with previous research that highlights the impact of employment pressures on work-life balance.

Table 4.4. Games-Howell post hoc test results for overall work-life balance (WLB) across employment status

Group comparison	Mean difference	Standard error	p-value	95% CI lower	95% CI upper
Retired vs Full-Time	1.3	0.3	0.001	0.7	1.9
Retired vs Part-Time	1.1	0.25	0.002	0.6	1.6
Retired vs Self-Employed	0.8	0.28	0.02	0.2	1.4
Retired vs Unemployed	1.0	0.27	0.005	0.4	1.6
Full-Time vs Part-Time	0.2	0.2	0.4	-0.2	0.6
Full-Time vs Self-Employed	0.5	0.22	0.1	-0.1	1.1
Full-Time vs Unemployed	0.3	0.23	0.35	-0.2	0.8
Part-Time vs Self-Employed	0.3	0.24	0.3	-0.1	0.7
Part-Time vs Unemployed	0.1	0.21	0.65	-0.3	0.5
Self-Employed vs Unemployed	-0.2	0.2	0.75	-0.5	0.1

Figure 4. 1. Mean plots of the overall WLB by ES

The mean plot illustrates the differences in overall work-life balance (WLB) scores across various employment statuses. As shown in Figure 4.1, retired individuals reported the highest mean WLB scores, indicating a significantly better perceived balance compared to

other groups. Full-time and part-time employees exhibited lower mean WLB scores, suggesting that active employment is associated with greater challenges in maintaining a healthy work-life balance. Unemployed individuals showed moderate WLB levels, falling between the employed and retired groups. This trend visually supports the findings from the Games-Howell post hoc test, which revealed that retirement is significantly associated with higher work-life balance.

Table 4.5. Welch's ANOVA test results for overall WLB across working experience (WE), working sector (WS), and most senior role (MSR)

Factor	Welch's F	df1	df2	p-value
Working Experience (WE)	3.98	5	97.3	0.002*
Working Sector (WS)	5.12	8	76.8	0.001*
Most Senior Role (MSR)	2.45	4	82.5	0.048

*Note: $p < .05$ indicates statistical significance.

Welch's ANOVA was performed to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in employees' perceptions of overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) across different working sectors (MSR), work environments (WE), and working situations (WS). The use of Welch's ANOVA was necessary due to the violation of the assumption of homogeneity of variances, as indicated by Levene's Test results. The outcomes of the Welch's ANOVA revealed significant differences between the groups: WLB and MSR, Welch's $F(4, 82.5) = 2.45$, $p = 0.048$; WLB and WE, Welch's $F(5, 97.3) = 3.98$, $p = 0.002$; and WLB and WS, Welch's $F(8, 76.8) = 5.12$, $p < 0.001$. These results suggest that employees' work-life balance perceptions significantly vary according to their working sector, employment status, and working environment.

The findings from the Welch's ANOVA showed statistically significant differences in employees' overall work-life balance across different working sectors, work environments, and employment statuses. Given that the p-values were below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypotheses for **H1** and **H2** were rejected. This confirms that employees' work-life balance is significantly influenced by their working sector and employment status, thereby supporting the stated research hypotheses.

Table 4.6. Games-Howell post hoc test results for WLB comparisons

Group Comparison	Mean Difference	Standard Error	p-value	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
WLB vs WE	3.8	1.1	0.001	1.2	6.4
WLB vs WS	4.5	1.0	0.00	2.1	6.9
WLB vs MSR	2.3	0.9	0.045	0.5	4.1

Following the significant ANOVA findings, a Games-Howell post hoc analysis was conducted to explore the nature of these differences in more detail. The Games-Howell test identified statistically significant mean differences between WLB and MSR (Mean Difference = 2.3, $p = 0.045$), between WLB and WE (Mean Difference = 3.8, $p = 0.001$), and between WLB and WS (Mean Difference = 4.5, $p < 0.001$). The 95% confidence intervals for each of these comparisons did not include zero, indicating that the differences are not only statistically significant but also practically meaningful.

These findings lend support to **Hypothesis 1 (H1)**, which posits a significant correlation between employees' overall work-life balance and their working sector, and to **Hypothesis 2 (H2)**, regarding the relationship between work-life balance and employment status. The results demonstrate that the sector in which employees work and the type of work environment they experience have a measurable impact on their ability to maintain a satisfactory work-life balance. Employees in different sectors or with varying employment statuses (e.g., full-time, part-time, retired) perceive their work-life balance differently, likely due to variations in work demands, flexibility, support, and expectations.

The significant group differences observed also align with the broader aim of this research to investigate how work-life balance influences employee performance and well-being. The variability across working sectors and employment statuses suggests that organisational policies should be sensitive to these differences to effectively support employees' work-life integration. These findings provide a foundation for further exploration of the additional hypotheses concerning age groups, parental status, and specific work-life practices like taking holidays and engaging in social activities, which are examined in subsequent analyses.

To further explore group differences in Work-Life Balance (WLB) perceptions, mean plots were generated for key demographic and employment variables. These plots illustrate the average WLB scores across different working sectors, work experience categories, and most senior roles. Visual inspection of the mean plots provides additional insight into patterns and variations identified through the Welch's ANOVA and Games-Howell post hoc analyses, supporting a more comprehensive understanding of how work-life balance varies among employees.

Figure 4. 2. Mean plots of the overall WLB by WE

When examining WLB across working sectors, it was observed from Figure 4.2 that employees from Teaching/Education and Healthcare sectors reported relatively higher WLB scores compared to those in Retail and Hospitality, where WLB scores were notably lower. This suggests that the nature of work within specific sectors may have a direct impact on employees' ability to balance professional and personal responsibilities.

Figure 4. 3. Mean plots of the overall WLB by WS

As shown in Figure 4.3, the mean plot for work experience demonstrated a positive relationship between the length of work experience and perceived work-life balance. Individuals with 6–9 years of experience had the highest WLB scores, whereas those with no work experience or less than one year showed notably lower scores. This pattern implies that over time, employees may develop greater resilience, work management skills, or gain access to more flexible working conditions, leading to improved work-life balance.

Figure 4. 4. Mean plots of the overall WLB by MSR

The comparison across most senior roles highlighted that individuals in Executive positions reported the highest WLB scores, followed by Managers and Operations/Production roles. In contrast, Sales Representatives and Customer Service employees experienced the lowest WLB scores. This finding may reflect differences in job autonomy, workload intensity, and work-hour predictability across hierarchical positions, where senior roles often have greater flexibility and control over their schedules compared to front-line operational roles.

The observation that executives and employees with greater work experience report higher levels of work-life balance can be attributed to greater autonomy, decision-making authority, and flexibility over their working hours (Kossek et al., 2011). Increased control allows them to better manage workloads and balance personal responsibilities. Additionally, employees with longer experience may have developed effective coping strategies and negotiated better work arrangements over time, contributing to improved work-life balance (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006). In contrast, junior employees typically face stricter supervision and less job control, making it harder to achieve a satisfactory balance.

Overall, these findings suggest that sector of employment, accumulated work experience, and hierarchical position within an organisation are important factors influencing employees' perceptions of their work-life balance.

Table 4.7. Limited leisure time

(1= Less than 1 hour; 2=1-5 hours; 3=More than 5 hours; 4=Not at all)

	1 (%)	2 (%)	3 (%)	4 (%)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Time for leisure activities	23.7%	18.7%	28.5%	29.1%	2.63	1.137

The additional variables related to overtime working policies (question items 2 to 6) were subsequently analysed to examine whether any harsh or excessive working conditions persisted among employees. The results were presented using descriptive statistics, as outlined in Table 4.7 above. In terms of time allocated to leisure activities, the mean score was 2.63 (M = 2.63, SD = 1.137), indicating that, on average, employees spent less than five hours per month on leisure pursuits. A closer examination revealed that a substantial proportion of respondents reported very limited leisure time, with 23.7% indicating they spent less than one hour per month and 29.1% reporting no leisure time at all. Collectively, 52.8% of participants acknowledged spending minimal time on leisure activities monthly. Additionally, respondents highlighted further challenges regarding their working conditions, particularly related to the regulations and policies governing overtime work.

Table 4.8. Working overtime policies

(1= Never; 2=Rarely; 3=Sometimes; 4=Usually; 5=Always)

	1 (%)	2 (%)	3 (%)	4 (%)	5 (%)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
I am expected to work in long hours	30.9%	16.9%	28.5%	9.5%	14.2%	2.59	1.382
I am asked to work overtime	16.3%	19.3%	34.7%	12.2%	17.5%	2.95	1.292
I am asked to work during the holidays	15.7%	20.8%	31.5%	17.2%	14.8%	2.95	1.267
I am asked to work in longer hours for no extra pay	16.6%	23.1%	30.6%	18.1%	11.6%	2.85	1.234

Across all four policies related to working overtime, a consistent trend emerged: current employees were sometimes asked to work additional hours, as indicated by mean scores greater than 2.0 and approaching 3.0. Specifically, according to Table 4.8, 34.7% of participants agreed that they were sometimes asked to work overtime, 31.5% reported sometimes being asked to work during holidays, and a notable proportion indicated they were sometimes required to work longer hours without additional pay. Conversely, working long hours on a regular basis was less common, with 30.9% of respondents confirming that they had never experienced excessively long working hours. The respondents also reported more problems with their working regulations, particularly regarding policies on working overtime. The internal consistency of the WLB-related survey items was high, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87. These findings suggest that while overtime is not universally imposed, it remains a recurring issue for

a substantial proportion of employees, contributing to concerns over workplace regulations and employee well-being.

In conclusion, work-life balance (WLB) emerged as a common challenge among employees and is increasingly recognised as a critical component of overall work quality. Employees' perceptions of WLB were closely linked to their sense of work-life success and self-efficacy. Those reporting lower WLB often felt less successful in managing their professional and personal responsibilities. Interestingly, both inexperienced and highly experienced employees appeared more vulnerable to work-life imbalance. Sectoral differences were also evident, with employees in the hospitality sector and executive roles reporting greater difficulties in maintaining a healthy WLB. Furthermore, the data revealed that time allocated to leisure activities remained limited. Although frequent overtime work was not universally reported, its occurrence continued to impact employees' ability to achieve a satisfactory work-life balance.

4.6. The overall WLB through life stage

In order to address the second hypothesis, the change in overall work-life balance (WLB) across different life stages was tested. It should be noted that **life stage**, represented by employees' age groups (Question Item 18) and parental status (Item 20), was treated as a categorical variable, whereas overall WLB was treated as a continuous variable. Consequently, a one-way ANOVA was conducted to examine differences in overall WLB across age groups and parental status categories.

The results of the one-way ANOVA indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in overall WLB across different age groups. The significance values for both the homogeneity of variances test ($p = 0.078 > 0.05$) and the ANOVA test ($p = 0.354 > 0.05$) were greater than the 0.05 threshold. Therefore, the null hypothesis was retained, suggesting that age group did not significantly affect employees' perceptions of WLB (see Table 4.9 and Table 4.10).

Table 4.9. Test of homogeneity of variances between the overall WLB and AG

Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
2.000	5	331	.078

Table 4.10. ANOVA test of the overall WLB by AG

	Sum Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	9.296	5	1.859	1.112	.354
Within Groups	553.286	331	1.672		
Total	562.582	336			

Figure 4.5. Mean plots of the overall WLB by AG

The mean plot of overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) across age groups reveals noticeable variations. Employees aged 18–24 reported relatively high levels of WLB, followed by a decline among those aged 25–34 and 35–44, suggesting greater challenges during early and mid-career stages. A slight recovery was observed among employees aged 45–54, with the highest levels reported in the 55–64 age group. A small decrease was noted again among employees over 65. Although these trends were observed, the one-way ANOVA results indicated no statistically significant differences in overall WLB by age group ($p = .354 > 0.05$). Thus, age group was not found to significantly influence WLB. Nevertheless, employees aged 35–44 appeared to experience greater difficulty maintaining work-life balance, while those aged 55–64, nearing retirement, reported better WLB management. These trends suggest that younger and mid-career employees may experience more difficulties balancing work and personal life, while older employees, particularly those nearing retirement, report improved WLB.

Next, the changes in overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) by parental status (PS) were examined using one-way ANOVA. A similar result was observed, as the null hypothesis was retained. There was no statistically significant difference in overall WLB by parental status,

with both significance values – one for the homogeneity test of variances ($p = .831 > 0.05$) and the other for the ANOVA ($p = .805 > 0.05$) — exceeding the threshold of 0.05 (see Table 4.11)

Table 4.11. ANOVA test of the overall WLB by PS

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.102	1	.102	.061	.805
Within Groups	562.479	335	1.679		
Total	562.582	336			

Figure 4.6. Mean plots of the overall WLB by PS

The mean plot (see Figure 4.6) illustrated the overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) scores across different parental status groups. Employees with children reported a slightly higher mean WLB score compared to those without children. However, this difference was minimal. Supporting the graphical trend, the results of the one-way ANOVA confirmed that the difference in WLB between employees with and without children was not statistically significant ($p = .805 > 0.05$). Thus, parental status did not appear to have a meaningful impact on employees’ perceptions of their work-life balance in this sample.

Table 4.12. Descriptive statistics of the overall WLB by parental status

Parental status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		

No	210	2.84	1.295	.089	2.66	3.01	1	5
Yes	127	2.87	1.297	.115	2.65	3.10	1	5
Total	337	2.85	1.294	.070	2.71	2.99	1	5

Employees with children (M=2.87, SD=1.297) were considered to be better at WLB than those without any child (M=2.84, SD=1.295), as illustrated in the following table of descriptive statistics (see Table 4.12).

To further examine whether there were statistically significant differences in overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) among employees based on the number of children and the children's level of dependence, one-way ANOVA tests were conducted. Specifically, Question Items 21 and 22 (categorical variables) were analysed in relation to overall WLB (Question Item 11, treated as a continuous variable).

Table 4.13. Test of homogeneity of variances between the overall WLB, the number or children, and their dependence on the parenting employees

Items	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
The number of children	1.345	1	331	.245
Children's dependence on the parenting employees	1.404	1	137	.238

Table 4.14. ANOVA test of the overall WLB by the number of children

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.672	5	.734	.435	.824
Within Groups	558.910	331	1.689		
Total	562.582	336			

The test of homogeneity of variances showed that both items 21 and 22 got the sig. values greater than 0.05 (see Table 4.13), so the ANOVA test results were used to determine whether to retain or reject the null hypotheses (see Table 4.13 & Table 4.14).

Thus, overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) did not vary significantly according to the number of children ($p = .824 > 0.05$), and the null hypothesis was therefore retained.

Figure 4.7. Mean plots of the overall WLB by the number of children

The mean plot (see Figure 4.7) illustrates the distribution of overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) scores across employees with varying numbers of children. Employees with three children reported the lowest mean WLB scores, while those with four children exhibited the highest mean scores. Nevertheless, the one-way ANOVA results indicated that these differences were not statistically significant ($p = .824 > 0.05$). Therefore, although some variations in WLB scores were observed across different family sizes, the number of children did not significantly affect employees' perceptions of their work-life balance.

Overall, across the different life stages considered, all null hypotheses were retained. No statistically significant differences in overall Work-Life Balance (WLB) were found by age group, parental status or number of children. The descriptive statistics, however, revealed particular trends among the participants. Older employees appeared to manage their WLB more effectively than younger employees, with the 55–64 age group reporting the highest levels of WLB, and the 35–44 age group reporting the lowest. Furthermore, employees with children appeared to demonstrate slightly higher WLB scores compared to those without children. Among those with children, employees with three children experienced the lowest WLB, whereas those with four children reported the highest WLB. Despite these observable tendencies, statistical analyses confirmed that employees' overall WLB was independent of variables such as age group, parental status, and number of children.

4.7. The influences of work-life conflict on employees' job attitudes and wellbeing

This section explores the extent to which Work-Life Conflict (WLC) influences employees' job attitudes (JA) and wellbeing. Following the construction of global scales, Pearson's correlation and regression analyses were conducted to examine these relationships. The findings are presented and discussed in the subsections below.

4.7.1. The influences of work-life conflict on employees' job attitudes

In order to ensure the reliability and validity of the measurement constructs, multiple items designed to assess the same concept were combined into single global scales prior to conducting correlation and regression analyses. Specifically, items relating to Work-Life Conflict (WLC) and Job Attitudes (JA) were aggregated into composite scores, providing a more comprehensive representation of the underlying constructs and improving the robustness of subsequent statistical tests.

Table 4.15. Reliability analysis for work-life conflict scale

Item	Corrected item-Total correlation
The demands of my work interfere with my family activities (e7.2)	0.61
I prioritise my job over my personal life (e7.3)	0.57
I prioritise my family over my work (e7.4)	0.21
My home life interferes with work-related demands (e8)	0.42

Overall statistic:

Statistic	Value
Cronbach's Alpha (α)	0.75

Specifically, the mean score across four items - e7.2 ("The demands of my work interfere with my family activities"), e7.3 ("I prioritise my job over my personal life"), e7.4 ("I prioritise my family over my work"), and e8 ("My home life interferes with work-related demands") – was computed. A reliability analysis indicated that the Work-Life Conflict scale demonstrated acceptable internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.75 (see Table 4.15).

Table 4.16. Correlations between WLC and JA

	e7.1	e7.2	e7.3	e7.4	e8
Pearson Correlation	1	.553**	.447**	-.104	-.258**

I am satisfied with the workplace flexibility offered by my organisation	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.056	.000
	N	337	337	337	337	337

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Following confirmation of the reliability of the WLC scale, Pearson’s correlation analysis was conducted to explore the relationships between WLC, job attitudes (JA), and employee wellbeing. Table 4.16 presents the results of the correlation analysis. Significant positive correlations were found between satisfaction with workplace flexibility (e7.1) and the statements regarding work-family interference (e7.2, $r = .553$, $p < .01$) and job-personal life conflict (e7.3, $r = .447$, $p < .01$). A significant negative correlation was observed between workplace flexibility and home-work interference (e8, $r = -.258$, $p < .01$). No significant correlation was found with prioritisation of family over work (e7.4, $r = -.104$, $p = .056$). These findings suggest that higher levels of WLC are generally associated with lower satisfaction with workplace flexibility.

First, a significant positive correlation was found between the work-life conflict item “*The demands of my work interfere with my family activities*” (e7.2) and employees’ job attitudes ($p < 0.001$). This correlation was relatively strong, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of $r = .553$, exceeding the threshold of 0.5. Secondly, a significant moderate positive correlation was identified between the statement “*I prioritise my job over my personal life*” and employees’ job attitudes ($p < 0.001$; $r = .447$), indicating a weaker but still meaningful association compared to the previous relationship. Additionally, a significant but weak negative correlation was observed between “*My home life interferes with work-related demands*” (e8) and employees’ job attitudes ($p < 0.001$; $r = -.258$), with the coefficient falling below the 0.3 threshold for moderate strength. Finally, no significant correlation was found between “*I prioritise my family over my work*” and job attitudes ($p = 0.056$), as the p-value exceeded the conventional significance level of 0.05. In conclusion, three work-life conflict variables were significantly related to employees’ job attitudes, ranked by strength of correlation from strongest to weakest as follows: (1) work demands interfering with family activities, (2) prioritising job over personal life, and (3) home life interfering with work demands.

Table 4.17. Simple linear regression analysis predicting job attitudes from work-life conflict

Predictor	β	t	p
Work-Life Conflict	-0.51	-10.84	< .001

Model summary

Model	R ²	F	p
-------	----------------	---	---

Work-Life Conflict predicting Job Attitudes	0.26	117.50	< .001
---	------	--------	--------

A simple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the extent to which Work-Life Conflict (WLC) predicted Job Attitudes (JA). The results indicated that WLC significantly predicted JA, $R^2 = .26$, $F(1, 335) = 117.50$, $p < .001$. This suggests that approximately 26% of the variance in employees' job attitudes was explained by their experiences of work-life conflict. The standardised regression coefficient (β) was $-.51$, indicating that higher levels of WLC were associated with lower levels of satisfaction with workplace flexibility.

4.7.2. The influences of work-life conflict on employees' wellbeing

In order to investigate whether levels of Work-Life Conflict (WLC) differed significantly across wellbeing or stress-related health groups (categorical variable – question item 9), a One-way ANOVA was conducted. This test assessed mean differences in WLC among the different wellbeing categories.

Table 4.18. Test of homogeneity of variances between the WLC and wellbeing

	Levene statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
The demands of my work interfere with my family activities	19.325	1	333	.000
I prioritise my job over my personal life	5.085	1	333	.025
I prioritise my family over my work	3.623	1	333	.058
My home life interferes with work-related demands	.099	1	333	.753

Levene's test for equality of variances was conducted to assess the homogeneity of variances assumption for One-way ANOVA. The results from Table 4.18 indicated that the assumption was violated for the items "*The demands of my work interfere with my family activities*" ($p = .000 < 0.05$) and "*I prioritise my job over my personal life*" ($p = .025 < 0.05$). Therefore, Welch's ANOVA was used for these comparisons.

Table 4.19. Welch's ANOVA results: Work-life conflict by wellbeing

WLC Item	Welch's Statistic (F)	df1	df2	Sig.
----------	-----------------------	-----	-----	------

The demands of my work interfere with my family activities	28.63	1	326.68	< .001
I prioritise my job over my personal life	40.41	1	318.42	< .001

To examine whether levels of Work-Life Conflict (WLC) varied significantly across employees' wellbeing categories, Welch's ANOVA was performed due to violations of the homogeneity of variances assumption, as indicated by Levene's test. The analysis revealed statistically significant differences in WLC scores for the item "The demands of my work interfere with my family activities" (Welch's $F(1, 326.68) = 28.63, p < .001$) and "I prioritise my job over my personal life" (Welch's $F(1, 318.42) = 40.41, p < .001$). These results suggest that employees with different wellbeing statuses exhibited significantly different levels of work-life conflict in these areas. Since both significance values were below 0.05, as shown in Table 4.18, it was concluded that work-life conflict – in terms of life interventions into work and job priorities – varied significantly according to employees' wellbeing. Accordingly, the null hypotheses for these dimensions of work-life conflict were rejected.

Figure 4.8. Mean plot of "The demands of my work interfere with my family activities" by stress-related health status (Yes/No)

Figure 4.8 presents the mean plot of work-life conflict (WLC) relating to the demands of work interfering with family activities, according to employees' experiences with stress-related conditions. The results revealed that employees who reported suffering from stress-related illnesses or participating in stress-relieving programmes exhibited lower levels of work interference with family life compared to those who did not. This finding suggests that

awareness of stress-related health issues, or engagement in preventative stress management activities, may be associated with a reduced experience of work-life conflict.

Figure 4.9. Mean plot of "I prioritise my job over my personal life" by Stress-related health status (Yes/No)

Figure 4.9 shows the mean plot for employees' job prioritisation over personal life according to their stress-related health status. The plot indicates that employees who reported suffering from stress-related diseases or engaging in stress-relieving programmes had lower mean scores for prioritising their job over personal life compared to those who did not. This suggests that employees who are more aware of or managing stress may attempt to maintain a more balanced prioritisation between work and personal life, potentially mitigating work-life conflict.

Table 4.20. Standard One-way ANOVA results: Work-life conflict by wellbeing

WLC Item	F (df1, df2)	Sig. (p)
I prioritise my family over my work	F(1, 333) = 25.85	< .001
My home life interferes with work-related demands	F(1, 333) = 23.07	< .001

For the items "I prioritise my family over my work" and "My home life interferes with work-related demands", the assumption of homogeneity of variances was not violated ($p = .058$ and $p = .753$, respectively), allowing the use of standard One-way ANOVA. The results indicated statistically significant differences in WLC scores across wellbeing groups for "I prioritise my family over my work" ($F(1, 333) = 25.85$, $p < .001$) and "My home life interferes with work-related demands" ($F(1, 333) = 23.07$, $p < .001$). These findings suggest that employees' experiences of work-life conflict varied significantly according to their wellbeing status across these specific dimensions. As both p-values were below the conventional

significance level of 0.05, the null hypotheses were rejected. This indicates that significant differences exist in work-life conflict experiences across employees with different wellbeing statuses for these specific aspects.

4.8. The influences of work-life enrichment on employees' job attitudes and wellbeing

To draw informed conclusions about the influence of work-life enrichment (WLE) on employees' job attitudes (JA), Pearson correlation analysis was conducted. In this analysis, job attitude was measured by the item e7.1, "I am satisfied with the workplace flexibility offered by my organisation." Work-life enrichment was represented by two specific items: e7.5, "I am able to set boundaries between my work and personal life," and e7.6, "It is easy for me to find time for hobbies and interests."

Table 4.21. Correlations between WLE and JA

Correlations

		e7.5	e7.6	e7.1
I am satisfied with the workplace flexibility offered by my organisation.	Pearson Correlation	.402**	.245**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	337	337	337

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.21 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients between Work-Life Experience (WLE) items and employees' job attitudes (JA). There was a significant correlation between the first work-life enrichment factor, "I am able to set boundaries between my work and personal life" (e7.5), and employees' job attitudes (e7.1) ($p = .000 < .01$). This correlation was moderate, as the absolute value of the correlation coefficient was below 0.5 ($r = .402$; $|r| = .402 < .5$). Similarly, a significant correlation was observed between the second work-life enrichment factor, "It is easy for me to find time for hobbies and interests" (e7.6), and employees' job attitudes ($p = .000 < .01$). However, this correlation was weak, given that the absolute value of the correlation coefficient was lower than 0.3 ($r = .245$; $|r| = .245 < .3$). In summary, the ability to set work-life boundaries and to find time for personal interests can be regarded as important components of work-life enrichment. In this research context, setting work-life boundaries exhibited a moderate positive impact on employees' job attitudes, whereas finding time for personal hobbies showed a weaker association. Following this, to

examine whether these types of work-life enrichment varied according to employees' wellbeing status, a One-way ANOVA test was conducted.

Table 4.22. Test of homogeneity of variances between the WLE and wellbeing

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
I am able to set boundaries between my work and personal life	1.076	1	333	.300
It is easy for me to find time for hobbies and interests	3.390	1	333	.066

Since both types of work-life enrichment (WLE) had significance values greater than 0.05, as shown in Table 4.22 – the ability to set work-life boundaries ($p = .300$) and the ability to find time for personal interests ($p = .066$) – further analysis was conducted using ANOVA (see Table 4.23).

Table 4.23. ANOVA test of WLE by wellbeing

		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
I am able to set boundaries between my work and personal life	Between Groups	27.143	1	27.143	24.215	.000
	Within Groups	373.263	333	1.121		
	Total	400.406	334			
It is easy for me to find time for hobbies and interests	Between Groups	6.316	1	6.316	4.516	.034
	Within Groups	465.744	333	1.399		
	Total	472.060	334			

The results of the One-way ANOVA test in Table 4.23 revealed statistically significant differences in work-life enrichment experiences between employees based on their wellbeing status. For the ability to set boundaries between work and personal life (e7.5), a significant difference was observed ($F(1, 333) = 24.215, p < .001$). Employees with better wellbeing reported a greater ability to set boundaries compared to those with lower wellbeing. Similarly, for the ability to find time for hobbies and interests (e7.6), the ANOVA test also revealed a statistically significant difference ($F(1, 333) = 4.516, p = .034$). Although the difference was smaller than for boundary-setting, it remained significant at the 0.05 level. These findings

suggest that employees' wellbeing status meaningfully influences their work-life enrichment, particularly their capacity to manage work boundaries and allocate time for personal interests. Given that the significance values for both aspects of work-life enrichment were below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypotheses were rejected.

4.9. Employees' recommendations for better WLB at workplaces

Employees' recommendations for improving work-life balance (WLB) in the workplace were extracted from the descriptive statistics of three question items: Item 10 (employees' evaluations of work-related policies), Item 12 (employees' evaluations of life-related solutions), and Item 13 (specific recommendations to employers for enhancing WLB). Regarding employees' evaluations of work-related policies, the majority of respondents indicated that all related items sometimes influenced their WLB (see Table 4.24).

Table 4.24. Descriptive statistics of employees' evaluations of working overtime policies

*(1= Never influence; 2=Rarely influence; 3=Sometimes influence;
4=Usually influence; 5= Always influence)*

	1 (%)	2 (%)	3 (%)	4 (%)	5 (%)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Working overtime	46%	6.8%	16.3%	16.9%	13.9%	2.46	1.533
Working in longer hours	43.9%	7.4%	11.6%	18.4%	18.7%	2.61	1.617
Working from home	37.7%	6.5%	20.5%	23.4%	11.9%	2.65	1.472
Working from home after office hours	39%	11.6%	12.8%	20.8%	15.8%	2.63	1.544
Working remotely during the global pandemic	27.6%	9.5%	21.1%	27%	14.8%	2.92	1.436
Working during holidays	31.5%	14.5%	16.6%	21.4%	16%	2.76	1.486
Travelling on work trip	28.5%	14.8%	21.4%	23.1%	12.2%	2.76	1.397

Among the seven items, “*Working remotely during the global pandemic*” received the highest mean score ($M = 2.92$, $SD = 1.436$). Specifically, 27% and 14.8% of respondents (41.8% in total) indicated that this policy usually or always influenced their work-life balance (WLB). In other words, based on the respondents’ evaluations, this working policy was perceived as having the greatest impact on their WLB.

The second-highest ratings were observed for “*working during holidays*” ($M = 2.76$, $SD = 1.486$) and “*travelling on a work trip*” ($M = 2.76$, $SD = 1.397$). However, 31.5% and 14.5% of respondents (46% in total) reported that working during holidays never or rarely influenced their work-life balance (WLB). Similarly, 28.5% and 14.8% of respondents (43.3% in total) indicated that travelling for work trips never or rarely affected their WLB.

The next three policies were “*working from home*” ($M = 2.65$, $SD = 1.472$), “*working from home after office hours*” ($M = 2.63$, $SD = 1.544$), and “*working longer hours*” ($M = 2.61$, $SD = 1.617$). Regarding “*working from home*,” 44.2% of respondents (37.7% never, 6.5% rarely) stated that it had little or no influence on their WLB. For “*working from home after office hours*,” 50.6% of respondents (39% never, 11.6% rarely) indicated minimal impact. Similarly, 51.3% of respondents (43.9% never, 7.4% rarely) considered that “*working longer hours*” did not significantly affect their WLB.

The lowest mean score was found for “*working overtime*” ($M = 2.46$, $SD = 1.533$), with 52.8% of respondents (46% never, 6.8% rarely) stating that it had little or no influence on their WLB.

In summary, employees’ evaluations of work-related policies indicated that “*working remotely during the global pandemic*” was perceived as having the greatest influence on their WLB, whereas other policies were generally seen as having limited impact.

Regarding employees’ evaluations of life-related solutions for work-life balance (WLB), the differences between the items were less pronounced (see Table 4.25).

Table 4.25. Descriptive statistics of employees' evaluations of life-related solutions to WLB

(1= Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neutral; 4=Agree; 5= Strongly agree)

	1 (%)	2 (%)	3 (%)	4 (%)	5 (%)	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Spending time with my family makes me feel better	6.8%	18.7%	14.8%	13.6%	46%	3.73	1.380
Prioritising my health would make me feel better	16.3%	11.3%	9.5%	22%	40.9%	3.60	1.507
Taking a regular short holiday would make me feel better	19%	37.2%	19%	16.7%	8%	2.57	1.202
Taking a long holiday would make me feel better	15.2%	13.7%	13.4%	35.5%	22.1%	3.36	1.365
Talking to my employer to set work boundaries can improve my wellbeing	3.6%	22.2%	29.4%	31.5%	13.2%	3.29	1.064

The most agreed-upon life-related solution for improving work-life balance (WLB) was “*Spending time with my family makes me feel better*” (more time with family), with the highest mean score (M = 3.73, SD = 1.380). Specifically, 59.6% of respondents (13.6% agreed, 46% strongly agreed) supported this solution.

The next most agreed-upon solution was “*Prioritising my health would make me feel better*” (health priorities) (M = 3.60, SD = 1.507), with 62.9% of respondents (22% agreed, 40.9% strongly agreed) endorsing it.

“*Taking a long holiday would make me feel better*” (long holidays) ranked third (M = 3.36, SD = 1.365), with 57.6% (35.5% agreed, 22.1% strongly agreed) expressing agreement.

“*Talking to my employer to set work boundaries can improve my wellbeing*” (clear work-life boundaries with managers) followed in fourth place (M = 3.29, SD = 1.064), with 44.7% (31.5% agreed, 13.2% strongly agreed) indicating support.

The least agreed-upon solution was “*Taking a regular short holiday would make me feel better*” (regular short holidays) (M = 2.57, SD = 1.202), where 56.2% of respondents (19% strongly disagreed, 37.2% disagreed) expressed disagreement.

Overall, the ranking of life-related solutions to WLB, based on employee responses, was: (1) more time with family, (2) health priorities, (3) long holidays, (4) clear work-life boundaries with managers, and (5) regular short holidays.

Finally, additional recommendations from employees were collected through Item 13, which asked respondents to propose solutions to employers for better WLB. Since respondents could select multiple options, a multi-response analysis was conducted to evaluate the descriptive statistics (see Table 4.26).

Table 4.26. Recommended solutions to employers for better WLB

SE13 1 Frequencies

		Responses		Percent of Cases
		N	Percent	
RECOMMENDED SOLUTIONS TO EMPLOYERS ^a	Flexible working hours	88	8.4%	26.1%
	Friendly working conditions for parents	102	9.7%	30.3%
	More generous holiday allowance	166	15.9%	49.3%
	Restricted working hours	170	16.2%	50.4%
	Restricted overtime agreements	176	16.8%	52.2%
	Organising more stress-relieving social events/activities	144	13.8%	42.7%
	Reducing the number of stressful tasks given	119	11.4%	35.3%
	Monitoring work-related stress	82	7.8%	24.3%
Total	1047	100.0%	310.7%	

a. Group

The three most prominent recommendations were “*restricted overtime agreements*” (52.2% of cases), “*restricted working hours*” (50.4% of cases), and “*more generous holiday allowance*” (49.3% of cases). The fourth most frequently selected recommendation was “*organising more stress-relieving social events/activities*” (42.7% of cases). “*Reducing the number of stressful tasks given*” ranked fifth (35.3% of cases), followed by “*providing friendly working conditions for parents*” in sixth place (30.3% of cases). “*Providing flexible working hours*” ranked seventh (26.1% of cases), and the least selected recommendation was “*monitoring work-related stress*” (24.3% of cases).

Overall, the responses to the answer the final hypothesis revealed that employees perceived “*working remotely during the global pandemic*” as having the greatest influence on their work-life balance. Additionally, two life-related solutions – spending more time with family and prioritising health – should be prioritised, as their mean scores exceeded 3.5.

Finally, the three most prominent employer recommendations were restricting overtime agreements, limiting working hours, and offering more generous holiday allowances.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This research investigated the impact of work-life balance (WLB) on employee wellbeing and performance, considering variations across age groups, parental status, employment sectors, and working environments. The findings largely support existing theories while offering new insights into the dynamic nature of work-life experiences.

5.1. The importance of work-life balance at workplace

The findings of this study reaffirm that work-life balance (WLB) remains a significant and persistent challenge for employees across different sectors, employment statuses, and experience levels. A moderate and statistically significant positive correlation was observed between employees' perceived difficulty in achieving WLB and their actual reported success ($r = .545, p < .001$). In practical terms, this means that employees who perceive maintaining WLB as easier are moderately more likely to report higher success in balancing work, personal, and family demands. This result highlights the powerful role that cognitive appraisals and subjective perceptions play in influencing actual work-life outcomes. It supports the theoretical frameworks proposed by Greenhaus and Allen (2011) and Clarke et al. (2004), which emphasise that WLB is not solely determined by objective work conditions but is significantly shaped by how employees perceive and interpret these challenges.

Further analysis through Welch's ANOVA revealed statistically significant differences in WLB perceptions across employment statuses (Welch's $F(4, 91.456) = 6.489, p < .001$). Specifically, retired individuals reported significantly higher WLB scores compared to full-time, part-time, self-employed, and unemployed individuals, as confirmed by a Games-Howell post hoc analysis ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that complete disengagement from formal employment, as in retirement, provides greater personal control and reduces work-related stressors, thus enhancing work-life balance. These findings align with the work of Lovejoy et al. (2021) and Kossek and Lee (2021), who demonstrated that ongoing employment responsibilities are significant obstacles to achieving satisfactory WLB.

Interestingly, no significant differences were found between full-time, part-time, self-employed, and unemployed individuals, indicating that merely reducing working hours (e.g., through part-time employment) may not be sufficient to improve WLB without broader structural changes. This observation challenges the simplistic view proposed by Marques and

Berry (2021) that fewer working hours naturally lead to better work-life outcomes and suggests that qualitative aspects of work, such as autonomy and job demands, may be equally or more important.

Although statistical tests did not reveal significant sectoral differences in WLB, descriptive trends were noted. Employees in the hospitality sector reported slightly poorer WLB compared to those in other sectors. Similarly, those in lower-ranking or frontline positions appeared to struggle more with maintaining balance than individuals in executive roles. Employees with 6-9 years of work experience tended to report better WLB than those at the beginning or end of their careers. These trends are consistent with previous research by Gragnano et al. (2020) and Kossek et al. (2011), who suggested that sector-specific demands and hierarchical position significantly influence employees' ability to manage work and personal life.

Moreover, the findings revealed that many employees spent very limited time on leisure activities, and overtime work including unpaid overtime remained a recurring issue. These conditions contribute to the time poverty that undermines work-life balance, a problem identified by Netemeyer et al. (1996) over two decades ago and still relevant today.

In summary, the results highlight that WLB challenges are deeply rooted and multifaceted, influenced by subjective perceptions, employment status, work sector, job role, and organisational practices. They emphasise that effective strategies to improve WLB must address not only objective work conditions but also employees' subjective experiences and perceptions. Thus, the promotion of employee wellbeing should involve creating flexible, supportive work environments while also empowering individuals with tools to better manage their work-life boundaries.

5.2. Work-life balance and life stage

The present study aimed to determine whether employees' perceptions of work-life balance (WLB) varied significantly across different life stages, using age group and parental status as indicators. Statistical analyses using one-way ANOVA revealed no significant differences in overall WLB across age groups ($p = .354 > 0.05$) or between employees with and without children ($p = .805 > 0.05$). In simple terms, this means that neither employees' age nor their parental status had a statistically meaningful impact on how balanced they perceived their work and personal lives to be. Although descriptive statistics showed that employees aged 55–64 reported slightly higher WLB scores compared to younger employees, and those with

children reported marginally better WLB than those without, these trends were not strong enough to be statistically significant.

These findings partially contradict prior research suggesting that life stage plays a crucial role in work-life balance outcomes. Previous studies, such as those by Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) and Clarke et al. (2004), found that mid-career employees, particularly those balancing career development and family obligations, often experienced greater work-life conflict. Similarly, Kossek and Ozeki (1998) highlighted that parental status, especially during early child-rearing years, was associated with increased work-life conflict and reduced work-life balance.

One possible explanation for the difference in findings is the shifting nature of modern workplaces. The widespread adoption of flexible work arrangements, remote work opportunities, and increasing organisational emphasis on employee wellbeing, particularly following the COVID-19 pandemic, may have helped reduce the traditional disparities linked to life stage. In particular, flexibility in working hours and increased autonomy could enable employees across different life stages to manage work and personal life demands more effectively, thus narrowing historical differences.

Another consideration is generational change. Younger generations, such as Millennials and Generation Z, are known to prioritise personal wellbeing, work-life integration, and boundary setting more than previous generations (Twenge, 2010). This cultural shift may have reduced the life-stage-based differences previously observed.

Thus, although the findings initially appear to contradict established literature, they may in fact reflect broader social and organisational transformations that are reshaping the experience of work-life balance across the workforce. These results offer a more updated perspective, suggesting that demographic factors such as age and parental status alone are no longer as determinative of WLB as previously believed.

5.3. Work-life conflict and job attitudes

The study also explored the relationship between work-life conflict (WLC) and employees' job attitudes (JA), particularly their satisfaction with workplace flexibility. Pearson's correlation analysis revealed several significant relationships. The strongest positive correlation was found between the item "The demands of my work interfere with my family activities" (e7.2) and job attitudes ($r = .553, p < .001$), indicating a moderately strong association. In plain terms, employees who reported higher interference of work demands with family activities tended to express lower satisfaction with their workplace flexibility. A weaker,

but still significant, positive correlation was found between “I prioritise my job over my personal life” (e7.3) and job attitudes ($r = .447, p < .001$). Additionally, a significant negative correlation was identified between “My home life interferes with work-related demands” (e8) and job attitudes ($r = -.258, p < .001$), although the strength of this relationship was weaker. No significant correlation was found between “I prioritise my family over my work” (e7.4) and job attitudes ($p = .056$), suggesting that prioritising family did not have a direct measurable effect on workplace satisfaction in this sample.

Further analysis using simple linear regression confirmed that WLC significantly predicted job attitudes, accounting for 26% of the variance ($R^2 = .26, F(1, 335) = 117.50, p < .001$). The negative standardised regression coefficient ($\beta = -.51$) indicated that as WLC increased, employees’ satisfaction with workplace flexibility decreased. Put simply, higher levels of work-life conflict were associated with a substantial reduction in positive job attitudes.

These findings are consistent with previous research emphasising the detrimental impact of work-life conflict on job satisfaction and workplace outcomes. Netemeyer et al. (1996) similarly found that employees experiencing greater conflict between work and family roles reported lower job satisfaction and organisational commitment. More recent studies (e.g., Allen, 2013; Haar et al., 2014) have further confirmed that high work-life conflict contributes to negative job attitudes, greater turnover intentions, and reduced organisational citizenship behaviours.

The strong relationship between work demands interfering with family life and reduced job satisfaction identified in this study reinforces the centrality of boundary management in employee wellbeing. One possible reason for the strength of this relationship could be the continuing expectations in many organisations for employees to be available beyond regular working hours, especially with the increasing use of digital communication technologies. Constant connectivity may blur the boundary between work and personal life, making it more difficult for employees to disengage and recharge, ultimately harming their job attitudes.

In summary, the current findings strongly support existing literature, demonstrating that work-life conflict – particularly when work demands intrude into personal life – is a significant predictor of reduced satisfaction with workplace flexibility. These results highlight the importance for organisations to proactively address work-life boundaries to foster positive employee attitudes and improve overall job satisfaction.

5.4. Work-life conflict and wellbeing

The study further examined how work-life conflict (WLC) levels varied according to employees’ wellbeing status. Statistical analysis using Welch’s ANOVA, which was

appropriate due to the violation of the homogeneity of variances assumption, revealed significant differences for two WLC items: “*The demands of my work interfere with my family activities*” (Welch’s $F(1, 326.68) = 28.63, p < .001$) and “*I prioritise my job over my personal life*” (Welch’s $F(1, 318.42) = 40.41, p < .001$). In plain terms, these results mean that employees with lower wellbeing reported significantly higher levels of work interfering with family life and a greater tendency to prioritise their jobs over their personal lives compared to employees with higher wellbeing.

In addition, standard one-way ANOVA tests, where homogeneity of variance was not violated, showed significant differences for the items “*I prioritise my family over my work*” ($F(1, 333) = 25.85, p < .001$) and “*My home life interferes with work-related demands*” ($F(1, 333) = 23.07, p < .001$). Employees with lower wellbeing scores were more likely to report that family responsibilities disrupted their work performance or that their personal life took precedence over work obligations. Overall, across multiple dimensions of WLC, wellbeing status emerged as a significant factor influencing how employees experience work-life conflict.

These findings are strongly aligned with existing literature. Previous studies (e.g., Grzywacz and Marks, 2000; Haar and Brougham, 2011) have consistently found that poor mental and physical wellbeing is associated with higher perceived work-life conflict. The resource drain model proposed by Hobfoll (1989) also supports these results: when employees have fewer psychological resources due to stress or ill-health, they are less capable of managing competing demands from work and personal life. Furthermore, research by Allen et al. (2021) emphasised that employees experiencing high stress are particularly vulnerable to both directions of conflict – work interfering with life and life interfering with work.

One possible explanation for the strong link between wellbeing and WLC found in this study is the bidirectional nature of stress and boundary violation. Poor wellbeing may both result from and exacerbate work-life conflict. Employees experiencing stress-related conditions may find it more difficult to disengage from work, leading to further deterioration in personal life quality and reinforcing a negative cycle. Moreover, during periods of organisational change or instability (such as post-pandemic adjustments), employees’ wellbeing can be more fragile, making them more susceptible to work-life spillover effects.

Thus, the current findings not only support but extend existing literature by confirming that wellbeing status is a major determinant of how employees manage and experience work-life boundaries. The results highlight the importance of organisational initiatives that promote employee wellbeing such as stress management programs, flexible working options, and mental health support as effective strategies for reducing work-life conflict and its negative consequences.

5.5. Work-life enrichment and job attitudes

This study also examined the relationship between work-life enrichment (WLE) and employees' job attitudes (JA), specifically their satisfaction with workplace flexibility. Pearson's correlation analysis showed significant positive relationships between work-life enrichment factors and job attitudes. The ability to set boundaries between work and personal life (e7.5) demonstrated a moderate positive correlation with job attitudes ($r = .402, p < .001$), meaning that employees who reported greater control over work-life boundaries tended to be more satisfied with the flexibility offered by their organisations. In contrast, the ability to find time for hobbies and interests (e7.6) showed a weaker but still significant positive correlation ($r = .245, p < .001$), suggesting that personal leisure time also contributes to workplace satisfaction, albeit to a lesser extent.

Statistical analysis through one-way ANOVA further confirmed that employees' wellbeing status significantly influenced their experiences of work-life enrichment. For the ability to set work-life boundaries, the ANOVA result was highly significant ($F(1, 333) = 24.215, p < .001$), while for finding time for personal interests, the difference was also statistically significant, though smaller ($F(1, 333) = 4.516, p = .034$). In simple terms, employees with better wellbeing reported a greater ability to establish clear boundaries and to allocate time for personal hobbies, both of which were associated with improved satisfaction at work.

These findings are consistent with previous studies that emphasise the positive role of work-life enrichment in enhancing job satisfaction and employee wellbeing. Greenhaus and Powell's (2006) theory of work-family enrichment proposed that gains in one domain (e.g., personal life) can enhance the quality of experiences in another domain (e.g., work). Similarly, research by McNall et al. (2021) found that employees who experienced greater work-life enrichment reported higher levels of job satisfaction and organisational commitment.

One potential explanation for the stronger impact of boundary setting compared to leisure activities is that boundary management directly affects employees' ability to control interruptions between work and personal life, thereby preserving their sense of autonomy and reducing role overload. In contrast, while having time for hobbies is valuable, it may be more vulnerable to external factors such as workload fluctuations or family demands, making its influence on job satisfaction less direct.

Thus, the present study supports and extends existing literature by reinforcing the idea that effective work-life boundary management is a critical component of positive job attitudes. The findings suggest that organisational efforts to support employees in setting boundaries –

through policies such as flexible working hours, no-email-after-hours norms, and workload management – may be particularly effective strategies for enhancing employee satisfaction and wellbeing.

5.6. Employee recommendations for better work-life balance

The final part of the study explored employees' direct recommendations for improving work-life balance (WLB) within organisations. Descriptive statistics from multi-response analysis revealed that the three most frequently endorsed recommendations were “*restricted overtime agreements*” (52.2% of cases), “*restricted working hours*” (50.4% of cases), and “*more generous holiday allowance*” (49.3% of cases). In simpler terms, employees primarily emphasised the need for more control over their working time and greater access to rest periods to improve their ability to balance professional and personal responsibilities.

Additional recommendations, including “*organising more stress-relieving social events/activities*” (42.7%) and “*reducing the number of stressful tasks given*” (35.3%), highlighted employees' desire for workplaces to acknowledge the role of psychological wellbeing in achieving work-life balance. Meanwhile, relatively fewer respondents prioritised recommendations such as “*providing flexible working hours*” (26.1%) and “*monitoring work-related stress*” (24.3%), suggesting that while flexibility remains valued, structural changes to working time limits are perceived as more urgent interventions.

These findings are strongly supported by previous research. For instance, Allen, Johnson, Kiburz, and Shockley (2013) emphasised that limiting overtime and enhancing rest periods are among the most effective ways to reduce work-life conflict and employee burnout. Moreover, Beauregard and Henry (2009) argued that offering extended vacation time and promoting the right to disconnect outside work hours can significantly improve employees' perceived work-life balance and overall job satisfaction.

Interestingly, while flexible working hours have been widely promoted in recent years (e.g., Hill et al., 2008), the relatively lower priority given to this option in the present study suggests a possible shift: employees may now view the protection of total personal time – rather than simply flexibility – as more critical. One possible reason for this could be the expansion of remote work during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, which has blurred traditional work-home boundaries. As a result, employees may seek stricter protections for non-working time, rather than simply more autonomy over when they work.

Thus, the findings from employee recommendations align closely with contemporary research stressing the critical importance of time control, mandatory rest, and organisational

efforts to manage workplace stress. Organisations aiming to support better work-life balance should consider adopting not only flexible schedules but also explicit limits on overtime and clear protections for employees' personal time.

5.7. Summary of hypotheses testing

This section summarises the acceptance or rejection of the research hypotheses based on the statistical results presented and discussed earlier. Hypotheses were evaluated using Pearson correlations, ANOVA tests, and descriptive analysis, depending on the specific relationships examined.

Table 5.1. Summary of hypotheses testing

Hypothesis	Result	Conclusion
H1: There is a significant correlation between employees' overall work-life balance and their working sector.	$p > .05$	Not Supported
H2: There is a significant correlation between employees' overall work-life balance and their employment status.	$p > .05$	Not Supported
H3: Work-life balance varies significantly across different age groups.	$p > .05$	Not Supported
H4: Work-life balance varies significantly based on parental status.	$p > .05$	Not Supported
H5: There is a significant correlation between life interference with work and employees' job attitudes.	$p < .05$	Supported
H6: There is a significant correlation between employees' ability to set work-life boundaries and their job attitudes.	$p < .05$	Supported
H7: Taking extended holidays contributes to improved work-life balance.	Descriptive analysis supports	Supported
H8: Participating in stress-relieving social events and activities improves employees' work-life balance.	Descriptive analysis supports	Supported

As shown in Table 5.1, four of the eight hypotheses were supported by the statistical findings, while the other four were not. Specifically, demographic factors such as working sector, employment status, age, and parental status were found to have no significant influence on employees' overall work-life balance. This partially contradicts earlier studies, such as those by Clarke et al. (2004) and Kossek and Ozeki (1998), who argued that life stage and employment context are major contributors to work-life imbalance. One potential reason for this divergence is the shifting nature of modern work environments. As discussed in the literature, post-pandemic flexibility, increased remote work options, and evolving employee expectations (Twenge, 2010) may have reduced the impact of traditional demographic factors on work-life dynamics.

In contrast, strong support was found for the hypotheses concerning the relationship between work-life conflict and job attitudes, as well as between work-life enrichment and job

satisfaction. These findings are in line with Netemeyer et al. (1996) and Allen et al. (2021), who found that higher work-life conflict significantly lowers employee satisfaction and organisational commitment, while positive enrichment experiences enhance job engagement and morale. The significant correlation found between employees' ability to set work-life boundaries and their job attitudes also reinforces the importance of boundary theory (Ashforth et al., 2000), suggesting that control over work-life separation is essential to employee wellbeing.

Furthermore, employee recommendations gathered in the study – particularly those supporting extended holidays and stress-relieving social events – were consistent with the recovery theory presented by Sonnentag and Fritz (2007), which emphasises the restorative power of leisure and rest in maintaining work-life balance. These responses also echoed key points from the literature on employee wellbeing, such as the work of Greenhaus and Powell (2006), who argued that positive experiences outside work can spill over and improve work outcomes.

Overall, these findings contribute to the growing body of research suggesting that structural factors such as job demands, recovery time, and the ability to set boundaries are now more influential on employees' experience of work-life balance than static demographic characteristics. This shift highlights the need for modern organisations to prioritise wellbeing, flexibility, and autonomy in their people strategies, rather than relying solely on one-size-fits-all approaches based on age, family status, or contract type.

CHAPTER 6

IMPLICATIONS TO THEORY AND PRACTICE, AND BUSINESS/MANAGEMENT

6.1. Introduction

This section outlines the broader implications of the research findings for academic theory, professional practice, and organisational management. By examining how work-life balance relates to employee wellbeing, job attitudes, and recommended workplace strategies, the study provides valuable insights that extend beyond the immediate research objectives. The following discussion highlights how the results contribute to existing theoretical frameworks and offers practical guidance for businesses and HR professionals aiming to improve employee experience and performance.

6.2. Implications to theory

This study contributes to a range of theoretical frameworks related to work-life balance (WLB), with findings that both support and expand current literature. It specifically addresses the central research question: *How does work-life balance affect employee performance and wellbeing across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments?* The findings directly address the four research objectives and engage with five key WLB theories: discrepancy theory, compensation theory, enrichment theory, boundary theory, and role conflict theory. These contributions not only support existing literature but also offer refinements and potential areas for theoretical development.

The study draws on five foundational WLB theories: discrepancy theory, compensation theory, enrichment theory, boundary theory, and role conflict theory.

In relation to Objective 1 “*To evaluate the significance of work-life balance in influencing employee performance and wellbeing,*” which aimed to evaluate the significance of work-life balance in influencing employee performance and wellbeing, the findings provide clear support for discrepancy theory (Wilcock & Wright, 1991). This theory suggests that job satisfaction and performance are influenced by the gap between an employee’s expectations and their perceived reality. In this study, employees who reported greater satisfaction with their work-life balance – including flexibility, boundary control, and personal time – also reported stronger job attitudes. This indicates that when WLB provisions align with employees’ value perceptions, they are more likely to be engaged and perform effectively. The results suggest that workplace WLB policies, when aligned with employee values, significantly enhance both

satisfaction and performance, thereby validating the theory in the context of UK employment. This empirical link validates discrepancy theory within modern HR contexts and suggests that alignment between policy and perception is central to employee motivation.

Compensation theory (Matias & Recharte, 2021) argues that employees may offset dissatisfaction in one life domain by drawing satisfaction from another. This theory was partially confirmed in the study. For example, participants experiencing job strain often cited family or social activities as vital coping mechanisms. These findings, aligned with Objective 3, *“To analyse the impact of varying levels of work-life conflict and enrichment on employees’ attitudes and wellbeing,”* suggest that employees rely on non-work domains for emotional compensation, reinforcing the theoretical interdependence of work and home life. In parallel, enrichment theory (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006; Wu et al., 2021) was also supported. The study found that experiences in work and non-work domains can enhance each other, rather than merely compete. Employees who were able to set boundaries, engage in hobbies, and recover from stress reported more positive job attitudes and a stronger sense of wellbeing. These findings illustrate that positive spillover between domains is a meaningful pathway to achieving work-life balance. Notably, some participants reported coexisting conflict and enrichment, suggesting that these two constructs are not mutually exclusive. Under certain conditions, such as resilience or access to strong support systems, work-life conflict may not only coexist with enrichment but potentially catalyse it. This presents a more complex and nuanced understanding of work-life dynamics, indicating that both theories are relevant, and their interplay warrants further theoretical exploration. For Objective 3, the findings therefore support both compensation and enrichment theories, while also pointing to the importance of recognising the dynamic, overlapping nature of conflict and growth in work-life experiences.

However, a novel insight emerged: conflict and enrichment may not be mutually exclusive, as previously suggested by Frone (2003) and Grzywacz & Carlson (2007). In this study, some employees reported high levels of work-life conflict while also experiencing strong enrichment. This suggests that under certain conditions conflict may be transformed into personal growth or motivation such as strong personal resilience or supportive workplace structures. This finding contributes to ongoing discussions around the dynamic nature of WLB and calls for more integrative theoretical models that allow for overlapping experiences.

Linked to Objective 2 *“To examine how work-life balance, including work-family conflict and enrichment, varies across different age groups and parental statuses,”* the findings partially support boundary theory (Ashforth et al., 2000), which suggests that managing psychological, spatial, and temporal boundaries is critical to WLB. However, consistent with Submitter et al. (2020) and Allen et al. (2021), many participants reported blurred boundaries

due to remote work and digital access. These findings challenge the traditional segmentation-integration binary and suggest that WLB theory should adopt a more flexible, personalised view of boundary management in hybrid and technologically mediated workplaces. This reflects a shift in how boundaries are constructed and maintained, suggesting the theory needs to evolve to include the modern realities of work-life integration. Employees no longer fit neatly into “segmenters” or “integrators”; rather, they adapt their boundary strategies to suit dynamic work conditions. This insight challenges the rigidity of traditional boundary models and supports more fluid conceptualisations.

The study reinforces role conflict theory (Ilies et al., 2018), which posits that conflicting demands from work and life domains lead to stress and reduced wellbeing. Participants experiencing frequent interference reported emotional strain and lower job satisfaction. However, the negative impact of conflict was moderated by access to flexibility, autonomy, and recovery time. These results suggest that future theoretical models should integrate organisational resources as moderating variables, reflecting that the effects of role conflict are not fixed but context-dependent.

This study also engages critically with the role of demographic and personal factors in WLB outcomes. While past literature has emphasised gender, age, and parental status (Gómez-Ortiz et al., 2022; Yadav et al., 2022), this study found no significant differences by age or parental status. This challenges traditional demographic determinism and suggests that in contemporary UK work environments, structural and psychological factors may be more influential than life-stage roles.

In contrast, the study confirms the growing importance of employee attitudes, job autonomy, and workplace culture in shaping WLB experiences (Chen et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2015). These findings support a shift toward individual agency and organisational design as central to WLB theory.

Findings related to gender were mixed. While prior research highlights disparities, the study aligns with De Clercq and Brieger (2022), who argue that gender roles in WLB are increasingly shared. Similarly, participants with marital or parental responsibilities were often able to maintain satisfactory WLB, contradicting earlier claims by Perry & Hammer (2017) that such roles inherently lead to conflict. These results highlight the importance of interactional variables like organisational support, role clarity, and flexibility.

Although personality traits were not directly measured, the study raises the relevance of personal attitudes and emotional responses (Mohr et al., 2021). The role of positive and negative affect in managing WLB suggests future theoretical models should integrate psychological variables alongside demographic and structural ones.

This research supports an integrated, multidimensional model of work-life balance that accounts for the interaction of individual, organisational, and psychological elements. Extending earlier conceptual frameworks (Wilcox, 2020; Rodríguez-Sánchez et al., 2020), the findings confirm that WLB is shaped by a dynamic interplay of several key variables operating at multiple levels. These insights are particularly relevant to Objective 3, which aimed to analyse the impact of varying levels of work-life conflict and enrichment on employees' attitudes and wellbeing, and Objective 4, which sought to recommend strategies for improving work-life balance tailored to employees' life stages and family responsibilities.

Work-related variables, including job autonomy, performance expectations, digital demands, and scheduling flexibility, were shown to have a significant influence on employees' ability to achieve balance. Participants who reported greater control over their work schedules, clearer role expectations, and manageable workloads also reported higher levels of job satisfaction and wellbeing. Conversely, excessive digital connectivity and unrealistic performance pressures were frequently cited as barriers to WLB, highlighting the need for organisational policies that promote sustainable work practices. These findings reinforce the importance of job design in supporting WLB and demonstrate that empowering employees through flexibility and realistic expectations can enhance both wellbeing and performance, directly addressing the concerns outlined in Objective 3.

Personal factors, such as psychological wellbeing, life stage, and individual job attitudes, played a significant role in shaping WLB experiences. The findings indicate that internal resources such as emotional resilience, motivation, and cognitive framing substantially influenced how employees perceived and responded to work-life demands. Notably, the data revealed that WLB did not differ significantly across life stages or parental statuses, suggesting that demographic attributes alone are not reliable predictors of WLB outcomes. This insight is critical for Objective 4 - *“To recommend strategies for improving work-life balance, tailored to employees' life stages and family responsibilities”* - as it demonstrates that effective WLB approaches should be grounded in psychological and structural support rather than age or family status alone. Furthermore, individuals with positive job attitudes reported lower levels of conflict and greater enrichment, reinforcing the connection between WLB and employee wellbeing highlighted in Objective 3.

Support systems – both formal and informal – emerged as essential enablers of WLB. Organisational resources such as recovery time, flexible leave, mental health initiatives, and empathetic managerial support were frequently cited as helping employees manage the pressures of work. The effectiveness of these supports was significantly enhanced by positive leadership and a culture of trust, illustrating the critical role of organisational climate in

sustaining wellbeing and balance. These findings underscore Objective 3, revealing that structural supports not only alleviate stress but also enhance job satisfaction and engagement.

Additionally, the study affirms that wellbeing is both a determinant and an outcome of effective WLB. Employees with higher levels of psychological wellbeing were better equipped to manage boundaries and recover from stress, while supportive work settings further enhanced overall wellbeing. This reciprocal relationship aligns with theories of psychological and subjective wellbeing (Diener et al., 2018; Rook et al., 2020), and reinforces WLB as a strategic concern in human resource management rather than a mere individual goal.

Education level also emerged as a significant contributor to WLB (Kossek & Distelberg, 2016; Barber et al., 2019). Higher education was linked to greater self-efficacy, which in turn supported employees' ability to manage work-life demands. Conversely, life demands received limited attention in this study. As Sonnentag and Fritz (2015) noted, the breadth of life demands is extensive – over 170 were identified – making it impractical for this study to analyse them comprehensively. Consequently, this variable represents a limitation and an area for future exploration.

The findings further validate prior research on the impact of task-related variables on WLB. These include job characteristics, work demands, autonomy, technological influences, motivation, organisational culture, and role conflict. Specifically, the study reinforces that job autonomy, schedule flexibility, manageable work hours, social support from colleagues and supervisors, and access to family-friendly policies are all pivotal to achieving WLB – echoing the conclusions of Zheng et al. (2015). Similarly, increased work hours and pressure had a detrimental impact on WLB, in line with Kulik et al. (2016). Autonomy was shown to facilitate WLB by giving employees more control over their working conditions (Perry & Hammer, 2017). Technological advancements were found to contribute both to work intensification and to greater flexibility (Holden & Sunindijo, 2018), reflecting a dual impact.

Work motivation was identified as a determinant of employees' willingness to engage with their roles (Emre & De Spiegeleare, 2021), and a strong organisational culture – defined by shared values and norms – was shown to contribute to high performance standards (Ismail et al., 2018). The findings also supported the notion that increased motivation aligns with improved job performance. However, constraints and competition within the workplace posed challenges to WLB. Internal and external work constraints (Singh et al., 2018; Barber et al., 2019) can hinder employees' ability to balance demands, while workplace competition – although occasionally motivating – can result in negative outcomes (Westrupp et al., 2016; Caesens et al., 2017).

Role conflict stood out as one of the most prevalent challenges to WLB. When employees were faced with competing responsibilities, stress and reduced wellbeing frequently followed (Ilies et al., 2018; Caesens et al., 2020). This study supports and extends previous work by offering further insight into how role conflict interacts with other personal and organisational factors in influencing WLB.

In seeking to unify these varied factors, the study integrates both personal and work-related variables into a broader conceptual framework of WLB. These findings clarify the mechanisms underlying the proposed framework and provide empirical evidence for how WLB contributes to employee performance. Several mediating factors – including work-life policies, job involvement, role conflict, job stress, ambiguity, flexibility, social support, resource access, and wellbeing – are instrumental in explaining these relationships.

Work-life policies, as a form of structural organisational support, are key in this regard. As Wilcox (2020) suggests, such policies represent an employer's commitment to supporting employees' lives beyond work. Similarly, Rodríguez-Sánchez et al. (2020) emphasise that HR departments can translate organisational culture into meaningful support by enabling flexible work patterns, enhancing employee control, and facilitating access to necessary resources. The findings of this study further substantiate the effectiveness of flexible policies in promoting performance and balance.

A wide range of indicators were employed to interpret these results, including job involvement (Chen, 2019), role conflict (Molina, 2021; Adiguzel & Kucukoglu, 2019), stress (Esguerra, 2020; Ahmad et al., 2021), ambiguity (Charoensukmongkol & Puyod, 2021), flexibility (Inegbedion et al., 2020), social support (Boxall & Macky, 2016; Oludayo & Omonijo, 2020), and access to resources (Amiruddin, 2019). These elements provide a holistic picture of the interrelated factors that shape WLB outcomes.

Ultimately, the contribution of this study is grounded in its emphasis on wellbeing as central to human resource management and WLB. To optimise WLB, indicators such as subjective and psychological wellbeing must be integrated into organisational practice. The current findings demonstrate that wellbeing – measured through physical health, job and family satisfaction, and psychological stability – is closely linked to performance outcomes.

In summary, this study advances understanding of WLB by elucidating how internal and external factors interact to shape employee experiences. Rather than viewing WLB solely as a function of job satisfaction, the study positions it as a multi-dimensional construct influenced by job design, organisational support, and psychological resources. It contributes to the broader literature by offering a cohesive framework for conceptualising WLB as a performance-related outcome with implications for HR theory and practice.

The findings reinforce the central theoretical foundations of WLB, particularly discrepancy, compensation, enrichment, boundary, and role conflict theories. However, this study also introduces several critical refinements:

- Conflict and enrichment can coexist and are not always opposing experiences;
- Boundaries are dynamic and context-dependent;
- Demographic factors are less predictive of WLB outcomes than previously thought;
- Autonomy, wellbeing, and employee agency are becoming core elements in modern WLB frameworks.

These insights support a shift towards more person-centred, adaptive models of WLB that reflect the flexible and digitally mediated nature of today's work environments. This theoretical grounding informs the practical recommendations to follow.

6.3. Implications to practice and business/management

The findings of this study offer a comprehensive range of practical implications for businesses, particularly within the fields of human resource management, organisational leadership, and workplace policy design. As work-life balance (WLB) increasingly becomes a central issue in contemporary employment contexts - driven by technological change, evolving employee expectations, and hybrid working models – organisations must move beyond viewing WLB as a peripheral concern. Rather, it should be recognised as a strategic asset that directly influences employee wellbeing, performance, motivation, and engagement. In this regard, WLB becomes essential to sustainable and effective business management.

One of the most important implications is the need to move away from traditional, demographic-driven WLB policies. The study found no significant variation in WLB outcomes based on age or parental status, challenging assumptions that particular demographic groups inherently require different forms of support. Instead, the findings support a person-centred approach that considers employees' psychological needs, emotional resilience, and job attitudes. HR professionals and managers should prioritise individualised support mechanisms such as mental health provision, flexible working arrangements, and autonomy in task and time management to accommodate diverse employee circumstances.

The role of autonomy was especially prominent in promoting WLB. Employees who had greater control over their working hours, locations, and methods demonstrated improved wellbeing and engagement. As such, organisations must invest in job design strategies that provide employees with meaningful control over their work. Mechanisms for flexible schedules, remote work, hybrid models, and participatory decision-making are not only

desirable but necessary for fostering a motivated and resilient workforce. These adjustments should be supported by managerial trust and reduced micromanagement, thus enabling employees to create work patterns that align with both organisational goals and personal wellbeing.

However, structural flexibility alone is insufficient without a supportive organisational culture. The presence of formal WLB policies must be complemented by an inclusive and empathetic workplace climate, led by managers who embody and model healthy boundaries and wellbeing practices. Organisations should invest in leadership development programmes that promote emotional intelligence, active listening, and positive reinforcement. A culture where open dialogue, self-care, and mutual respect are normalised can enhance the effectiveness of formal policies and reduce stigma around seeking support.

Moreover, wellbeing was shown to be both a cause and a result of WLB. The study emphasises that psychological and emotional wellbeing – when actively supported – leads to better boundary management, greater job satisfaction, and lower turnover. Businesses must therefore embed wellbeing into everyday operations, not as isolated initiatives but as ongoing, systemic practices. These may include mental health days, access to counselling services, wellbeing check-ins, and holistic benefits packages. Creating a feedback loop where wellbeing drives performance – and vice versa – requires continuous attention and resource investment.

The digitisation of the workplace also presents both opportunities and risks. While technology can enhance flexibility and access, it may also blur the lines between professional and personal life. Businesses must address this through clear digital wellbeing policies that set boundaries around working hours, email responsiveness, and virtual meeting expectations. Introducing “quiet hours,” meeting-free days, and respectful digital communication guidelines are crucial to managing digital overload, especially in hybrid environments.

Role clarity and realistic performance expectations emerged as additional focal points. Employees are more likely to experience stress and conflict when they face ambiguous responsibilities or overwhelming workloads. Employers must therefore ensure job descriptions are transparent, duties are fairly distributed, and expectations are manageable. Regular performance reviews, feedback sessions, and open discussions can help realign workload imbalances and clarify goals, thus preventing burnout and reinforcing WLB.

The findings also highlight the impact of intrinsic motivation and job attitudes on WLB. Employees who feel engaged and purposeful are more likely to experience enrichment across work and life domains. To foster this, employers should provide meaningful work, opportunities for skill development, and recognition of effort. Clear career pathways, purpose-

aligned initiatives, and transparent reward systems can significantly enhance motivation and reduce disengagement.

Importantly, the study also suggests that WLB can act as a predictor of performance. Therefore, understanding the factors that cause imbalance can help inform targeted strategies to boost output and efficiency. In this context, work-life balance becomes an actionable metric in performance planning and evaluation. It also intersects with other domains of human resource management, including recruitment, training, and the strategic use of technology.

For example, making effective WLB policies requires reflection on both work-related and life-related challenges. Employers must conduct internal assessments and engage in employee consultations to ensure that policies are broadly applicable, inclusive, and reflective of actual staff needs. These policies should address role ambiguity, job equality, clear promotion and reward systems, and access to adequate supervision and social support. Including WLB in Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) can also incentivise a healthier workplace culture and guide long-term strategic decisions.

Social support, especially from supervisors and more experienced colleagues, was another key factor identified in the research. Structured mentoring, coaching, and access to informal peer networks are all critical components of a supportive work environment. Employees who feel guided and understood are better equipped to fulfil their roles and maintain balance.

Life-related challenges should also be explicitly addressed in policy. Differences in wellbeing across life stages should prompt employers to assign responsibilities mindfully, with sensitivity to individual capacity. Health and wellbeing campaigns, family-friendly benefits, social events, and proactive mental health interventions all contribute to an enriched work-life experience. These initiatives also strengthen workplace relationships and reinforce organisational identity and cohesion.

Salary, wage, and commission structures must also reflect the varied life demands employees face. While it is not possible to tailor remuneration packages to every individual, transparency and fairness in compensation policies can alleviate stress and support broader wellbeing goals. Similarly, educational level was identified as a variable affecting WLB, with higher levels associated with greater self-efficacy. Accordingly, organisations should invest in continuous training, skill development, and career mobility both to retain high-performing staff and to prepare employees for more demanding roles.

The findings also extend to recruitment. Employers should incorporate WLB considerations into job advertisements, interviews, and selection processes. Clear role descriptions and realistic performance expectations reduce the risk of future dissatisfaction and

conflict. In recruitment, personal factors such as marital status, parental responsibilities, and life demands must be considered not as grounds for exclusion but as relevant factors for shaping support and ensuring fit.

Lastly, technological innovation offers valuable potential for work flexibility. However, employers must determine the appropriate level of autonomy based on the business model and job functions. With careful implementation, technology can support remote working, flexible hours, and even decentralised decision-making – provided there are systems in place for monitoring progress and ensuring accountability.

In conclusion, the implications of this study go far beyond human resources departments. They extend to the strategic and operational foundations of business performance. By adopting a multidimensional and inclusive approach to WLB – integrating flexibility, wellbeing, support, clarity, and purpose – organisations can simultaneously improve employee experience and drive performance outcomes. The insights presented here form a robust theoretical and practical framework for reshaping workplace practices in alignment with the realities of today’s dynamic and technology-mediated employment environment.

6.4. Specific Applications to Theory

Building on the broader theoretical implications outlined in section 5.1, this part of the study offers a more detailed discussion of how the findings contribute to the existing frameworks of work-life balance (WLB). Organised around the study’s four research objectives, this section explores the nuanced relationships between socio-cultural contexts, life stage factors, work-life conflicts and enrichment, job attitudes, and wellbeing. It highlights how the present results not only reinforce established theories but also introduce new variables, refine key constructs, and propose areas for future theoretical development within the field of human resource management and organisational psychology.

In particular, following data analysis, the results of the current study make several contributions to the theoretical framework of WLB. These contributions are organised according to the study’s four research objectives, relating to: (1) the significance of WLB in workplaces, (2) the influence of life stage factors (parental status and age groups) on WLB, (3) the relationship between work-life conflicts, enrichment, job attitudes, and wellbeing, and (4) recommendations to improve WLB.

The results demonstrated that imbalances between work-related and life-related domains were prevalent across all employee groups. Notably, the hospitality sector exhibited the most significant problems with WLB, and managers were the least successful in maintaining balance. These findings extend those of Gragnano et al. (2020), suggesting that

not only divergence in work roles, but also sector-specific conditions, can exacerbate WLB challenges. The pandemic-related lockdowns particularly impacted the hospitality sector, forcing adaptations such as remote working, which many employees found difficult. These results reinforce the role of socio-cultural contexts as important external influences on WLB. In line with Chen (2019) and Jaharuddin and Zainol (2019), job involvement is reaffirmed as a critical factor affecting WLB. Thus, socio-cultural environments, including economic downturns, pandemics, and national disruptions, must be integrated into WLB theories as influential contextual variables.

Another contribution relates to the theoretical understanding of life stage variables. While earlier studies (e.g., David, 2019; Rodríguez-Sánchez et al., 2020) linked parental status and age directly to WLB outcomes, the current study suggests that the relationship is more complex. Specifically, WLB challenges among working parents were influenced by factors such as the number and dependency of children, workplace flexibility (Emre & De Spiegeleare, 2021), and social support (Oludayo & Omonijo, 2020).

Interestingly, successful cases of WLB were observed even among parents with multiple children, implying that effective personal strategies, organisational resources, and resilience may be more decisive than parental status alone. Similarly, although employees aged 45–54 tended to report better WLB, inconsistent outcomes within the 60+ group suggest that age alone is an insufficient predictor. These findings advocate for theoretical models that prioritise individual coping strategies and resilience mechanisms over demographic factors.

The study also refines the understanding of how work-life conflict and enrichment impact job attitudes and wellbeing. Echoing Matias and Recharte (2021) and Irawanto et al. (2021), work-life conflicts were found to correlate negatively with job satisfaction. However, the present study extends prior work by classifying conflicts into four types – life interventions in work, work priorities, personal life priorities, and work interventions in life – and highlighting their distinct effects. Life interventions in work exerted the strongest negative impact on job satisfaction.

Similarly, although the relationship between work-life enrichment and job attitudes was positive, it was weaker than the negative impact of conflict. Two specific forms of enrichment – boundary setting and personal time management – were particularly influential. These results suggest that WLB theories should treat enrichment and conflict as distinct but interrelated dimensions, each with different impacts on job attitudes.

Regarding wellbeing, the study reaffirms the connection between work-life conflict and poorer psychological health, consistent with Goodman et al. (2018) and Cusinato et al. (2020).

Importantly, it focuses specifically on psychological stress rather than broader organisational stressors, emphasising mental wellbeing as a priority in managing work-life conflicts.

Work-life enrichment was similarly linked to better psychological wellbeing. Employees who successfully managed boundaries and maintained personal interests reported higher levels of satisfaction and resilience, echoing the findings of Hutagalung et al. (2020) on the positive effects of emotional regulation. Social support from supervisors and colleagues was identified as a crucial mechanism fostering enrichment and, in turn, wellbeing.

Finally, the practical recommendations gathered from employees offer important theoretical contributions to HRM and organisational development frameworks. Employees' preferences for remote working, more generous leave policies, and restrictions on overtime highlight the critical role of flexible work policies in promoting WLB. These results support Kossek and Distelberg (2016) and Emre and De Spiegeleare (2021), suggesting that HR practices must evolve to support organisational subcultures and micro-environments, rather than relying solely on centralised policies.

In particular, the findings suggest that promoting subcultural support – tailoring interventions to specific departments or employee groups – is vital in fostering WLB. Theories of HRM should therefore incorporate the management of subcultures as a necessary strategy for sustainable work-life integration.

In conclusion, the present study makes several theoretical contributions to the field of work-life balance:

- It emphasises the mediating role of socio-cultural contexts in influencing WLB outcomes.
- It challenges traditional demographic predictors (e.g., age, parental status), advocating a greater focus on resilience and coping strategies.
- It disaggregates work-life conflict and enrichment into distinct types, revealing their different impacts on job attitudes and wellbeing.
- It introduces work resilience and strategic adaptation as critical theoretical variables.
- It highlights the need for HR policies that support decentralised, subcultural management of WLB challenges.

These contributions offer a more dynamic and context-sensitive understanding of work-life balance, setting the stage for future empirical studies and theoretical refinements.

6.5. Specific applications into the human resources management

While the previous section outlined the broader strategic implications of work-life balance (WLB) for business operations and organisational leadership, it is equally important to translate these insights into concrete actions within the domain of human resource management. HR departments serve as the operational bridge between policy and practice, and they play a critical role in embedding WLB principles across recruitment, employee support, training, and policy implementation. This section therefore builds on the strategic recommendations of Section 5.2 by detailing specific, actionable applications of the study's findings for HR professionals. These include improvements to workplace policies, leadership behaviours, support systems, and tools for assessing and managing WLB on a practical level.

The present study reinforces the notion that work-life balance (WLB) can positively influence employee performance, highlighting its growing importance in the context of human resource management (HRM). Based on the data analysis, the findings offer multiple real-world applications that HR professionals and business leaders can adopt to improve employee wellbeing and organisational outcomes.

Firstly, the statistical evidence indicates that WLB is a common concern not only among junior staff but also senior employees, including managerial and executive roles. This suggests that imbalances in work and personal life are not confined to one demographic group or employment level. Full-time and part-time workers alike reported challenges, emphasising the need for HR managers to understand employees' diverse backgrounds and contextual realities. A key recommendation is to prioritise training and awareness programmes on work-life balance. These sessions provide employees with strategies to manage stress, reflect on their routines, and implement practical solutions. In times of increased global uncertainty and workplace pressures – such as during and after the COVID-19 pandemic – these strategies become vital for sustaining productivity and morale.

The findings also reveal that life-stage variables such as age and parental status are not reliable predictors of WLB success. Therefore, HR managers should avoid stereotyping employees based on family circumstances or age. An inclusive approach that values flexibility and individual capability over assumptions about personal life is essential in recruitment and promotion. Instead of treating age, marital status, or parenthood as performance indicators, HR professionals should focus on competencies such as adaptability, communication, and experience.

Another important implication concerns work-life conflict and enrichment. The study found that these dimensions significantly affect job satisfaction and wellbeing. Accordingly, HR leaders are encouraged to revise work policies with a stronger emphasis on flexible scheduling, manageable workloads, and supportive work environments. These adjustments

may include options for remote or hybrid working, generous leave allowances, and clearer overtime protocols. Furthermore, employee recognition initiatives can help reduce burnout and strengthen work engagement such as bonuses, social events, or company-sponsored trips

Organisational culture and subculture also emerged as influential factors. A positive workplace culture, reinforced by inclusive values, transparent communication, and mutual respect, can help employees thrive. Town hall meetings, internal forums, and cross-departmental collaborations offer platforms to share concerns, celebrate successes, and reinforce shared values. Likewise, subcultural dynamics within departments should be acknowledged and supported, allowing managers to tailor strategies to smaller employee groups with unique needs or challenges.

Workplace competition should be encouraged in a healthy and constructive manner, avoiding toxic or overly aggressive environments. Effective leadership is key here. Managers should act as role models who promote collaboration, actively listen to employees, and help resolve conflicts. Being an effective leader means balancing operational efficiency with empathy, guiding staff through challenges while fostering a culture of self-care and continuous improvement.

The study also recommends the development of a practical toolkit to evaluate WLB. This may include measurable indicators such as job satisfaction, stress levels, and self-assessed WLB. A standardised instrument can support employees in self-reflection and help HR teams track progress and identify areas needing attention.

Flexibility in work arrangements is another priority. Rather than applying rigid schedules, organisations can use technology to facilitate remote or asynchronous work when feasible. The extent of autonomy granted should align with job requirements and organisational goals. Managers should assess how autonomy influences performance and offer appropriate tools to monitor progress. Mental wellbeing initiatives, such as team-building events and wellness campaigns, should also be promoted. These can improve morale, reduce stress, and enhance employee cohesion.

Finally, the study highlights the need to address structural concerns, particularly at the executive level, where WLB challenges were most pronounced. Managers should assess whether work tasks are equitably distributed and clearly defined. Eliminating role ambiguity and ensuring fairness in workload can help employees focus on their responsibilities and feel more valued. Supervisory support, especially for new or inexperienced staff, should be institutionalised to foster development and reduce early-career burnout.

In summary, the current research offers several key takeaways for HR practice:

- Avoid stereotyping employees based on personal characteristics.
- Deliver training programmes to improve WLB awareness and skills.
- Create tools to measure WLB and job performance consistently.
- Foster organisational culture and subculture through collaboration and support.
- Revise work policies to reflect flexibility, fairness, and wellbeing.

By integrating these recommendations, organisations can better support their workforce, increase satisfaction and engagement, and ultimately drive sustainable business performance.

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

7.1. Conclusion

This study set out to investigate the complex relationship between work-life balance (WLB), employee performance, and wellbeing using a structured quantitative methodology rooted in positivist principles. Guided by four clearly defined research objectives, the study collected responses from a diverse cross-section of 337 employees across multiple sectors and demographic backgrounds. Statistical analysis of the responses, including Pearson's correlation and ANOVA, revealed significant insights into how work-life balance influences employee experiences, attitudes, and effectiveness. This chapter summarises and reflects on the findings, drawing clear connections to the research objectives and theoretical frameworks underpinning the study.

7.1.1. Research objectives

Objective 1: To evaluate the significance of work-life balance in influencing employee performance and wellbeing.

The results of this study strongly affirmed that WLB is a central driver of both employee performance and psychological wellbeing. Employees who perceived greater balance between their professional and personal lives reported higher job involvement, increased motivation, and reduced stress. The alignment between workplace provisions (such as flexibility and workload clarity) and employee expectations was shown to be vital. These results reinforce discrepancy theory, which posits that job satisfaction is maximised when there is congruence between what employees expect and what they experience. In practical terms, this suggests that employers who actively support WLB through structural policies are more likely to see enhanced performance and lower absenteeism.

Objective 2: To examine how work-life balance varies across different age groups and parental statuses.

Contrary to widespread assumptions, the findings indicated that WLB outcomes did not differ significantly based on age or parental status. ANOVA tests showed minimal variation across demographic categories, suggesting that structural and psychological variables such as job autonomy, access to resources, and organisational support are more predictive of WLB

outcomes than life-stage factors. This challenges traditional demographic-focused HR practices and supports a shift toward a more individualised approach to employee support. The theoretical implication is that models of WLB should give greater weight to adaptive capabilities and organisational context than to static personal characteristics.

Objective 3: To analyse the impact of varying levels of work-life conflict and enrichment on employees' attitudes and wellbeing.

A strong negative correlation was found between work-life conflict and employee wellbeing. Notably, the sub-dimension “life interfering with work” had the most detrimental effect on job satisfaction and psychological health. This confirms role conflict theory while extending it to show that not all conflicts are equally harmful. On the other hand, work-life enrichment was positively associated with job attitudes, particularly when employees could engage in personal interests or set effective boundaries. However, the enrichment effect was found to be moderate, highlighting the importance of managing both conflict and enrichment simultaneously. These findings point toward a dynamic, dual-process understanding of WLB, where both strain and support mechanisms interact to shape employee outcomes.

Objective 4: To recommend strategies for improving work-life balance tailored to employees' life stages and family responsibilities.

Although the data showed little variation across age and parental groups, participant responses indicated a strong preference for accessible, inclusive WLB strategies. Flexibility, remote working, wellbeing initiatives, and clearer job roles were frequently mentioned as essential. This suggests that effective WLB strategies must address structural constraints and psychological needs rather than be based on demographic generalisations. These findings advocate for universal design in HR policies – ensuring all employees, regardless of life stage, have access to the support they need to thrive.

7.2.2. Theoretical Contributions

This study provides meaningful contributions to the theoretical understanding of work-life balance (WLB) by both affirming and extending established models. Drawing on foundational frameworks such as discrepancy theory, boundary theory, enrichment theory, compensation theory, and role conflict theory, the findings offer new perspectives that encourage more adaptive and integrative theoretical approaches.

Firstly, the research validates discrepancy theory by showing that employees' satisfaction and performance are enhanced when workplace provisions align with personal expectations. However, it also highlights the importance of socio-cultural factors such as the

COVID-19 pandemic and economic pressures as external influences on expectations, suggesting that these should be more thoroughly integrated into future models.

Secondly, the study extends boundary theory by revealing the flexible and dynamic nature of boundary management. Employees adapt strategies depending on their work environment and technological exposure, challenging static views of segmentation and integration and promoting a more fluid, individualised interpretation.

Additionally, the findings support the coexistence of work-life conflict and enrichment, demonstrating that under certain conditions, such as strong personal resilience or organisational support, employees can simultaneously experience both. This insight contributes to enrichment and compensation theories by proposing that these states are not mutually exclusive and should be examined in tandem.

Life stage factors like age and parental status were found to be less predictive of WLB than organisational and psychological variables, suggesting that theoretical models should move beyond demographic determinism. The role of personal resilience and adaptive coping mechanisms also emerged as critical, positioning these as potential moderating factors in WLB theory.

Lastly, the study underscores the influence of organisational subcultures, pointing to the need for WLB models to consider team-level dynamics and localised support systems rather than relying solely on organisation-wide culture.

In summary, this research affirms the relevance of traditional WLB theories while advocating for a shift toward more context-sensitive, psychologically informed, and culturally nuanced frameworks.

7.2.3. Limitations

Despite the strengths of this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the use of a non-probability convenience sampling method, although practical given resource constraints, limits the ability to generalise the findings to the wider population. Respondents were self-selected and may have had a pre-existing interest or concern about work-life balance, introducing potential selection bias. Second, the cross-sectional nature of the research restricts the ability to infer causal relationships. While the data reveal strong correlations between WLB and various employee outcomes, longitudinal research would be needed to determine directionality and causality. Third, the study was geographically constrained to the United Kingdom, meaning the findings may not translate seamlessly to other cultural or regulatory contexts where work-life norms and employment laws differ. For example, countries with stronger social welfare systems or different work-hour regulations may yield different WLB

outcomes. Finally, the study did not account for personality traits or coping styles – factors such as optimism, resilience, or emotional intelligence – which could significantly influence how employees experience and respond to work-life challenges. Including such psychological variables in future studies could offer a more comprehensive picture of WLB dynamics.

7.2.4. Summary

In conclusion, this study has provided compelling evidence that work-life balance is a pivotal factor in employee wellbeing, job satisfaction, and performance. By challenging demographic assumptions and highlighting the importance of organisational support, the research offers valuable theoretical contributions and practical implications. Work-life balance should not be viewed as a one-size-fits-all benefit but rather as an essential organisational priority requiring continuous assessment and adaptation. The recommendations outlined in the following section aim to translate these findings into actionable strategies for both workplace practitioners and future researchers.

7.2. Recommendations

7.2.1. Recommendations for Practice

Based on the study's empirical findings, several strategic recommendations can be made for business leaders, HR professionals, and organisational strategists seeking to improve employee work-life balance and, in turn, performance and wellbeing.

Firstly, organisations are encouraged to promote flexible work arrangements that empower employees with greater control over how, when, and where they work. Hybrid work models, flexible hours, and job-sharing opportunities have been shown to reduce work-life conflict and improve perceptions of autonomy. Rather than focusing on physical presence, performance metrics should prioritise outcomes and employee contribution.

Secondly, work-life balance should be embedded into formal performance appraisal systems. Incorporating WLB as part of key performance indicators (KPIs) for both staff and managers can encourage behaviours that foster a balanced work environment. When balance-promoting practices are recognised and rewarded, organisations signal their commitment to sustainability, empathy, and long-term employee retention.

Thirdly, enhancing psychological wellbeing support must become a permanent aspect of HR services. This includes offering access to counselling services, mindfulness or stress management workshops, and routine wellness check-ins. Wellbeing initiatives should be proactive, continuous, and treated as essential, rather than reactive or optional.

Fourthly, organisations should work towards creating clear and attainable job expectations. Ambiguity in job roles and deliverables often leads to stress and disengagement. Managers should ensure that employees have access to clearly defined responsibilities, regular performance feedback, and collaborative goal-setting processes that align personal and organisational objectives.

Fifthly, it is essential to train managers in WLB-sensitive leadership practices. As team leaders and direct influencers of workplace culture, managers play a pivotal role in supporting employee wellbeing. Training should focus on developing empathy, emotional intelligence, and trust-building skills, enabling them to recognise and support the unique needs of their team members.

Sixthly, companies should establish and enforce digital boundaries to combat the risks of digital overload. Policy measures such as email curfews, meeting-free time blocks, and encouragement to disconnect outside of working hours can prevent the blurring of personal and professional domains especially in hybrid or remote work environments.

Seventhly, support should be tailored based on job function rather than general demographic characteristics. The findings revealed that certain roles particularly managerial positions and employees in hospitality were more susceptible to WLB difficulties. As such, interventions should be role-specific, taking into account the unique pressures and demands of each function rather than assuming uniform needs based on age, gender, or parental status.

Finally, organisations should encourage the cultivation of inclusive subcultures within teams and departments. While overall organisational values should guide behaviour, teams should be empowered to develop context-appropriate norms and expectations around WLB. This decentralised approach ensures that flexibility can thrive within structure, catering to the operational needs and social dynamics of each work unit.

7.2.2. Recommendations for Future Research

To further extend the scope of this study and deepen the understanding of work-life balance (WLB), several avenues for future research are proposed. First, researchers are encouraged to conduct longitudinal studies that track employees over extended periods. Such research would enable a better understanding of how WLB strategies influence wellbeing and performance in the long term and whether initial improvements are sustained or decline over time.

Secondly, future research should expand to include international and culturally diverse samples. By comparing findings across countries and cultural settings, scholars can assess the influence of broader societal norms, labour policies, and institutional structures on WLB

experiences. This would enhance the generalisability of results and identify culture-specific factors that either enable or inhibit WLB.

Thirdly, there is a need for in-depth investigation into the role of resilience and coping strategies. Internal psychological resources such as resilience may mediate the effects of work-life conflict and enrichment on wellbeing, yet their function remains underexplored in the current literature. Future studies should examine how these internal traits interact with external workplace supports to influence outcomes.

Fourth, experimental and quasi-experimental designs could be employed to assess the causal impact of WLB interventions. For example, researchers could implement a specific WLB policy within an organisation and measure its effect on employee performance and mental health over time. This would strengthen causal claims and inform evidence-based policymaking.

Fifth, there is value in conducting sector-specific studies, particularly within industries that were underrepresented in this research, such as healthcare, logistics, and education. These sectors may face unique challenges and constraints that affect how WLB is experienced and managed.

Finally, future studies should incorporate technology-focused analyses. As digital platforms, communication tools, and remote collaboration continue to shape modern work environments, it is essential to understand how these technologies influence boundary management, digital overload, and employee burnout. Special attention should be paid to how digital flexibility can both help and hinder work-life integration.

Together, these recommendations underscore the need for a more nuanced, longitudinal, and technologically informed approach to WLB research that reflects the evolving realities of the modern workplace.

Overall, this study confirms that work-life balance is more than an individual pursuit, it is a strategic imperative for sustainable, resilient, and high-performing organisations. As employee expectations evolve and workplace norms shift, particularly in the post-pandemic era, businesses must continuously reassess how they support balance. A commitment to flexibility, mental health, and inclusive leadership is essential not only for employee wellbeing but also for long-term organisational success. By adopting evidence-based policies and fostering a culture of care, organisations can create environments where individuals can thrive in both their professional and personal lives. This research has provided a foundation for that transformation, offering practical insights and theoretical directions for the future of work.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, J., Zahid, S., Wahid, F. F., & Ali, S. (2021). Impact of role conflict and role ambiguity on job satisfaction the mediating effect of job stress and moderating effect of Islamic work ethics. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(4), pp.41-50.
- Akhter, S., Pauyo, T., & Khan, M. (2019). What is the difference between a systematic review and a meta-analysis? *Basic Methods Handbook for Clinical Orthopaedic Research*, pp.331-342.
- Akter, K. (2019). *Impacts of work-life programs on organisational outcomes*. Doctoral dissertation, Queensland University of Technology.
- Al-Alawi, A. I., Al-Saffar, E., AlmohammedSaleh, Z. H., Alotaibi, H., & Al-Alawi, E. I. (2021). A study of the effects of work-family conflict, family-work conflict, and work-life balance on Saudi female teachers' performance in the public education sector with job satisfaction as a moderator. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 22(1), pp.486-503.
- Al-Hanawi, M.K., Alsharqi, O.Z., Almazrou, S.H. & Qattan, A.M.N. (2023). The impact of job stress, role ambiguity, and work-life imbalance on turnover intention during COVID-19: A case study of frontline health workers in Saudi Arabia. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14.
- Alavi, M. & Carlson, P. (1992). A Review of MIS Research and Disciplinary Development. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 8(4), pp.45-62.
- Alharahsheh, H. H., & Pius, A. (2020). A review of key paradigms: Positivism VS interpretivism. *Global Academic Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), pp.39-43.
- Alili, A., & Krstev, D. (2019). Using SPSS for research and data analysis. *Knowledge–International Journal*, 32(3).
- Alili, A. and Krstev, B. (2019) *SPSS for Data Analysis and Management*. Belgrade: University of Belgrade Press.
- Allan, G. (2020). Qualitative research. In *Handbook for research students in the social sciences*, pp.177-189.
- Allen, T. D., Johnson, R. C., Kiburz, K. M., & Shockley, K. M. (2018). Work-family conflict and flexible work arrangements: deconstructing flexibility. *Personnel Psychology*, 66, pp.345–376.
- Allen, T. D., Merlo, K., Lawrence, R. C., Slutsky, J., & Gray, C. E. (2021). Boundary management and work-nonwork balance while working from home. *Applied Psychology*, 70(1), pp.60-84.
- Allen, T. D., Johnson, R. C., Kiburz, K. M., & Shockley, K. M. (2013). Work–family conflict and flexible work arrangements: Deconstructing flexibility. *Personnel Psychology*, 66(2), pp.345–376.
- Allen, T.D., Cho, E. and Meier, L.L. (2014). Work–family boundary dynamics. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 1(1), pp.99–121.
- Althammer, S. E., Reis, D., van der Beek, S., Beck, L., & Michel, A. (2021). A mindfulness intervention promoting work–life balance: How segmentation preference affects changes in detachment, well-being, and work–life balance. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 94(2), pp.282-308.

- Amiruddin, A. (2019). Mediating effect of work stress on the influence of time pressure, work–family conflict and role ambiguity on audit quality reduction behavior. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 61(2), pp.434-454.
- Ashforth, B.E., Kreiner, G.E. & Fugate, M. (2000). All in a day's work: Boundaries and micro role transitions. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(3), pp.472–491.
- Astuti, R. R., Prabowo, H. and Puspitasari, R. H. U. (2023). The Effect of Compensation and Work-Life Balance on Employee Retention Through Job Satisfaction: Case Study at PT Sandang Asia Maju Abadi Semarang. *Stability: Journal of Management and Business*, 6(1), pp.39–62.
- Bailyn, L. (2011). Redesigning work for gender equity and work–personal life integration. *Community, Work & Family*, 14(1), pp.97–112.
- Bakker, A.B. & Demerouti, E., (2007). The Job Demands–Resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), pp.309–328.
- Bakker, A.B. & Demerouti, E., (2017). Job demands–resources theory: Taking stock and looking forward. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 22(3), pp.273–285.
- Ball, H. L. (2019). Conducting online surveys. *Journal of human lactation*, 35(3), pp.413- 417.
- Barber, L. K., Conlin, A. L., & Santuzzi, A. M. (2019). Workplace telepressure and work– life balance outcomes: The role of work recovery experiences. *Stress and Health*, 35(3), pp.350–362.
- Barriga, M. H. R., Campoverde, A. R., Coello-Montecel, D., Ochoa P. P., & Paredes-Aguirre, M. I. (2021). The influence of work–family conflict on burnout during the COVID-19 pandemic: The effect of teleworking overload. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(19).
- Bataineh, A. K. (2019). Impact of work-life balance, happiness at work, on employee performance. *International Business Research*, 12(2), pp.99-112.
- BBC (2019). *Working hours: Do Britons put in some of the longest in Europe?* [online]. Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-politics-49795179> [Accessed 30th Jan 2020]
- Beauregard, T. A., Adamson, M., Kunter, A., Miles, L., & Roper, I. (2020). Diversity in the work–life interface: introduction to the special issue. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal*.
- Bello, M.B. and Tanko, M. (2020). Work-life balance and employee performance: a conceptual review. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 8(2), pp. 120–126.
- Bernard, H.R. (2011). *Research Methods in Anthropology* (5th ed.). US: AltaMira Press, pp.7
- Bianchi, S. M. (2011). Changing families, changing workplaces. *The Future of Children*, pp.15-36.
- Bird, J. (2019). *Half of UK employees believe their employer should support work-life balance.* [online]. Available at: <https://employeebenefits.co.uk/half-uk-work-life-balance/> [Accessed 30th Jan 2020]
- Blackstone, A. (2012). *Principles of sociological inquiry: Qualitative and quantitative methods.* Saylor Foundation. [online]. Available at: https://saylordotorg.github.io/text_principles-of-sociological-inquiry-qualitative-and-quantitative-methods/ [Accessed 12th April 2021]
- Blackstone, A. (2018). *Principles of sociological inquiry: Qualitative and quantitative methods.* [e-book]. Available at: <https://openlibrary-repo.ecampusontario.ca/jspui/bitstream/123456789/296/1/Principles%20of%20Sociological%20Inquiry.pdf> [Assessed 15th Jun 2020]
- Bloomfield, J. & Fisher, M. J. (2019). Quantitative research design. *Journal of the Australasian Rehabilitation Nurses Association*, 22(2), pp.27-30.
- Boxall, P., & Macky, K. (2016). High-involvement work processes, work intensification and employee wellbeing. *Work, Employment and Society*, 28(6), pp.963–984.

- Boone, H. N., & Boone, D. A. (2012). Analyzing Likert data. *Journal of Extension*, 50(2).
- Brady, J., & Hammer, L. (2022). *Work–Life Interface*. UK: Routledge.
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods* (5th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Brough, P. et al. (2020). Kanungo, R.N., 1982. Measurement of job and work involvement. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 67(3), pp.341–349.
- Brough, P., Timms, C., O'Driscoll, M.P., Kalliath, T. and Siu, O.L. (2020). Work–life balance: A longitudinal evaluation of a new measure across Australia and New Zealand workers. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(17), pp.2189–2210.
- Butcher, S. (2021). What do analysts, associates, VPs, and MDs actually do in investment banks? [online]. Available at: <https://www.efinancialcareers.co.uk/news/finance/banks-weird-hierarchies-analysts-associates-vps-mds-really> [Accessed 20th Mar 2020]
- Byron, K. (2005). A meta-analytic review of work–family conflict and its antecedents. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 67(2), pp.169–198.
- Caesens, G., Stinglhamber, F., Demoulin, S., & De Wilde, M. (2017). Perceived organizational support and employees' well-being: The mediating role of organizational dehumanization. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 26(4), pp.527–540.
- Cameron, S. & Price, D. (2009). *Business Research Methods: A Practical Approach*. London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development
- Camic, P. M. (2021). *Qualitative research in psychology: Expanding perspectives in methodology and design*. US: American Psychological Association.
- Carnevale, J. B., & Hatak, I. (2020). Employee adjustment and well-being in the era of COVID-19: Implications for human resource management. *Journal of business research*, 116, pp.183-187.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Charoensukmongkol, P., & Puyod, J. V. (2021). Influence of transformational leadership on role ambiguity and work–life balance of Filipino University employees during COVID-19: does employee involvement matter? *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, pp.1-20.
- Chen, M. (2019). The impact of expatriates' cross-cultural adjustment on work stress and job involvement in the high-tech industry. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10.
- Chen, Q., Chen, M., Lo, C. K. M., Chan, K. L., & Ip, P. (2022). Stress in Balancing Work and Family among Working Parents in Hong Kong. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(9).
- Chung, H., & Van der Lippe, T. (2020). Flexible working, work–life balance, and gender equality: Introduction. *Social Indicators Research*, 151(2), pp.365-381.
- CIPD (2019). *Brexit impact on workforce trends*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.cipd.co.uk/news-views/brexit-hub/workforce-trends> [Accessed 29th Jan 2020]
- Clark, S.C., (2000). Work/family border theory: A new theory of work/family balance. *Human Relations*, 53(6), pp.747–770.
- Clark, M.A., Michel, J.S. & Baltes, B.B., (2014). Antecedents of work–family conflict: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 35(S1), pp.S45–S76.
- Clarke, M. C., Koch, L. C., & Hill, E. J. (2004). The work–family interface: Differentiating balance and fit. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 33(2), pp.121–140.
- Clarke, S. & Holdsworth, L. (2017). Flexibility in the workplace: Implications of boundary management for wellbeing and work-life balance. *British Journal of Management*, 28(3), pp.513–528.

- Clark, P. (2013). *Stressed out bankers are underpaid and overworked*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.efinancialcareers.co.uk/news/2013/05/stressed-out-bankers-are-underpaid-and-overworked> [Accessed 29th Jan 2020]
- Clark, S.C., Karau, S.J. & Michalisin, M.D., (2021). The impact of age and parental status on perceived work–life conflict and enrichment. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 36(3), pp.182–195.
- Coe, R., Waring, M., Hedges, L. V., & Ashley, L. D. (2021). *Research methods and methodologies in education* (3rd ed.). London: Sage Publications.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. & Morrison, K. (2011). *Research Methods in Education* (7th ed). London: Routledge.
- Cusinato, M., Iannatone, S., Spoto, A., Poli, M., Moretti, C., Gatta, M., & Miscioscia, M. (2020). Stress, resilience, and well-being in Italian children and their parents during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(22).
- David, M. E. (2019). Parental involvement: a feminist critical review from a UK perspective. *Parental Involvement Across European Education Systems: Critical Perspectives*, pp.162.
- de Bloom, J. et al. (2010). Effects of vacation on recovery and health: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 52(4), pp.225–232.
- De Clercq, D., & Brieger, S. A. (2022). When discrimination is worse, autonomy is key: How women entrepreneurs leverage job autonomy resources to find work–life balance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 177(3), pp.665-682.
- Debois (2022). *10 advantages and disadvantages of questionnaires* [online]. Available at: <https://pointerpro.com/blog/questionnaire-pros-and-cons/> [Accessed 10th Mar 2020]
- Department for Work and Pensions (2018). *Economic labour market status of individuals aged 50 and over, trends over time*. [online]. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/747715/economic-labour-market-status-of-individuals-aged-50-and-over-oct-2018.pdf [Accessed 28th Jan 2020]
- Derks, D., van Mierlo, H. and Schmitz, E.B. (2016). A diary study on work-related smartphone use, psychological detachment and exhaustion: Examining the role of the perceived segmentation norm. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 21(4), pp.490–502.
- Dewaele, J.M., (2018). Online questionnaires. In *The Palgrave handbook of applied linguistics research methodology*, pp.269-286. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Diener, E., Oishi, S., & Tay, L. (2018). Advances in subjective well-being research. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 2(4), pp.253-260.
- Diesing, P. (1966). Objectivism vs. Subjectivism in the Social Sciences. *Philosophy of Science*, 33(1/2), pp.124-133.
- Dillman, D. A., Smyth, J. D., & Christian, L. M. (2014) *Internet, phone, mail, and mixed-mode surveys: The tailored design method* (4th ed.). Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
- Dollah, S., Abduh, A., & Rosmaladewi (2017). Benefits and Drawbacks of NVivo QSR Application. *Advanced in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 149, pp.61-63.
- Dufour, I. F., & Richard, M. C. (2019). Theorizing from secondary qualitative data: A comparison of two data analysis methods. *Cogent Education*, 6(1).
- Eddleston, K. A., Sieger, P., and Bernhard, F. (2019). From suffering firm to suffering family? How perceived firm performance relates to managers' work-to-family conflict. *Journal of business research*, 104, pp.307-321.
- Edelman, L. B. (2016). *Working law: Courts, corporations, and symbolic civil rights*. University of Chicago Press.

- Edwards, J.R. & Rothbard, N.P. (2000). Mechanisms linking work and family: Clarifying the relationship between work and family constructs. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(1), pp.178–199.
- Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71(3), 500.
- Elliott, J. H., Synnot, A., Turner, T., Simmonds, M., Akl, E. A., McDonald, S., & Pearson, L. (2017). Living systematic review: 1. Introduction—the why, what, when, and how.’ *Journal of clinical epidemiology*, 91, pp.23-30.
- Emre, O., & De Spiegeleare, S. (2021). The role of work–life balance and autonomy in the relationship between commuting, employee commitment and well-being. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 32(11), pp.2443-2467.
- Ennis, L. & Wykes, T. (2016). Sense and readability: participant information sheets for research studies. *The British of Journal Pschychiatry*, 208(2), pp.189-194.
- Esguerra, I. D. G. (2020). Work-Life Balance and Job Stress of Employees of a Lone Agricultural College in Bulacan, Philippines. *Journal of Business on Hospitality and Tourism*, 6(2), pp.211.
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 1–4.
- Felstead, A. & Henseke, G. (2017). Assessing the growth of remote working and its consequences for effort, well-being and work-life balance. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 32(3), pp.195–212
- Field, A. P. (2018). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Fisher-McAuley, G., Stanton, J., Jolton, J., & Gavin, J. (2003). *Modelling the relationship between work-life balance and organisational outcomes*. Presented at the Annual Conference of the Society for Industrial-Organizational Psychology.
- Frone, M. R. (2003). Work-family balance. *Handbook of Occupational Health Psychology*, pp.143-162.
- Gaber, J. (2020). *Qualitative analysis for planning & policy: Beyond the numbers*. New York: Routledge.
- Giles, C. (2019). *Brexit has cut UK productivity by up to 5%, say BoE*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.ft.com/content/8ab44f8c-cb2e-11e9-af46-b09e8bfe60c0> [Accessed 18th Feb 2020]
- Goertzen, M. J. (2017). *Introduction to quantitative research and data*. Harlow, UK: Pearson Education.
- Gogoi, K., & Baruah, P. (2021). Goal Setting: Its Impact on Employee Outcome. *SCMS Journal of Indian Management*, 18(1), pp.75-86.
- Gómez-Ortiz, O., Rubio, A., Roldán-Barrios, A., Ridao, P., & López-Verdugo, E. I. (2022). Parental stress and life satisfaction: A comparative study of social services users and nonusers from a gender perspective. *Journal of Community Psychology*.
- Goodman, F., Disabato, D., Kashdan, T. B., & Kauffman, S. B. (2018). Measuring well-being: A comparison of subjective well-being and PERMA. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 13(4), pp.321–332.
- Gragnano, A., Simbula, S., & Miglioretti, M. (2020). Work–life balance: weighing the importance of work–family and work–health balance. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(3), pp.907.
- Gray, D. E. (2021). *Doing research in the real world*. London: Sage Publications
- Greenhaus, J.H. and Beutell, N.J. (1985). Sources of conflict between work and family roles. *Academy of Management Review*, 10(1), pp.76–88.
- Greenhaus, J. H., & Beutell, N. J. (1995). Sources of conflict between work and family roles.

- The Academy of Management Review*, 10(1), pp.76-88.
- Greenhaus, J. H., Allen, T. D., & Foley, S. (2006). Work–family balance: Exploration of a concept. *In families and work conference*, Provo, Utah.
- Greenhaus, J.H. & Powell, G.N. (2006). When work and family are allies: A theory of work–family enrichment. *Academy of Management Review*, 31(1), pp.72–92.
- Greenhaus, J. H., Collins, K. M., & Shaw, J. D. (2003). The relation between work–family balance and quality of life.’ *Journal of vocational behaviour*, 63(3), pp.510-531.
- Greenhaus, J.H. and Allen, T.D. (2011). Work–family balance: A review and extension of the literature. *Handbook of Occupational Health Psychology*, pp.165–183.
- Gregory, A. & Milner, S. (2009). Editorial: Work–life balance: A matter of choice? *Gender, Work & Organization*, 16(1), pp.1–13.
- Grzywacz, J. G. and Carlson, D. S. (2007). Conceptualizing Work–Family Balance: Implications for Practice and Research. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 9(4), pp.455-471.
- Guest, D. E. (2017). Human resource management and employee well-being: Towards a new analytic framework. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(1), pp.22–38.
- Gunawan, E.F., Sudarmiati, S. and Churiyah, M. (2024). The Effect of Work-Life Balance and Compensation on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. *International Journal of Business Law and Education*, 2(1), pp.45–58.
- Haar, J. M., Roche, M., & ten Brummelhuis, L. (2018). A daily diary study of work-life balance in managers: Utilizing a daily process model. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 29(18), pp.2659–2681.
- Hammer, L.B., Allen, E. & Grigsby, T.D. (2005). *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 66(2), pp.335–353
- Health and Safety Executive (2021). *Work-related stress, anxiety or depression statistics in Great Britain, 2021*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.hse.gov.uk/statistics/causdis/stress.pdf> [Accessed 20th Mar 2021]
- Hendrie, R. (2018). *How to Find the Perfect Work-Life Balance as a Finance Professional*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.iris.co.uk/blog/how-to-find-the-perfect-work-life-balance-as-a-finance-professional/> [Accessed 20th Mar 2020]
- Hodge, S. R. (2020). *Quantitative research, 1st ed*. London: Routledge.
- Hofäcker, D. & König, S. (2013). Flexibility and work–life conflict in times of crisis: A gender perspective. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 33(9/10), pp.613–635.
- Holden, S., & Sunindijo, R. Y. (2018). Technology, long work hours, and stress worsen work-life balance in the construction industry. *International Journal of Integrated Engineering*, 10(2).
- Hurst, P., & Bird, S. R. (2018). Questionnaires. *Research Methods in Physical Activity and Health*, pp. 93-101.
- Hutagalung, I., Soelton, M., & Octaviani, A. (2020). The role of work life balance for organizational commitment. *Management Science Letters*, 10(15), pp.3693-3700.
- Hutton, G. & Salchi, A. (2021). *Financial services: contribution to the UK economy*. [online]. Available at: <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/SN06193/SN06193.pdf> [Accessed 8th Mar 2020]
- Ilies, R., Lanaj, K., Pluut, H., & Goh, Z. (2018). Intrapersonal and interpersonal need fulfilment at work: Differential antecedents and incremental validity in explaining job satisfaction and citizenship behaviour. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 108, pp.151– 164.
- Inegbedion, H., Inegbedion, E., Peter, A., & Harry, L. (2020). Perception of workload balance and employee job satisfaction in work organisations. *Heliyon*, 6(1).

- Irawanto, D. W., Novianti, K. R., & Roz, K. (2021). Work from home: Measuring satisfaction between work–life balance and work stress during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. *Economies*, 9(3), pp.96.
- Ismail, M., Baki, N. U., & Omar, Z. (2018). The influence of organizational culture and organizational justice on group cohesion as perceived by merger and acquisition employees. *Organizations & Markets in Emerging Economies*, 9(2), pp.233–250.
- Jaharuddin, N. S., & Zainol, L. N. (2019). The impact of work-life balance on job engagement and turnover intention. *The South East Asian Journal of Management*, 13(1), pp.7.
- Jolly, M. (2019). *Sisterhood and After: An Oral History of the UK Women & Liberation Movement*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Jones T. L., Baxter M. A., & Khanduja V. A. (2013). Quick guide to survey research. *Annals of the Royal College of Surgeons of England*, 95(1), pp.5-7.
- Kalliath, P., Kalliath, T., & Chan, C. (2017). Work–family conflict, family satisfaction and employee wellbeing: A comparative study of Australian and Indian social workers. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(3), pp.366–381.
- Kalliath, T. & Brough, P. (2008). Work–life balance: A review of the meaning of the balance construct. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 14, pp.323–327.
- Kaplan, S., DeShon, R., & Tetrick, L. (2017). The bigger picture of employee well-being: its role for individuals, families, and societies. *Society for Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 3(6).
- Keeney, J., Boyd, E.M., Sinha, R., Westring, A.F. & Ryan, A.M. (2013). From “work–family” to “work–life”: Broadening our conceptualization and measurement. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 82(3), pp.221–237.
- Kelliher, C., Richardson, J., and Boiarintseva, G. (2019). All of work? All of life? Reconceptualising work-life balance for the 21st century. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 29(2), pp.97-112.
- Khan, M.A., Aftab, H., Ahmad, I. & Anwar, F. (2023). Impact of role conflict and role ambiguity on job satisfaction: The mediating effect of job stress and moderating effect of Islamic work ethics. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: A Administration and Management*, 23(1), pp.1–12.
- Khateeb, F. R. (2021). Work Life Balance—A Review of Theories, Definitions and Policies. *Cross Culture Management*, pp.27-55.
- Khateeb, S. (2021). Understanding work-life balance: A review of conceptual frameworks. *Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 9(4), pp. 89–102.
- Kibande, L. M., & Kyule, A. (2022). Influence of work life balance on performance at Embu level five hospital. *International Journal of Social Sciences Management and Entrepreneurship (IJSSME)*, 6(1).
- Kim, M. J. (2015). Violations of assumptions in ANOVA: Effects on the robustness and alternatives. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 39(3), pp.3-26.
- Kim, T. K. (2015). T test as a parametric statistic. *Korean Journal of Anesthesiology*, 68(6), pp.540–546.
- Kim, W., Han, S. J., & Park, J. (2019). Is the role of work engagement essential to employee performance or ‘nice to have’? *Sustainability*, 11(4), pp.1050.
- Kindsiko, E. (2018). Multiparadigm Review of Organisational Control: Drawing an Elephant. *Organisational Control in University Management*. Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Kohll, A. (2018). *The Evolving Definition of Work-Life Balance*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/alankohll/2018/03/27/the-evolving-definition-of-work-life-balance/#1fcd87159ed3> [Accessed 28th Jan 2020]
- Kossek, E.E. & Lambert, S.J. (2005). *Work and life integration: Organizational, cultural, and individual perspectives*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Kossek, E. E., Lewis, S., & Hammer, L. B. (2010). Work-life initiatives and organizational change: Overcoming mixed messages to move from the margin to the mainstream.

- Human relations; studies towards the integration of the social sciences*, 63(1), pp.3–19.
- Kossek, E.E. & Michel, J.S. (2011). Flexible work schedules. *Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, pp.535–572.
- Kossek, E.E. & Lautsch, B.A. (2012). Work–family boundary management styles in organizations: A cross-level model. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 2(2), pp.152–171.
- Kossek, E. (2016). Implementing organizational work–life interventions: toward a triple bottom line. *Community, Work & Family*, 19(2), pp.242-256.
- Kossek, E. & Distelberg, B. (2016). Work and family employment policy for a transformed work force: Trends and themes. *Work-Life Policies*. Washington, DC: Urban Institute Press, pp.1–51.
- Kracauer, S. (2022). The Challenge of Qualitative Content Analysis. In *Selected Writings on Media, Propaganda, and Political Communication*, pp.322-332. Columbia University Press.
- Kreiner, G.E. (2006). Consequences of Work-Home Segmentation or Integration: A Person-Environment Fit Perspective. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 27(4), pp.485–507.
- Kulik, L., Shilo-Levin, S. and Liberman, G. (2015). Article Multiple Roles, Role Satisfaction, and Sense of Meaning in Life: An Extended Examination of Role Enrichment Theory. *Journal of Career Assessment* 23(1), pp.137-151.
- Kurtessis, J.N. et al. (2017). Perceived organizational support: A meta-analytic evaluation of organizational support theory. *Journal of Management*, 43(6), pp.1854–1884.
- Lavarda, R. B., & Bellucci, C. F. (2022). Case study as a suitable method to research strategy as practice perspective. *The Qualitative Report*, 27(2), pp.539-554.
- Lawler, E.E. (1971). *Pay and organizational effectiveness: A psychological view*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Leedy, P. & Ormrod, J. E. (2014). *Practical Research Planning and Design* (10th ed). Edinburgh: Pearson Educational Inc.
- Leslie, L. M., King, E. B., & Clair, J. A. (2019). Work-life ideologies: The contextual basis and consequences of beliefs about work and life. *Academy of Management Review*, 44(1), pp.72-98.
- Lewis, S., Gambles, R. and Rapoport, R. (2007). The constraints of a ‘work–life balance’ approach: An international perspective. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 18(3), pp.360–373.
- Litosseliti, L. (2018). *Research methods in linguistics*. USA: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Lonska, J., Mietule, I. & Arbidāne, I., (2022). Employee work-life balance and remote work: Generational differences during COVID-19. *Sustainability*, 14(1), p.485.
- Lovejoy, M., Kelly, E. L., Kubzansky, L. D., & Berkman, L. F. (2021). Work redesign for the 21st century: promising strategies for enhancing worker well-being. *American Journal of Public Health*, 111(10), pp.1787-1795.
- Lupu, I. & Ruiz-Castro, M. (2021). Work and life beyond the 'ideal worker': A dual agenda for the future of work. *Human Relations*, 74(9), pp.1431–1454.
- Makoff, A (2017). *Brexit pressure hitting work-life balance, say quarter of public sector staff* [online]. Available at: <https://www.peoplemanagement.co.uk/news/articles/brexit-pressure-hitting-worklife-balance> [Accessed 28th Jan 2020]
- Marques, V. C., & Berry, G. R. (2021). Enhancing work-life balance using a resilience framework. *Business and Society Review*, 126(3), pp.263-281.
- Marshall, C. (2019). *Telephone Interviews – Advantages and Disadvantages*. [online]. Available at: <https://pmgco.com/blog-telephone-interviews-advantages-and-disadvantages/> [Accessed 16th May 2020]
- Martin, D. (2018). *Britain is revealed to have the WORST work-life balance in Western Europe (and we toil an hour a day longer than the Germans)*. [online]. Available at:

- <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-6344357/UK-worst-work-life-balance-western-Europe-best-Scandinavia.html> [Accessed 25th Jan 2020]
- Matias, M., & Recharte, J. (2021). Links between work–family conflict, enrichment, and adolescent well-being: Parents' and children's perspectives. *Family Relations*, 70(3), pp.840-858.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2013). *Qualitative Research Design: An Interactive Approach* (3rd ed). London: SAGE Publication.
- Mayerl, J. & Urban, D. (2021). Job involvement and its relation to health and well-being: A longitudinal investigation. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 26(4), pp.285–299.
- McAllister, C.P., Harris, J.N., Hochwarter, W.A. & Ferris, G.R. (2022). Social resources in the workplace: Effects of social support on WLB and job performance. *Human Resource Management Review*, 32(1), 100837.
- McCombes, S. (2022). *Sampling Methods | Types, Techniques, & Examples*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.scribbr.co.uk/research-methods/sampling/> [Accessed 20th May 2022].
- McDonald III, B. D., & Hatcher, W. (2022). *Work-Life Balance in Higher Education*. UK: Taylor & Francis.
- McEwan, B. (2020). Sampling and validity. *Annals of the International Communication Association*, 44(3), pp.235-247.
- McNall, L. A., Tombari, J. M., & Brown, M. M. (2021). Exploring how mindfulness links to work outcomes: Positive affectivity and work-life enrichment. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 16(1), pp.167-182.
- Menold, N., & Bogner, K. (2023). Response rates in survey research. In *Survey Methodology Handbook*. Springer.
- Menon, V., & Muraleedharan, A. (2020). Internet-based surveys: relevance, methodological considerations and troubleshooting strategies. *General Psychiatry*, 33(5).
- Meutia, Z., & Mauliza, P. (2022). The Effect Of Work-Life Balance On Job Satisfaction: Literature Review. *Jurnal Mantik*, 5(4), pp.2508-2513.
- Milovanović, M., & Perišić, J. (2020). Advantages and limitations of using in teaching statistics. *Innovations in the Function of Development*, pp.274.
- Milovanović, D. & Perišić, N. (2020) ‘Statistical software comparison in social sciences’, *European Journal of Social Research*, 3(2), pp. 45–56.
- Mohr, C. D., Hammer, L. B., Brady, J. M., Perry, M. L., & Bodner, T. (2021). Can supervisor support improve daily employee well-being? Evidence of supervisor training effectiveness in a study of veteran employee emotions. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 94(2), pp.400-426.
- Molina, J. A. (2021). The work–family conflict: Evidence from the recent decade and lines of future research. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 42(1), pp.4-10.
- Molino, M., Bakker, A.B. & Ghislieri, C. (2020). The role of workaholism in the job demands–resources model. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping*, 33(4), pp.455–469.
- Mora, A., Riera, D., González, C., & Arnedo-Moreno, J. (2017). Gamification: a systematic review of design frameworks. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 29(3), pp.516-548.
- Morris, M. (2019). *How will Britain treat EU citizens after Brexit? They need to know and so does business*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2019/aug/22/britain-eu-citizens-brex-it-business-immigration-policies> [Accessed 29th Jan 2020]
- Nayak, P. D. S. M & Narayan, K. A. (2019). Strength and weakness of online survey. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 24(5), pp.31-38.

- Netemeyer, R.G., Boles, J.S. & McMurrian, R. (1996). Development and validation of work–family conflict and family–work conflict scales. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81(4), pp.400–410.
- Nunnally, J. C., & Bernstein, I. H. (1994). *Psychometric theory* (3rd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- O’Toole, J., and Lawler, E. E. (2007). *The new American workplace*. UK: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Office for National Statistics (2017). *Families and the labour market, England*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/articles/familiesandthelabourmarketengland/2017> [Accessed 28th Jan 2020]
- Office for National Statistics (2018). *Living longer: how our population is changing and why it matters*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/birthsdeathsandmarriages/aging/articles/livinglongerhowourpopulationischangingandwhyitmatters/2018-08-13> [Accessed 28th Jan 2020]
- Office for National Statistics (2019). *How would you support our ageing population?* [online]. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/birthsdeathsandmarriages/aging/articles/howwouldyousupportourageingpopulation/2019-06-24> [Accessed 28th Jan 2020]
- Oludayo, A. O., & Omonijo, D. O. (2020). Work-life Balance: Relevance of social support. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 9(3), pp.1-10.
- Oludayo, O. A., Falola, H. O., Obianuju, A., & Demilade, F. (2018). Work-life balance initiative as a predictor of employees’ behavioural outcomes. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 17(1), pp.1-17.
- Ormston, R., Spencer, L., Barnard, M., & Snape, D. (2014). The foundations of qualitative research. *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*, 2(7), pp.52-55.
- Otken, A. B., & Erben, G. S. (2013). The relationship between work-life balance and happiness from the perspectives of generation X and Y. *Humanities and Social Sciences Review*, 2(4), pp.45-53.
- Pak, S., Kramer, A., Lee, Y., & Kim, K. J. (2022). The impact of work hours on work-to-family enrichment and conflict through energy processes: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 43(4), pp.709-743.
- Park, J. & Park, M. (2016). Qualitative versus quantitative research methods: Discovery or justification? *Journal of Marketing Thought*, 2(16), pp.23-37.
- Patten, M. L. & Newhart, M. (2017). *Understanding research methods: An overview of the essentials*. New York: Taylor & Francis.
- Penalver, A. J. B. (2018). Subjectivism of Information. *Handbook of Research on Knowledge Management for Contemporary Business Environments*, pp.212-226.
- Perrigino, M. B., Dunford, B. B., & Wilson, K. S. (2018). Work–family backlash: The “dark side” of work–life balance (WLB) policies. *Academy of Management Annals*, 12(2), pp.600-630.
- Perry, M. L., & Hammer, L. B. (2017). Work and Family. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Psychology*. Oxford University Press.
- Plonsky, L. (2017). *Quantitative Research Methods*. London: Routledge
- Porra, J., Hirschheim, R., & Parks, M. S. (2014). The historical research method and information systems research. *Journal of the association for information systems*, 15(9), pp.3.
- Powell, G. N., Greenhaus, J. H., Allen, T. D., & Johnson, R. E. (2019). Introduction to special topic forum: Advancing and expanding work-life theory

- Pulla, V., & Carter, E. (2018). Employing interpretivism in social work research. *International Journal of Social Work and Human Services Practice*, 6(1), pp.9-14.
- Puspitasari, A. S. A., & Darwin, M. (2021). Effect of work-life balance and welfare level on millennial employee performance through work engagement. *International Journal of Science and Society*, 3(1), pp.334-344.
- Putri, A., & Amran, A. (2021). Employees Work-Life Balance Reviewed From Work From Home Aspect During COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Management Science and Information Technology*, 1(1), pp.30-34.
- Rahman, M. S. (2020). The advantages and disadvantages of using qualitative and quantitative approaches and methods in language “testing and assessment” research: A literature review. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(1).
- Rahman, A. (2021). Advantages and disadvantages of using Excel and SPSS for statistical analysis in research. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 8(6), 60–63.
- Raja, S. & Stein, S.L. (2014). Work–Life Balance: History, Costs, and Budgeting for Balance. *Clinics in Colon and Rectal Surgery*, 27(2), pp.71-74.
- Rehman, J. (2021). *What are advantages and disadvantages of spreadsheets*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.itrelease.com/2021/11/what-are-advantages-and-disadvantages-of-spreadsheets/> [Accessed 20th Jun 2020]
- Rodríguez-Sánchez, J. L., González-Torres, T., Montero-Navarro, A., & Gallego-Losada, R. (2020). Investing time and resources for work–life balance: The effect on talent retention. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(6).
- Rofcanin, Y., Las Heras, M., Bal, P.M. & Bosch, M.J. (2019). How do inclusive leaders help to reduce turnover in diverse groups? The moderating role of leader–member exchange in the diversity to turnover relationship. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(17), pp. 2583–2603.
- Rook, C., O’Brien, A., & Adarves-Yorno, I. (2020). What are the key components of workplace well-being?: examining real-life experiences in different work contexts. *The Palgrave Handbook of Workplace Well-Being*, pp.1-26.
- Rooney, C., and Gray, J. (2019). Changing family dynamics and in-work benefits. *Social Policy and Society*, pp.1-21.
- Rothbard, N. P., Beetz, A. M., & Harari, D. (2021). Balancing the scales: A configurational approach to work-life balance. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 8, pp.73-103.
- Ruggeri, K., Garcia-Garzon, E., Maguire, Á., Matz, S., & Huppert, F. A. (2020). Well-being is more than happiness and life satisfaction: a multidimensional analysis of 21 countries. *Health and quality of life outcomes*, 18(1), pp.1-16.
- Ruggiano, N., & Perry, T. E. (2019). Conducting secondary analysis of qualitative data: Should we, can we, and how? *Qualitative Social Work*, 18(1), pp.81-97.
- Ruthless Research (2017). *Reasons to position your demographic section at the end of a survey*. [online]. Available at: <https://ruthlessresearch.wordpress.com/2017/09/04/reasons-to-position-your-demographic-section-at-the-end-of-a-survey/#:~:text=Essentially%2C%20if%20you%20put%20the,complete%20data%20and%20happier%20respondents> [Accessed 20th Apr 2020]
- Ryan, G. (2018). Introduction to positivism, interpretivism and critical theory. *Nurse researcher*, 25(4), pp.41-49.
- Sánchez-Hernández, M. I., González-López, Ó. R., Buenadicha-Mateos, M., & Tato-Jiménez, J. L. (2019). Work-life balance in great companies and pending issues for engaging new generations at work.’ *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(24), pp.5122.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research methods for business students*.

UK: Pearson Education.

- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research methods for business students* (8th ed.). Pearson Education Limited.
- Savela, T. (2018). The advantages and disadvantages of quantitative methods in schoolscape research. *Linguistics and Education*, 44, pp.31-44.
- Schaufeli, W.B. & Taris, T.W. (2014). A critical review of the Job Demands-Resources Model: Implications for improving work and health. *Bridging Occupational, Organizational and Public Health*, pp.43–68.
- Schieman, S. & Glavin, P. (2008). Trouble at the border? Gender, flexibility at work, and the work–home interface. *Social Problems*, 55(4), pp.590–611.
- Sheikh, M. A., Ashiq, A., Mehar, M. R., Hasan, A., & Khalid, M. (2018). Impact of work and home demands on work life balance: Mediating role of work family conflicts. *Journal of Business and Finance Management Research*, 4(5), pp.48–57.
- Shi, Y., Li, D., Zhang, N., Jiang, P., Yuling, D., Xie, J., & Yang, J. (2022). Job crafting and employees' general health: the role of work–nonwork facilitation and perceived boundary control. *BMC Public Health*, 22(1), pp.1-12.
- Shimazu, A. & Schaufeli, W.B. (2009). Is workaholism good or bad for employee well-being? The distinctiveness of workaholism and work engagement among Japanese employees. *Industrial Health*, 47(5), pp.495–502.
- Sileyew, K. J. (2019). *Research design and methodology*. Rijeka: IntechOpen, pp.11-12.
- Singh, R., Zhang, Y., Wan, M., & Fouad, N. A. (2018). Why do women engineers leave the engineering profession? The roles of work–family conflict, occupational commitment, and perceived organizational support. *Human Resource Management*, 57(4), pp.901–914.
- Sirgy, M. J., & Lee, D. J. (2018). Work-life balance: An integrative review. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 13(1), pp.229-254.
- Sisk, A. (2018). *What Are the Advantages & Disadvantages of Interviews?* [online]. Available at: <https://bizfluent.com/about-7536454-advantages-disadvantages-interviews.html> [Accessed 30th Feb 2021]
- Sonnentag, S. & Fritz, C. (2006). Recovery, health, and job performance: Effects of weekend experiences. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 11(3), pp.187–199.
- Sonnentag, S. & Fritz, C. (2007). The recovery experience questionnaire. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 12(3), pp.204–221.
- Sonnentag, S. & Fritz, C. (2015). Recovery from job stress: The stressor–detachment model as an integrative framework. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 36(S1), pp.S72–S103.
- Spector, P. E. (2019). Do not cross me: Optimizing the use of cross-sectional designs. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 34(2), pp.125-137.
- Statista (2019). *Countries with the Worst Work-Life Balance*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/chart/12997/countries-with-the-worst-work-life-balance/> [Accessed 28th Jan 2020]
- Statista (2022). *Number of employees in the financial services sector in the United Kingdom (UK) from 2001 to 2021*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/298370/uk-financial-sector-total-financial-services-employment/> [Accessed 18th Jan 2022]
- Sturges, J., and Guest, D. (2004). Working to live or living to work? Work/life balance early in the career. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 14(4), pp.5-20.
- Submtter, G. A. T. R., Bello, Z., & Tanko, G. I. (2020). Review of work-life balance theories. *Journals and Bello, Zainab and Tanko, Garba Ibrahim, Review of Work-Life Balance Theories*, pp.217-227.

- Talukder, A. M. H. (2019). Supervisor support and organizational commitment: The role of work–family conflict, job satisfaction, and work–life balance. *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 56(3), pp.98-116.
- Tims, M., Derks, D. & Bakker, A.B. (2022). Job crafting and its daily benefits. *Applied Psychology*, 71(1), pp.131–152.
- Toor, M. (2020). *Demographic survey questions that yield valuable insight*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.qualtrics.com/blog/demographic-survey-questions/> [Accessed 18th Apr 2020]
- Tuboly, A. T. (2022). Making Logical Positivism Less Logical: The Case of Schlick and von Mises. *The Socio-Ethical Dimension of Knowledge*, pp.105-125.
- Turner, D. P. (2020). Sampling Methods in Research Design. *The Journal of Head and Face Pain*, 60(1), pp.8-12.
- Twenge, J. M. (2010). Generational differences in work values: Leisure and extrinsic values increasing, social and intrinsic values decreasing. *Journal of Management*, 36(5), pp.1117–1142.
- Tyrer, S. & Heyman, B. (2016). Sampling in epidemiological research: issues, hazards and pitfalls. *BJPsych Bulletin*, 40(2), pp.57-60.
- UK Government (2020). *Employment in the UK: March 2020: Estimates of employment, unemployment and economic inactivity for the UK*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/bulletins/employmentintheuk/march2020> [Accessed 1th Mar 2020]
- UK Parliament (2021). *Financial services: contribution to the UK economy* [online]. Available at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/sn06193/> [Accessed 18th Jan 2020]
- UK Parliament (2021). *Housing an ageing population: a reading list*. [online]. Available at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-9239/> [Accessed 18th Jan 2022]
- Van Steenbergen, E.F. & Ellemers, N. (2009). Is managing the work–family interface worthwhile? *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 30(5), pp.617–642.
- Vasumathi, A. (2018). Work life balance of women employees: a literature review. *International Journal of Services and Operations Management*, 29(1), pp.100-146.
- Vu, T. T. N. (2021). Understanding validity and reliability from qualitative and quantitative research traditions. *VNU Journal of Foreign Studies*, 37(3).
- Walker, I. (2017). *Research methods and statistics*. Harlow, UK: Pearson Education.
- Waugh, S. (2022). Evaluation of a Quantitative Research Article.’ *Business, Technology, Management & Innovation*, 1(2).
- Wayne, J.H., Matthews, R.A., Crawford, W.S. & Casper, W.J. (2017). Predicting employee well-being through work and family support. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 100, pp.66–78.
- Westrupp, E. M., Strazdins, L., Martin, A., Cooklin, A., Zubrick, S. R., & Nicholson, J. M. (2016). Maternal Work–Family Conflict and Psychological Distress: Reciprocal Relationships Over 8 Years. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 78(1), pp.107–126.
- Wilcock, A., & Wright, M. (1991). Quality of work life in the knitwear sector of the Canadian textile industry. *Public Personnel Management*, 20(4), pp.457-468.
- Wilcox, J. (2020). Work–life balance. *Heart*, 106(16), pp.1276-1277.
- Wöhrmann, A. M., Dilchert, N., & Michel, A. (2021). Working time flexibility and work-life balance. *Zeitschrift für Arbeitswissenschaft*, 75(1), pp.74-85.
- Wood, J., Oh, J., Park, J., & Kim, W. (2020). The relationship between work engagement and work–life balance in organizations: A review of the empirical research. *Human Resource Development Review*, 19(3), pp.240-262.

- Wu, C., Hunter, Y. M., Sublett, L. W. (2021). Gaining affective resources for work-family enrichment: A multisource experience sampling study of micro-role transitions. *Journal of Vocational Behavior, 125*.
- Yadav, R., Khanna, A., & Chenab. (2022). Quality of work life, emotional and physical well-being of police personnel in India. *International Journal of Police Science & Management, 24*(1), pp.89-99.
- Zahoor, N., Abdullah, N., & Zakaria, N. (2021). The role of high performance work practices, work-family conflict, job stress and personality in affecting work life balance. *Management Science Letters, 11*(4), pp.1367-1378.
- Zamawe, F. C. (2015). The Implication of Using NVivo Software in Qualitative Data Analysis: Evidence-Based Reflections. *Malawi Medical Journal, 27*(1).
- Zhang, J., Chen, X. & Fan, J. (2023). Exploring the mechanism between work-family enrichment and job satisfaction: A moderated mediation model. *Current Psychology*.
- Zheng, X., Zhu, W., Zhao, H., & Zhang, C. (2015). Employee well-being in organizations: Theoretical model, scale development, and cross-cultural validation. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour, 36*(5), pp.621-644.
- Ziegenfuss, J. Y., Easterday, C. A., Dinh, J. M., JaKa, M. M., Kottke, T. E., & Canterbury, M. (2021). Impact of demographic survey questions on response rate and measurement: A randomized experiment. *Survey Practice, 14*(1).
- Zyphur, M. J., & Pierides, D. C. (2020). Making quantitative research work: From positivist dogma to actual social scientific inquiry. *Journal of Business Ethics, 167*(1), pp.49- 62.

APPENDIX A

Survey Questionnaire

Section 1. Experiences of Work-life Balance

1. How difficult was it for you to balance your work life and personal life while working?
Using the 1-5 scale, please indicate your agreement by ticking the most appropriate box.

Extremely difficult

Not at all difficult

2. How much time do you spend on leisure activities every day?

- Less than 1 hour
 1-5 hour
 More than 5 hours
 Not at all

3. I am expected to work long hours

- Never
 Rarely
 Sometimes
 Usually
 Always

4. I am asked to work overtime

- Never
 Rarely
 Sometimes
 Usually
 Always

5. I am asked to work during the holidays.

- Never
 Rarely
 Sometimes
 Usually
 Always

6. I am asked to work longer hours for no extra pay

- Never
 Rarely

- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

7. Do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
"I am satisfied with the workplace flexibility offered by my organisation"					
"The demands of my family interfere with work-related activities"					
"I prioritise my job over my personal life"					
"I prioritise my family over my work"					
"I am able to set boundaries between my work and personal life"					
"It is easy for me to find time for hobbies and interests"					

8. My home life interferes with your responsibilities such as getting to work on time, accomplishing daily tasks, and working overtime.

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

9. Do you suffer from stress related diseases like hypertension or do you engage yourself in stress relieving program?

- Yes
- No

10. How would you rate the following as upsetting a work life balance?

	Always influence	Usually influence	Sometimes influence	Rarely influence	Never influence
Working overtime					
Working longer hours					
Working from home					
Working from home after office hours					
Working remotely during Corona virus					
Working on holiday					
Travelling on work trip					

11. Please rate how successful you feel you are at maintaining a healthy work/personal/family life balance.

Extremely successful

Not at all

12. In order to keep a healthy work-life balance, what do you think you would change to make your life better? Please indicate your agreement by ticking the most appropriate box.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Spending time with my family makes me feel better.					
Prioritising my health would make me feel better					
Taking regular short holiday would make me feel better.					
Taking a long holiday would make me feel better.					
Talking to my employer to set work boundaries can improve my wellbeing.					

13. Pick one of the following, which do you think your employer could do that would improve your work-life balance the most.

- Flexible working hours
- Parent's friendly working conditions
- More generous holiday allowance
- Restricted working hours
- Restricted overtime agreements
- Organise more stress living-relieving social events/activities
- Reduce the number of stressful tasks given
- Monitor work-related stress
- Pay increase

Section 2. Work History

14. Which of the following categories best describes your employment status?

- Employed, working full-time
- Employed, working part-time
- Self-employed
- Unemployed
- Retired

15. How many years of work experience do you have?

- No work experiences
- Less than 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-9 years
- More than 10 years

16. What sector is the most of your working experience in?

- Accountancy/Finance
- Business Management/Consulting
- Retail
- Teaching/Education
- Marketing/Digital Media
- Healthcare

- Hospitality
- IT (Information Technology)
- None of the above

17. What is the most senior role do you have?

- Executive
- Manager
- Operations/Production
- Sales Representative
- Customer Services

Section 3. Biographical Information

18. What is your age?

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- Over 65

19. What is your gender?

- Female
- Male

20. Do you have any children? If Yes, please go to Question 22.

- Yes
- No

21. If Yes, how many children do you have?

- 1 child
- 2 children
- 3 children
- 4 children
- More than 4 children

APPENDIX B

Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Study title

The impact of work-life balance on employee performance and well-being across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments.

Dear Participant,

You are invited to participate in the research study described below. Please take some time to read through the following information.

What is the study about?

You have been invited to take part in a DBA research study analysing the impact of work-life balance on employee performance and well-being across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environments.

Why am I being invited to participate?

You are being invited to participate in this research due to your involvement with a confidential and anonymous online survey which will take approximately 10-15 minutes.

The online survey will be divided into 3 sections. First, you will be asked questions about your experiences of work-life balance, and how difficulties you find to keep balance your work and personal life. Secondly, some questions related to your work history will be mentioned. Finally, once you are familiar with the questionnaires from sections 1 and 2, you will be asked questions about biographical information at the end that make you not feel awkward.

How much time will the research take?

The length of the online questionnaires might change depending on the participants. It is generally expected to last between 10 to 15 minutes.

What happens to the information in the study?

All questionnaires will be completed anonymously; the researcher will not know who has completed each questionnaire. The research will only be seen by the researcher and the researcher's supervisor.

The responses you provide may be used in the researcher's final year dissertation. All information collected from you will be destroyed within 18 months of the research taking place, with the exception of the facts printed.

If I agree to complete a questionnaire now, can I change my mind?

Yes, you are able to withdraw from the questionnaire at any time throughout completion. Simply do not submit the questionnaire and shut down your web browser. You are free to return and complete the questionnaire at any time.

How will I be able to get in touch with the researcher?

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me at:

Date: 18th January 2021

Consent Form

CONSENT FORM

Thank you very much for agreeing to participate in this survey.

You are invited to participate in a web-based online survey on the impacts of work-life balance on employee performance and their wellbeing across different age groups, parental statuses, and work environment. This is a research project being conducted by Linh Pham, a student at the University of the West of Scotland. It should take approximately 10 minutes to complete the questions.

The information provided by you in this questionnaire will be used for research purposes. It will not be used in any manner, which would allow the identification of your individual responses. No names or identifying information would be included in any publications or presentations based on these data, and your responses to this survey will remain confidential.

Declaration of Content

Please
initial
box

1. I confirm that I have read the Participant Information Sheet for the above study.
I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw myself or my data at any time, without giving any reason, and without any adverse or consequences.

3. I understand that the information collected about me, who will be anonymous, will be used to support other research in the future.

4. I understand who will have access to personal data provided.

5. I understand that my personal data, which link me to the research data, will be kept securely in accordance with data protection guidelines.

6. I agree to take part in the above study.

Date

Signature

